

**PILOTs for robotic INspection and maintenance
Grounded on advanced intelligent platforms and
prototype applications**

Deliverable D8.2

**PILOTING: Final Pilot Experiments
- Results, Training sessions and Evaluation -**

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Acronyms

Abbreviation	Explanation
AESA	Agencia Estatal de Seguridad Aérea (Spanish for “State Agency for Aviation Safety”)
AI	Artificial Intelligence
API	Application Programming Interface
A-SCAN	An Ultrasound Scan
ASME	American Society of Mechanical Engineers
ATEX	ATmosphères EXplosives (French for "Explosive Atmospheres") - Common name for Directive 2014/34/EU
CNOA	Centre Nationale Opérationnel Aérien (French for “National Air Operations Centre”)
CTR	Controlled Traffic Region
DDHL	Data Distribution and Harmonization Layer
DMS	Data Management System
DSAC	Direction de la Sécurité de l’Aviation Civile (French for “Directorate of Civil Aviation Safety”)
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
GCS	General Control Station
GNSS	Global Navigation Satellite System
gRCS	general Robot Control Station
HD	High Definition
HMI	Human Machine Interface
I&M	Inspection and Maintenance
ICT	Information Communication Technologies
ID	Identification
IMU	Inertial Measurements Unit

IoT	Internet of Things
IVP	Intelligence and Visualization Portal
JSA	Job Site Analysis
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LEL	Lower Explosion Limit
LIDAR	Light Detection and Ranging
MB	Megabyte
MQTT	Message Queuing Telemetry Transport
mRCS	mission-specific Robot Control Station
MTOW	Maximum Take-Off Weight
NDT	Non-Destructive Testing
NE	North East
NW	North West
POI	Point of Interest
PV	Pressure Vessel
RMCP	Robotic Mobile Contact Platform
RMSE	Root mean squared error
SLAM	Simultaneous Localization and Mapping
TEB	Timed-Elastic-Bands
TLX	Task Load Index
TRL	Technological Readiness Level
UAS	Unmanned Aircraft System
UAV	Unmanned Aerial Vehicle
UGV	Unmanned Ground Vehicle
UT	Ultrasonic Testing

UTM	Unmanned Traffic Management
UWB	Ultra-Wideband
VLOS	Visual Line Of Sight
VT	Visual Testing
WP	Work Package
WSN	Wireless Sensor Network

1. Introduction

1.1. Purpose of the document

Following the final integration of the PILOTING I&M platform and services with each of the robotic solutions in mid 2023, this document serves to report the results of the final round of experiments with the integrated PILOTING system in each of the pilot scenarios (refinery, viaduct and tunnel). See Table 1 for a list of all the executed pilot experiments.

Table 1. Pilot experiments performed during the first PILOTING validation phase.

Pilot Demonstrations	Use Cases	Responsible partner-Assigned robot(s)
Refinery pilot case Pilot demonstration (2 nd phase) 18-22/9/2023	Tank Large Structure Inspection	CATEC (AEROX)
	Tank Local Visual Inspection	CATEC (AEROCAM)
	Pipe Inspection	CATEC/WTR (HYBRID)
	Pressure Vessel Inspection	WTR (BIKE)
	Ground Monitoring	ROBOTNIK (WATCHER) & ETHZ (UGV)
Viaduct pilot case Pilot demonstration (2 nd phase) 6-17/11/2023 ¹	Visual Inspection	CATEC (AEROCAM)
	Installation of survey targets, bearing inspections and sensor installations	USE (VIAD-DRONE)
Tunnel pilot case Pilot demonstration (2 nd phase) 25/9-6/11/2023	General Inspection	ROBOTNIK (CART)
	Local Inspection	ROBOTNIK (CART) & USE (TT-DRONE)

Moreover, this document analyses the fulfilment of the Key Performance indicators, or KPI's, defined in deliverable D3.2, and also the validation during the pilot experiments of the original project requirements per use case.

A short description of the training sessions performed during the experiments, along with a assessment of the developed HMI interfaces has been also included.

¹ Plus three more weeks of technological pilot experiments that were performed between June and October 2023.

Finally, the document also identifies best practices, as well as opportunities for improvement for future exploitation of the technologies.

1.2. Scope of the document

This document contains the results of the work performed in WP8 during the second and final development and experimental cycle of the project. As it was considered in the project planning, PILOTING considers two development and experimental cycles in order to be able to gain experience in the first cycle, and apply the identified improvements and lessons learnt in the second one. Then, this document describes the project results from the second and final experimental cycle for the three considered pilot scenarios.

1.3. Structure of the document

The document is organized to report out the site experiment results from Refineries (Section 2), Viaducts (Section 3) and Tunnels (Section 4).

Section 5 provides a summary of the evaluation of the KPI's originally defined in deliverable D3.2, and the validation of the original project requirements (deliverable D3.1). While the traceability matrices with the original project requirements are shown in Annex I: Requirements Validation.

Section 6 presents a summary of the performed training sessions during the second set of experiments. This section presents the results of the assessment of the developed HMIS (IVP and gRCS) using NASA TLX methodology.

Finally, Section 77. provides a summary of best practices and lessons learned derived from the execution of the pilot experiments followed by the conclusions (Section 8).

The deliverable is completed with the following Annexes:

- Annex I: Requirements Validation. Validation matrices of the original project requirements.
- Annex II: Generic safety template (required during the final review meeting).
- Annex III: Report on the impact of previous European projects into PILOTING.

2. Refinery experiments and results

2.1. Description of Refinery Location

Chevron Oronite site is located in the north of France in Gonfreville L'Orcher near the port of Le Havre. It is a live industrial facility, Europe's largest additive manufacturing facility. As the plant processes hydrocarbon products, some areas of the plant are rated as explosive atmosphere (ATEX) zones. For the purpose of the experiments as part of this project, all testing will be carried out in safe zones with no ATEX regulations.

The plant is a large industrial complex which offers multiple opportunities to test inspection procedures at height making it an ideal candidate for the PILOTING project, addressing a wide range of inspection categories such as large structure inspection, inspection of pipework at height, internal vessel inspection, ground monitoring and manipulation of equipment.

Figure 1. A general view of the Chevron Oronite Plant.

Testing for all refinery work scopes was conducted in the northern part of the Oronite plant split over four main work areas: 1. The Tank farm; 2. The water treatment plant; 3. A decommissioned module; 4. A pressure vessel.

- **The tank farm** offered access to a large storage tank to conduct UT inspection at height.
- **The water treatment plant** offered up two work areas. A ground level pipe rack to conduct UT inspection on pipe work and some pipelines in constant use for the IoT vibration sensors (wireless sensors network) for leak detection.
- **A decommissioned process module** offered up two work areas, a congested facility for ground monitoring work scopes (navigation and manipulation) and additionally it offered up an area for inspection imagery at height for AI defect recognition (corrosion) work scopes. The decommissioned module also offered an area to perform autonomous pipe landing and takeoff.
- **A pressure vessel** offered up a work area for testing inspection capabilities in a confined space.

Figure 2. Map of inspection areas in Oronite plant.

Table 2. Environmental conditions experience during week of testing.

Environmental conditions	
temperature	~20 deg C ambient temp.
light conditions	Natural lighting. Overcast for most of the week with occasional sun. Sky mostly cloudy.
humidity	Approx 60% humidity
wind velocity (potentially not that important as not flying)	6-13 knots
wind direction (same as above)	East-Northeast

2.1.1. Flight Authorisation process

FADA-CATEC is a registered Spanish UAS operator. These flights cannot be included into ‘Open’ category, due airspace restrictions and specific local ground considerations for industrial areas. Therefore, a flight authorization process for ‘Specific’ category was requested.

Figure 3. Restriction area for Open category around Chevron Oronite.

As these flights scenario is set in France, a Cross-Border authorization was required, in order to get the flight permits, which requires two steps:

- 1- AESA documental inspection and authorisation of the flight operation, as aeronautical authority from the country of origin of the operator.
- 2- DSAC verification of this authorisation, checking local conditions and zonification, as authority from the destination country for the proposed flights.

Operational authorisation for the ‘Specific’ category has been issued by AESA, Spanish aeronautical authority, for these flight operations, with “ESP-OA-00019/000” number.

Confirmation acceptability from DSAC has “FRA-CBO-2022FADA001/000” number.

Figure 4. Aeronautical chart Chevron Oronite area.

In addition, some more specific and local authorisations were needed for these flight operations. Flights were planned in the prohibited airspace P-28, and inside the HAROPA port area:

- CNOA P-28 access Authorisation, with number “**220819-P28-1202-1248**”
- HAROPA port – DT Le Havre: Authorisation number “**2022-SPS-158**”

All these flight authorizations were obtained on time. It is important to point out that these flight authorizations are the same as the ones required by commercial aerial works, which it is a major milestone to facilitate the future exploitation of the developed technologies.

2.2. Refinery Large Structure (Tank) Inspection

In standard oil refineries, corrosion poses a risk, making wall thickness measurements critical. Chevron chose AeroX to perform ultrasonic readings on a large tank at Oronite. See Table 3 for a detailed description of the tank, and Figure 5 for a general view of the field setup.

Table 3. Description of the tank inspected by AeroX.

Tank conditions	
Tank material	Carbon steel.
Wall plate thickness	8.18mm nominal thickness.
Coating material and thickness	Unknown thickness. Most likely 2-3 coats/layers.
Other equipment or obstructions present	No major obstructions.
Pipe elevation	Base of accessible tank wall, approximately 1.4m above ground level. Tank height approx. 20m.

Figure 5. AeroX experiment setup at the tank farm.

During last year's experiments, both gRCS integration and the Leica-based position estimator were successfully demonstrated. However, the need for a more accurate measuring method became evident. Consequently, this year, it was made a priority to finally validate AeroX's ultrasonic data. Both Figure 6 and Figure 7 emphasize the previous statements, showing a comparison between measurements taken by a plant technician and AeroX's output data. As you will see in Table 4, the platform successfully accomplished its ultrasonic testing validation.

Regarding flight operations, the weather was far from favorable. With sporadic rain and gusts of wind reaching up to 15m/s, the opportunity for a complete mission only presented itself once (mission_20231019083005 in the IVP) throughout the entire week. It's important to note that RLS-Op-03, RLS-Op-04, and RLS-Op-05 (D3.1) stipulate a MUST of 5m/s, a SHOULD of 8m/s, and a COULD of 13m/s, respectively. As outlined further in this section, Figure 10 demonstrates that this year's mission followed a significantly shorter flight path compared to what was achieved last year. This deliberate decision was made to avoid pushing the time window beyond its limits.

Figure 6. Selecting test points to validate the UT measurements on the tank plate.

Figure 7. Manually placing the AeroX to validate the measurements.

Note the significant improvement in accuracy compared to the 2022 results presented in Table 4 (reference points visible in Figure 6). The error margins have reduced by two orders of magnitude, with the maximum error decreasing from 0.400mm to 0.008mm. This remarkable enhancement in accuracy can be attributed to two distinct lines of effort, addressing hardware and software revisions, respectively.

Table 4. Results of AeroX UT measurements against hand tool measurements.

Tank plate UT measurement validation				
# 2023 Points		Manual reading (mm)	AeroX’s reading (mm)	Measured gap (mm)
1	Top	8.11	8.109	0.001
2	Bottom	8.08	8.079	0.001
3	Right	8.13	8.138	0.008
# 2022 Points ²		Manual reading (mm)	AeroX’s reading (mm)	Measured gap (mm)
1	Left of weld	8.3	7.9	0.4
2	Right of weld	8.2	7.9	0.3
3	Mid plate	8.5	8.2	0.3

With the measurements now validated, our objective was to demonstrate the platform’s positional repeatability in comparison to last year’s inspection plan. To establish a consistent frame of reference as in 2022, three targets conveniently positioned from the previous year were relocated and utilized to align the tracking data with millimetric precision. This feature is built into the Leica total station. However, if the targets were removed from the site, the same outcome could be achieved by aligning a new point cloud of the asset. Figure 8 illustrates the Leica targets remaining in the same position across missions.

Figure 8. AeroX in front of the tank, 2022 (left) and 2023 (right) respectively. Markers visible are the same.

² Testing points do not share the same location between testing phases. Note that in contrast with last year, phase 2 points do not refer to any given weld.

Figure 9. AeroX platform performing a line scan, 2022 (top) and 2023 (bottom) respectively.

Figure 10 illustrates the difference in the inspection line between the current year and the previous one. As you may have noticed, this distance can also be visually confirmed using real-world photos (Figure 9), where they share about one meter of separation.

Figure 10. Visualization of 2022 (left) and 2023 (right) missions, respectively.

In correlation with the hand-held ultrasonic validation, the measurements taken from the tank exhibited a noticeable increase in cohesiveness compared to last year's results. All in all, we successfully validated the pending issue with the ultrasonic measurements and once again demonstrated the platform's capability to revisit the same asset with the same reference system.

However, this time, the inspection location was slightly moved to the left (from Figure 10 perspective), akin to continuing an inspection.

2.3. Refinery Pipe Inspection

Definition of landing point

Although the original HYBRID inspection area was the Water Holding Pipes, we decide to carry out the experiments at the Decom Zone where the pipe distribution was more suitable for landing. This zone had few ideal pipes for the experiments at 5m height with enough separation to be safe. It also contains a wide-open area used for takeoff and landing.

Figure 11. Environment of the Decom Zone with tentative pipes.

After analyzing the best area for the operation, the outermost upper rack pipe was chosen. In Table 5 it has compiled a set of relevant information from the pipeline on which the HYBRID platform has been landed.

Table 5. Description of the inspection area for HYBRID.

Plant / Area description	
Plant	Oronite additives plant in Gonfreville, France
Experiment area	Decom Zone

Pipework	
Pipe material	Oronite additives plant in Gonfreville, France
Diameter and thickness	12 Inch Schedule 40 (9.525 mm nominal thickness)

Coating material and thickness	Unknown thickness. Most likely 2-3 coats/layers.
Parallel pipe distance separation	Minimum 300 mm.
Parallel pipe characteristics	Similar pipe parallel to this at the same height.
Other equipment or obstructions present	No major obstructions.
Pipe elevation	5 m above ground level approx..

Once the landing zone and the target pipe has been selected, a 3D model of the environment was created with a total station. In this way, the landing point could be defined on this map and thus integrated into the PILOTING platform.

Figure 12. On the left, selected pipe to land. On the right, 3D map created with a total station.

A single Inspection Plan with an Inspection Point was defined. This inspection point will be the desired landing point of the HYBRID platform. This point will be downloaded and refined in the mission manager, as will be shown later. This desired landing point is shown in Figure 13.

Figure 13. Inspection Location in the IVP.

Landing procedure

Figure 14 shows the safe area set up by CATEC in the Decom area. Within this area, the appropriate detectors were placed to make it a safety area, as well as the minimum distance to the aircraft. In this way we ensured that the operation was as safe as possible.

Figure 14. CATEC team and setup of the safe working area.

On the previous experiments, due to safety reasons, we decided not to fly HYBRID and instead we focused on the UT satellite crawler robot for taking UT thickness measurements. However, for the last experiments, we developed a new aerial platform concept in addition with a new control mode which allowed us to perform landing on pipes safely. Thanks to this improvement, we were able to perform real flights on site.

In the Figure 15 is shown a comparative between two versions of HYBRID. Having a look to both, the previous and new HYBRID, there are many differences between them from the landing gear to the body and rotors distribution. Even though the whole changes were made for the purpose of landing safely on pipes, the motor distribution and the control technique were the key to achieve it.

The tilted rotors configuration allowed the aircraft to flight and move around without performing roll and pitch. Thanks to this feature, the Force Mode Control was developed specifically making easier and safer to land the aircraft on top of pipes.

Figure 15. On the left, previous version of HYBRID. On the right, new version of HYBRID platform.

HYBRID relies in LiDAR localization and multi-sensor pipe detection and tracking to perform the autonomous landing on pipes supervised by the state machine. Before flying, a rigorous check is performed to make sure all communications, modules and submodules are working as expected.

In Figure 16 is shown a normal operation of HYBRID. Once the main check list has been completed successfully and landing point is selected on the desired pipe by the GCS, is as follows:

1. Pilot takes the control and perform a manual take-off placing the aircraft in a safe place for the operation and decide when to pass to auto mode.
2. Once the control is passed to auto, the UAS waits for the users to start the mission which starts looking for the selected pipe to perform the inspection.
3. If the pipe is found the UAS first prepare itself for landing by, while pipe is being detected, getting the same orientation as the pipe and moving above the selected landing point.
4. It continues performing a pre-landing where the UAS moves closer to the landing point in order to verify the alignment with the pipe for a safe and successful landing.
5. Lands making a X,Y active control thanks to the continuous Pipe's location information provided by the pipe detector.
6. Attach the landing gear to the pipe and turn off the motor in order to be ready for the pipe inspection done by the crawler robot.
7. Once inspection is finished and the crawler robot is in place ready for take-off, this is done manually by the pilot performing a return to home.

Figure 16. HYBRID normal operation procedure.

During the whole operation, the system was monitored from two different user interfaces: the PILOTING gRCS, to visualise the telemetry and the aircraft alarms. Rviz to monitor the aircraft's perception, both the location relative to the take-off point and the detection and tracking of the pipes. In addition, the correct association of the desired landing point received from the IVP with the estimation of the on-board perception algorithms is also monitored.

Figure 17 shows the gRCS during the landing process in the Decom area of the refinery. This shows the Inspection Plan received from the IVP and thus the desired landing point expressed as an Inspection Point.

Figure 17. gRCS with the Inspection Plan during the landing.

In the Figure 18 is shown the RViz window from which the aircraft on-board perception is monitored is displayed. The point cloud from the on-board LiDAR, the image from the depth camera used for pipe detection and the position estimation from the odometry algorithm can be seen. In addition, purple cylinders are shown which correspond to the pipe detections made and with a red arrow, the point received in the Inspection Plan is shown.

Figure 18. Rviz window to monitor on-board perception.

Finally, in the Figure 19 is shown a comparison of the moment when the aircraft lands on the pipe. Note that, in the part of the perception, on the left, there is an offset between the received landing point, represented by the red arrow, and the estimated landing point, represented by an axis on the cylinder of the pipe. This is due to possible misalignment and drift errors and illustrates the importance of landing using the on-board sensor system and not directly using as a control reference the point selected in the IVP.

Figure 19. On the left, Rviz pipes detection during landing. On the right, image of the HYBRID landed.

After the execution of the inspection, the generic data from the gRCS have been uploaded to the IVP portal for further analysis and exploitation. These data have been uploaded on arrival at the laboratory and are shown in Figure 20.

Figure 20. HYBRID path followed shown in the IVP.

Pipe inspection

The second main structures in a refinery environment are pipes and pipe racks. For these structures the major inspection requirement is wall thickness measurements using ultrasonic sensors in the parts of the structure where corrosion is most prevalent such as bends, elbows, T-sections and reducers.

Table 6. Description of the inspection area for HYBRID.

Plant / Area Description	
Plant	Oronite additives plant in Gonfreville, France.
Experiment Area	The water pumping station in NW area of facility. Provided accessible pipe work of sufficient size (8") to test the HYBRID and UT Crawler robot.

Pipework		
Location	Lower section	Upper section
Pipe material	Carbon Steel	Carbon Steel
diameter and thickness	8 Inch Schedule 40 (8.18 mm nominal thickness)	8 Inch Schedule 40 (8.18 mm nominal thickness)
Coating material and thickness	Unknown thickness. Most likely 2-3 coats/layers.	Unknown thickness. Most likely 2-3 coats/layers.
Parallel pipe distance separation	minimum 140 mm	minimum 140 mm
parallel pipe characteristics	Nearest obstacle was conduit tray below pipe ~ 140 mm clearance. Tray ~140-200 mm wide and carrying multiple ground cables.	I-Beam under pipes as support.
Other equipment or obstructions present	No major obstructions as pipe runs at grade.	Pipes only accessible from permanent scaffold with walkway on same height as pipe rack.
Pipe elevation	Elevation approx. 50 cm above ground level	Approx. 3 meter above ground level

Two sites were chosen to validate the magnetic crawler and its ultrasonic thickness measurement (UTM) sensor. Both are located in the water pumping station in NW area of facility. This piping is not critical and therefore not subject regular inspection and maintenance. But this also poses additional challenges to the inspection system, as they would tend to be more weathered, and the welds are coarser, steeper, and higher as more critical process piping may be.

Calibration

Following best practices based on applicable standards, a UT calibration at the beginning and end of each inspection set was performed. A simple step gauge manually held to the probe was used for that purpose. One thickness step was selected that would be representative of the thickness range expected on the pipe to be tested. With the system using a mode 3 measurement principle (backwall to backwall echo), the speed of sound may be adjusted to match the measurement to the actual thickness value. Figure 21 shows the step gauge held to the probe at the underside of the crawler and the resulting measurement value on the measurement instrument.

Figure 21. Calibration using a 1/2 inch thickness of a step gauge.

Lower section UTM validation

This first section is located on the ground floor. The inspection location is however about three meters from the next marked walkway, behind a number of piping running along the floor as seen in Figure 22. The operator did not have to remain in this congested area once the magnetic crawler had been deployed.

Figure 22. Utility water piping lower section image of test area.

The same inspection locations from the 2022 PILOTING field tests were selected. Figure 23 shows the original inspection plan and the corresponding definition on the platform.

Figure 23. Utility water piping lower section inspection locations definition sketch and in IVP.

The UT readings with the crawler were again validated with a manual reading by a qualified inspector. Table 7 lists these new results alongside the corresponding values from the 2022 field trials.

Table 7. Lower section results of UT crawler measurements against hand tool measurements.

Utility water piping (Lower section) UT Measurement (mm)							
		2022			2023		
# point		Manual	Crawler	Diff	Manual	Crawler	Diff
1	Top pipe	8.06	7.57	0.49	7.78	7.22	-0.56
2	Top pipe	8.35	8.11	0.24	7.72	7.57	-0.15
3	top tee	9.47	9.50	-0.03	9.87	9.55	-0.32
4	Side tee	9.98	10.00	-0.02	10.20	10.10	-0.10
5	Side tee	10.45	10.20	0.25	9.98	9.93	-0.05
6	Side pipe	8.04	7.90	0.14	7.42	7.08	-0.34
7	Bottom Elbow	8.07	8.28	-0.21	8.01	7.81	-0.20
8	Bottom Elbow	7.79	8.30	-0.51	7.57	7.43	-0.14
9	side pipe	7.96	7.60	0.36	8.09	8.02	-0.07
10	Side pipe	7.95	7.75	0.2	7.85	7.77	-0.08
Average of Absolute Value (error)				0.245			0.201
Average				-0.091			-0.201

The average error in UT readings between a manual measurement and the HYBRID crawler in 2022 was 0.245 mm. Results of 2023 showed a similar average difference of 0.201 mm. The crawler result was also on average lower by 0.091 mm and 0.201 mm respectively, which might indicate that some of this may be attributed to calibration. This was not further investigated, as this error is well within both the expected calibration and measurement accuracy.

Upper section UTM validation

This second location has the piping at a height of 3 to 4 meters. There is an adjacent permanent scaffold seen on the right of Figure 24. The walkway height is level with the pipes.

Figure 24. Utility water piping upper section image of test area.

The HYFLIERS EU project had used this location for its field trials. The same inspection spots were chosen. First defined in the IVP and then executed on the mRCS as shown in Figure 25.

Figure 25. Utility water piping upper section in mRCS and IVP.

An up-to-date manual reference measurement was taken by a qualified operator. Two sets of measurements were performed with the crawler. Table 8 shows these results alongside previous measurements from the HYFLIERS project field trials in 2022.

Table 8. Upper section results of UT crawler measurements against hand tool measurements.

Utility water piping (upper section) UT measurement (mm)										
		HYFLIERS 2022			PILOTING 2023					
#point		manual	crawler	diff	manual	crawler	diff	crawler	diff	
1	Top tube 1	7.5	6.6	0.9	7.66	7.38	0.28	7.67	-0.01	
2	Side T	9.2	9.3	-0.1	9.00	8.85	0.15	9.31	-0.31	
3	Side T	8.7	8.9	-0.2	8.64	9.08	-0.44	8.91	-0.27	
4	Top tube 2	7.8	7.6	0.2	7.77	7.54	0.23	7.58	0.19	
5	Elbow down	8.6	8.6	0	8.73	8.52	0.21	8.66	0.07	
6	Elbow mid	8.6	8.8	-0.2	8.50	8.29	0.21	8.50	0	
7	Elbow top	8.6	8.7	-0.1	8.43	8.39	0.04	8.48	-0.05	
8	Elbow side	8.0	8.13	-0.13	-	7.50	-	7.97	-	
9	Tube 3 top	7.9	7.4	0.5	7.81	7.52	0.29	7.66	0.15	
10	Bottom T	10.3	10.2	0.1	-	10.22	-	10.32	-	
10.1	Bottom T	10.7	10.9	-0.2	-	10.55	-	10.66	-	
10.2	Bottom T	10.7	10.0	0.7	-	10.12	-	10.64	-	
Average of Absolute Value (error)				0.278				0.231	0.131	
Average				0.122				0.121	-0.029	

Locations 8, 10, 10.1 and 10.2 were not measured in 2023 using the hand tool, as these locations were not accessible from the walkway without additional safety equipment such as climbing gear. The crawler of the HYBRID system on the other hand is not affected by such access limitations.

In 2023 the average error between the UT hand measurement and first crawler measurement set was 0.231 mm and 0.131 mm for the second set. Comparing favourably to the 2022 results averaging 0.278 mm.

The second mission was further analysed to evaluate inspection times in Table 9.

Table 9. Upper section inspection time results.

Utility water piping (upper section) inspection times		
#point	Mission time (s)	Δ time (s)

1	Top tube 1	0:36:42	-
2	Side T	0:38:33	00:01:51
3	Side T	0:39:42	00:01:09
4	Top tube 2	0:41:13	00:01:31
5	Elbow down	0:42:30	00:01:17
6	Elbow middle	0:43:11	00:00:41
7	Elbow top	0:46:14	00:03:03
8	Elbow side	0:47:16	00:01:02
9	Tube 3 top	0:52:04	00:04:48
10	Bottom T	0:53:41	00:01:37
10.1	Bottom T	0:55:32	00:01:51
10.2	Bottom T	0:56:57	00:01:25
Average			00:01:50
Median			00:01:31

During the 2022 field tests the median for an equivalent set of inspection locations was 36 seconds and the average 52 seconds. Though the time per location has been slower in 2023, 13 to 15 minutes for a set of 10 measurements is a reasonable duration.

2.4. Refinery Pressure Vessel Inspection

The verification testing followed the same procedure as in the year before. All major functions were re-tested with an emphasis on those which were modified and improved since the first test. It should be noted that only tests which deviated from the first tests will be reported in this deliverable.

Table 10. Description of work area for BIKE.

Plant / Area Description	
Plant	Oronite additives plant in Gonfreville, France.
Experiment Area	A decommissioned pressure vessel different from last year. Last year pressure vessel was not available for testing due to refinery restrictions

Pressure Vessel	
Vessel material	Carbon Steel
Wall Thickness	12 mm nominal thickness (more on the head sections)
Coating material and thickness	No coating
Access	Scaffold erected to allow for level access to manway
Other equipment or obstructions present	Weather protection nearby for operators and control computers

Figure 26. Pressure vessel manway (left) and side view (right).

Figure 27. BIKE inside pressure vessel.

Measurement Equipment Verification

VT (Visual Testing) equipment (the inspection camera) and UT (Ultrasonic Testing) equipment must be verified / calibrated prior to as well as after an inspection mission. The camera verification was performed successfully in the same way as in the first evaluation.

Figure 28. Resolution achieved by TZ1 inspection camera on BIKE. ASME Section V limit is achieved up to a distance of 3.2 meters.

The UT calibration was performed using the newly developed BIKE specific UT calibration tool. The calibration worked perfectly and was so much easier to use that it was done before every deployment with the UT system.

Figure 29. Redesigned UT calibration which Uses standard (metric and imperial) calibrated step wedges. Operator can slide them in with ease and without having to worry about the magnetic wheels catching them.

Figure 30. VT and UT calibration readings.

Mobility Capabilities and Safety Demonstration

Gas Detection:

The gas detection system worked as expected.

Deployment:

The depth of the protruding flanges was low enough for the BIKE to cross. A novel way of mitigating this issue was the newly developed deployment tool. This was already verified in the lab, however there was no need or opportunity to test it on the available pressure vessel.

Figure 31. Non-protruding manway flange and BIKE entering over it (extract from 3D mission file).

Mobility:

All BIKE mobility capabilities were successfully verified by moving the BIKE along the internal vessel surface.

Figure 32. BIKE mobility verification.

3D Reconstruction and Map Verification

A major upgrade in capabilities was given to the pointcloud / mesh generation by the onboard rotating LIDAR unit. – When only single pointclouds with lots of artefacts were obtainable in the first field trials, the system was now fully SLAM capable and generated an entire pointcloud and mesh in a single short mission.

Figure 33. (left) BIKE with rotating LIDAR unit – (right) generated pointcloud from SLAM.

Figure 34. Automatically generated mesh from pointcloud scan.

Figure 35. Difference map from model to scan. Most deviations are observed in the vessel head sections. - However, an entire large nozzle on the top (red circles) was missing in the drawings and therefore the model.

Figure 36. Model to scan deviations observed in the pressure vessel head sections.

Figure 37. Mesh from scan data of the missing nozzle. Measurements on the scan were used to upgrade the model prior to the BIKE inspection mission(s).

Results:

1. The newly available SLAM for pointcloud and mesh generation worked very reliably and the result turned out to be both accurate and helpful
2. Several model deviations were observed and a crucial one was incorporated into the asset model on the PILOTING portal.

Surface Preparation Demonstration

The surface preparation tool was improved with spacer discs and better visibility for the operator. Furthermore, the same raster scan tool as used for the UT raster scanning was used for the cleaning process. This led to more accurate cleaning, precise overlap as well as less stress to the operator. The improved system was working fine. – However, there was not a lot of debris to clean in the asset.

Figure 38. Cleaning was tested on an area where UT raster scanning was planned.

Inspection Demonstration

As in the previous verifications, an inspection plan containing a representative set of points of interest was used. The plan contained many visual inspections, some ultrasonic spot measurements and one ultrasonic raster scan inspection.

During the first run of the inspection, there were some issues with the autonomous robot control, resulting in lost time and the need to change the control software settings. The repeat mission then worked flawlessly.

The captured visual data was of high quality. The recorded UT values matched expectations. Figure 40 shows the raster scan data.

Figure 39. Vessel Inspection Demonstration VT and UT.

Figure 40. UT raster scan results.

Figure 41. UT spot reading on cylindrical shell where the nominal thickness is 12 mm.

Figure 42. UT spot reading on the vessel head section.

Repeatability Demonstration

The inspection was performed twice for repeatability checking.

Figure 43. Visual Inspection of same Inspection point in mission one (above) and mission two (below).

Results:

1. After fixing the controller issue, inspection performance was as expected.
2. Localization and path-tracking accuracy was very good and lead to excellent repeatability

2.5. Refinery Ground Monitoring

The rationale of the ground monitoring use case keeps the same as in previous pilots. The refinery operators are constantly looking for opportunities to reduce the amount of time staff need to be out in the facilities doing dull, dangerous, or dirty work. Different routine checks are the focus of this robotic pilots.

In this second pilot, the project will test and validate ground monitoring tasks performed by different assets, including a new robot Robotnik’s **RB-Watcher** with a value proposition based on new sensors, together with enhanced manipulation functionalities of ETHZ’s UGV and the use of static sensors on pipelines to assess leak detection and or flow anomalies (ICCS).

Table 11. Description of work area for ground monitoring.

Plant / Area Description	
Plant	Oronite additives plant in Gonfreville, France.
Experiment Area	A multi-level decommissioned process module housing a mix of process piping and vessels. RB-WATCHER and UGV experiments done on ground level.

RB-WATCHER

The Ground Monitoring tests with the RB-Watcher robot were done in a similar way as last year’s pilot and against the specification, also keeping in mind the defined KPI’s for validating the solution. In the first place, verifications of such adaptations done to the robot were made.

Figure 44. RB-WATCHER starting mission.

In order to check further these points, the envisioned tests conducted are explained in the following sections.

Equipment Verification

- *The robot is inspected to check if it has integrated a gas detection system, a traction system for operating on different surfaces, a lidar, a datalink for ground communications, and different cameras including a thermal one.*
- *Given the “sensor” value proposition, integration of Reality Capture solution (Leica BLK ARC) is verified.*
- *A reliable time of operation is ensured by the robot’s battery capacity, equaling previous mission times.*
- *Robustness of the robot is inspected against certain conditions during the test, such as water splashing and dust presence.*

Again, conclusions could be extracted not only by inspecting the equipment but also by analyzing the robot behavior within the very first mission tests. It is important also to highlight the acquired knowledge of first refinery pilot, helpful to already assess known problems in a lab environment.

The highlights about these tests would be:

- RB-Watcher robot is also capable of moving smoothly in all different terrains, including different types of asphalt, cement and steel grating despite having a different kinematic configuration (4-wheel drive, differential configuration). Rubber wheels proved to be even more resistant than in-house tracks of RISING robot and they are also easily changed if needed.
- Same 4 video streams in the visual spectrum and 1 thermal video/picture can be retrieved any time from the robot since RB-Watcher can also mount the same sensors.
- The additional data retrieved by the BLK ARC reality capture device is providing a whole new level of environment awareness thanks to the panoramic images and dense coloured pointclouds that can be automatically registered and stitched.

- Environmental conditions favored the validation of robustness against water splashing, as a light rain was present during experiments again. In this context however, the BLK ARC was not operated due to its lower ip rating.
- Battery level is also within expectations. General data capturing is much faster than previous iteration and the missions are shorter. Taking into account that robot can come back and charge in between missions, endurance is assured and even lighter options for battery could be explored.

Mapping

- *The robot is tele-operated around the plant with a LIDAR to acquire 3D scans while traversing the site. The 3D scans are processed offline to build a final 3D map of the plant that is useful for creating and navigating within an inspection plan.*

Similar to RISING robot, RB-WATCHER is mounting a 30°x360° LIDAR (Robosense Helios16) that features 16 lines and a horizontal resolution of 0.2°/0.4° and Vertical resolution of 2°.

On the other hand, a reconstruction provided by this Lidar would have to be registered manually. also having the main disadvantage of being colourless. This proved a major shortcoming during first pilots, while planning new missions since specific features to be inspected are difficult to find without images or at least coloured pointclouds.

Because of that, and thanks to the BLK ARC (and its API) integration in RB-WATCHER, the uploaded 3D map (coloured) is being recorded and registered automatically, at the same time as the map used for the autonomous navigation. Both mappings are done in movement and consistent with robot's odometry with a <1cm precision. Also, the rich map has the possibility to be visualized together with the panoramic images that are being taken with a desired frequency. Furthermore, the BLK ARC has the ability of capturing a dedicated "static scan" so that pcl is even denser in a certain point, where the robot needs to keep position for about a minute. This operation is also interesting for dedicated POI's where a better resolution of a map is requested.

In this case, there is no need of multiple runs for map creation, as the registering is done in one session. Future or past data can also be added to the existent point cloud seamlessly thanks to the Leica software.

Figure 45. Maps generated from BLK ARC.

Autonomous Navigation

- *The robot is commanded manually to a predefined entry point to the designated and pre-mapped area.*
- *The robot, starting from the base station, autonomously navigates to a pre-specified location through a set of waypoints while avoiding obstacles.*

For the autonomous navigation tests, the same approach from the first pilot was followed.

For a POI to be inspected, it was required to have successfully created the map in a previous test. Due to the fact that now the map features are easily recognized, even the user can propose the optimal run for the robot to navigate.

Figure 46. RB-WATCHER robot running autonomous navigation.

Inspection

- *An inspection plan created and downloaded to the robot can be executed together with the autonomous navigation system.*
- *At the end of the inspection plan, the robot returns autonomously to the base station.*
- *All relevant sensing (images, thermal, audio) is recorded, and associated with a location and a timestamp.*
- *Time is automatically tracked in the mission data. From this data cost savings and other information required for PGM-KPI-B-01 and PGM-KPI-B-02 can be directly derived.*

The workflow is again consistent with the previous tests.

Once the map was tuned and uploaded to the portal, different missions and inspection points were issued within the PILOTING portal.

Figure 47. Ground inspection portal site.

With the gRCS instance launched in the Robot and local ground control (in a dedicated laptop) the robot was able to perform such missions, mainly consisting on navigating to a point and then gathering data. In this case the inspection data is enriched by the Leica BLK ARC data including panoramic images and denser point clouds wherever the “static scan” operation is triggered by a mission request.

Figure 48. GRCS RB-WATCHER interface.

The data is again recorded in a dedicated folder following the defined structured readable by DMS, where each inspection folder has an associated telemetry, device data and media recorded. Thanks to the integration effort, full workflow was validated by checking uploaded data and mission results in the portal. The value of such data was already discussed directly after the mission since some hot pipes could be identified in the same area of Hybrid tests.

Figure 49. IVP results screen of RB-WATCHER inspection.

UGV

Figure 50. UGV running autonomous navigation in the decommissioned module.

Figure 51. UGV autonomously manipulating a hand wheel valve.

Figure 52. UGV tablet display showing valve handwheel detection prior to manipulation.

Figure 53. UGV running autonomous pressure gauge reading.

The validation of the developed autonomous functionalities for the UGV robotic inspector has been carried out following the planned mapping, navigation and manipulation and inspection sessions.

2.5.1. Mapping session

The robot navigated the refinery in teleoperation mode while capturing the required data, in this case point clouds from a LiDAR scanner and IMU data, to build a 3D representation of the plant (a map). The map covers a total area of 30 m x 30 m (see Figure 54). However, the inspection was confined to a smaller area of 5 m x 10 m that was the area assigned to this pilot by the refinery plant. The UGV robotic inspector does not have any limitation, apart from 2h battery life time, on the area it can navigate.

Figure 54. 3D map reconstruction of the refinery by teleoperating the UGV.

2.5.2. Autonomous navigation session

The robot is then controlled from the ground control station providing target inspection points as waypoints on the previously built map. The robot successfully performed localization and followed autonomously and safely the waypoints while avoiding obstacles that were not present in the prior map (see Figure 50). In more detail, the robot loads the prior map and its traversability mask. The robot continuously localizes in the prior map through point cloud registration. The traversability mask (see Figure 55) is used to perform the global planning towards the next inspection waypoint. To follow the global plan and keep a safe operation, the robot uses a TEB local planner that allows it to safely avoid obstacles that did not appear in the prior map. The local planner is reactive, meaning that dynamic obstacles could also be avoided.

Figure 55. 2D traversability mask computed from the prior 3D map for the specifications of the UGV robot inspector.

2.5.3. Manipulation and inspection session

After autonomously navigating to a target inspection point for valve manipulation, the robot detected the asset (see Figure 56), in this case hand-wheel valves in 3D space (see Figure 57), and approached it (see Figure 51). Then, it started the manipulation task (see Figure 51) by turning the valve by a predefined angle set in the inspection plan (see Figure 58). The compliant approach and the adaptive gripper design allowed successful manipulations even under small errors in the 3D pose of the valve. After manipulation completion, the robot autonomously navigated to the final waypoint, the location of a base station.

Figure 56. UGV follows inspection waypoints and detects the target valve.

Figure 57. Typical detections of hand wheel valves in the refinery by the UGV.

Figure 58. UGV manipulating the detected hand-wheel valve by a predetermined angle.

Figure 59. Typical detection and reading of an analog pressure gauge by the UGV.

It has been shown that the developed functionalities are robust and deliver reproducible results. The entire mission was repeated more than 10 times. When the valve was not detected or grasped successfully in the first attempt, the robot triggered the functionality again until successful detection and manipulation. The same holds true for the analog pressure gauge detection.

Due to the compliance of the system, no damage to the robot nor the asset was caused. In contrast to the first pilot, the robustness could be further enhanced. Due to this circumstance, the safe execution speed of the valve manipulation action could be further increased.

Finally, a summary of the main mission metrics are shown below.

Key Mission Metrics

- Total robot startup time: 8 min
- Total mission duration: 6 min
- Total valve detection duration: 1 min
- Number of valve detections before manipulation start: 3
- Valve manipulation duration: 20 s
- Valve turning angle step size: 130°
- Peak exerted absolute end-effector force: 2.8 N
- Individual gauge detection duration: 10 s
- Number of gauge detections before result calculation: 3
- Total gauge reading duration: 60 s
- Replanning for obstacles not in map: successful
- Total data processing and DDHL upload time: 2 min
- Data processing and DDHL upload: successful

2.6. IoT Sensors

2.6.1. Introduction

During the first deliverable, we in detail described the full rationale behind the adoption of an IoT accelerometer solution as according to the literature it resulted to be the most efficient solution for the identification of “abnormal” vibrations in water pipes that could give indications of leak events. The whole design of this solution, the integration as well with the I&M Piloting Platform and the

deployment during the first pilots was fully covered through the respective documents of D6.3, D8.1 and D6.7.

Thus, the following sections are keen on giving additional details on updates that were made in order to overcome several bottlenecks on the continuous operations of the aforementioned IoT Wireless Sensor Network (WSN) solution and the two conducted efforts that were implemented with the first to be two months before the pilots and during the official second phase of the experiments. In addition to the abovementioned aspects, brief descriptions and modifications on the installation of the IoT WSN solution and the components that is consisted of will be presented as well, so as to preserve consistency in the presented content with respect to D8.1.

2.6.2. Pilot demonstration: Installation of the IoT Wireless solution

2.6.2.1. Improvements of the improved IoT WNS solution

Due to unresolvable connectivity issues in the 4G modem of the IoT Gateway, an external off-the-shelf 4G modem/router (TP-Link Archer MR600) was added to the solution, in order to enable an internet connectivity for the IoT gateway.

An extra 20W solar panel was added, in parallel with the existing one, in order to compensate for the extra power consumption of the external 4G modem/router.

Finally, a system reset functionality was added to the solution, based on an Arduino Pro Mini Microcontroller Board which briefly interrupts the power supply of the IoT gateway and the external 4G modem/router every hour, as a failsafe in case they become unresponsive

2.6.2.2. Installation of the improved IoT WNS solution

The installation of the WSN along with the supplementary solar power system that contributes to the power autonomy of the whole system had been implemented in the Green water piping area inside the Oronite plant.

Table 12. Description of work area for installation of the IoT Wireless solution.

Plant / Area Description	
Plant	Oronite additives plant in Gonfreville, France.
Experiment Area	Water processing facility - Along Green water piping.

Both the indoor and outdoor vibration sensors had been already installed on water pipes in the Refinery during the first pilot experiments (13/9/2022). A single replacement of an indoor sensor was made during the second pilot experiments (20-22/09/2023) as it was identified that it wasn't able to continue operating. Additional efforts were oriented on the enhancement of the solar power system capacity, by the inclusion of a second solar panel. The installation of the two previously described additions as well as the complete evaluation of the operation of the system was lasted approximately 4 hours. Table 13 summarises the main characteristics of the five sensors installed in the refinery, with the highlighted rows to present the sensor that was replaced.

Table 13. Summary of the main characteristics of the five sensors installed in the refinery.

Static Data	Description	Sensor 1	Sensor 2	Sensor 3	Sensor 4	Sensor 5
Unique identifier	The identifier of the sensor.	a3bb0bc5-c449-41be-ba1e-7634acf4369e	fceb084d-603d-433d-8f92-9e0d3de8b304	cc6d68f6-c35b-40d1-a8ae-295a558f56ef	5845f4a3-df8f-4165-9c46-daa6fc49cb8e	04b6feec-2dbf-41f4-b8c1-e76883e79690
name	The name of the sensor.	Vibration	Vibration	Vibration	Vibration	Vibration
type	The type of the sensor.	accelerometer (indoor)	accelerometer (indoor)	accelerometer (indoor)	accelerometer (outdoor)	accelerometer (outdoor)
address or sequence number	The mac address or the sequence number of the sensor	00:13:a2:00:41:e3:4d:de	00:13:A2:00:41:E2:35:51	00:13:A2:00:41:EF:E1:50	00:13:A2:00:41:E3:3A:22	00:13:A2:00:41:E3:2F:52
location of the sensor	The point where the sensor is installed.	49.49661,0.21250	49.49654,0.21248	49.49659,0.21250	49.49674,0.21227	49.49658,0.21252
frequency	Sampling rate of the sensor	300 sec	300 sec	300 sec	720 sec	720 sec

Sensors communicate with a wireless gateway at sub-gigahertz frequencies. The gateway as well as the additional 4G router that is interconnected with the gateway in order to provide wireless communication is placed in the waterproof case with a battery to provide the necessary power for the gateway to operate for approximately 60 hours, with constant sun light presence. The battery is being charged with two 20W solar panels in parallel connection that are placed on a high point in the refinery.

Figure 60. Solar panel location.

The design of the data flow that is responsible to interconnect the deployed components (i.e., the 5 WSN, the gateway up to the message broker specific topic) was implemented in the Node-RED, and remained unchanged since the first integration and pilot demonstration as it was able to successfully maintain the aforementioned transmission flow and deliver the collected observations. The figure below illustrate all the aforementioned interconnection between the components and the delivery of the msg.data to the backend in the desired JSON format.

Figure 61. Flow design in node-red.

The sensors produce data and then they are passed to a function that selects the desired format to be sent to MQTT. The purple node contains the information required for the connection with the MQTT

server (IP, port, topic). The two bottom nodes are there for debugging the gateway, the green node outputs any messages from the gateway to the debug window in node-red. Finally, the wireless gateway is equipped with the Hologram 4G/LTE IoT, Global coverage, connectivity card that ensures the remote connection of the IoT solution. For the second pilot demonstration days (20-27/9/2023) the system consumed approximately 9.18 MB per day, with the total consumption on weekly basis to be 35.93 MB (Figure 62).

Figure 62. Data consumption ensuring wireless communication and data transmission.

3. Viaducts experiments and results

Ferrovial is the end user for the Viaduct Inspection operations. For this second phase, the experiments carried out on a new viaduct served to technologically validate the developments made throughout the project, but more specifically the progress made since phase 1. The tests carried out have not only served to demonstrate the capacity of the aerial platforms to perform the tasks, but also to improve key aspects since the previous campaign, such as greater automation of the process and improved execution times. Ferrovial was therefore responsible for providing a new location that met the objectives for this second phase of experimentation and allowed the aerial platforms to demonstrate their potential, improving on the previous phase 1.

In addition, this new experimentation campaign has served to complete the validation of the KPIs of the use cases.

3.1. Description of Viaduct Location

The test location for this second phase meets all the requirements for the use cases. On this occasion, two viaducts have been chosen: one to test all the visual inspection (general visual, target installation, specific visual and bearings) and another one for the installation of sensors. This is because, for the first viaduct, it has been decided to advance in the development and choose a larger viaduct with inaccessible areas and much more height, which represents a new realistic challenge in this pilot. However, for the installation of sensors, physical access to the deployment area is required, so a lower altitude one has been chosen only for this use case, facilitating the development and testing.

The Archidona viaduct of the conventional railway line between Granada and Antequera. It is part of the Spanish railway infrastructure manager, Adif. It is a low viaduct with pier heights of no more than 7 m and 4 m abutments. The spans have horizontal widths of 25m. It was built using the in situ cantilever method and is a rigid viaduct like all railway viaducts in southern Spain.

Of this viaduct only half the load is used because it is built for two tracks and only one of them is used. Underneath the viaduct is the A 92 motorway Sevilla Granada, with four lanes, two in each direction.

It is located in the municipality of Archidona, Granada and its geographical location coordinates are 37.129820, -4.341662.

Figure 63. Geographical location.

This viaduct was selected for the installation tests of the box because of its low height and easy recovery capacity of the same.

Location

Archidona (Málaga)

<https://maps.app.goo.gl/7DgdWDrqXos7bgeM9>

Location

Marbella – AP7 (Málaga)

<https://maps.app.goo.gl/DznXNtdcMAT54QM38>

Figure 64. Map with the location of the viaducts.

The "Autopista del Sol" is owned by the concessionaire Ausol part of the international concessionary group Meridiam. The viaduct is located in the municipality of Marbella with approximate coordinates 36.525722, -4.956650.

It was built by Ferrovial between 94 and 97. It consists of 6 spans with pier heights between 15 m and 60m. It is a concrete viaduct, built using the technique known as successive T-shaped segments interconnected with temporary and permanent internal prestressing. It is 540 m long with two lanes in each direction and 12.5 m wide paved.

This viaduct has been chosen for the final tests of all the possible cases, except for the installation of the box.

3.1.1. Flight Authorisation process

For the case of the new viaducts, the flights are again under the "Open" A3 category with the following requirements:

- Registered UAS operator.
- Less than 25Kg UAS.
- Visual line of sight (VLOS).
- 120m maximum height.

- Do not fly near or over people.
- Fly at least 150m away from residential, commercial or industrial areas.

In the case of the Rio Verde viaduct, its location is outside the Malaga airport CTR, so it has not been necessary to coordinate with them. However, coordination efforts have had to be made since the flight zone is within the safety limits of the Marbella heliport. In addition, the area is within the natural environment of Rio Verde, so we had to ask for a flight authorization to the Junta de Andalucía to fly over the area.

Figure 65. Flight restrictions for Rio Verde viaduct.

In the case of the Archidona viaduct, again its location is outside the Malaga Airport CTR. However, it has been necessary to coordinate with the aerodromes of Loja and Villanueva del Trabuco, which are nearby locations, to obtain permission to fly in the area.

Figure 66. Flight restrictions for Bobadilla viaduct.

3.2. Viaduct Visual Inspection (including surveying target installation)

The viaduct visual inspection process followed in this second phase is the same as the one described in the previous deliverable. This document described the current viaduct inspection process versus the one proposed in the PILOTING project using drones. In this last phase, the process has been maintained, performing first a general visual inspection with the AERO-CAM platform. Then, when an area of interest is located, the VIAD-DRONE platform installs a surveying target of known geometry to obtain more data. Finally, AERO-CAM again performs a survey, but this time specifically by taking photographs of the installed target to complete the information.

In the second pilot experiments, the inspections were carried out on the 4 pillars and 2 decks of the Rio Verde viaduct. For this purpose, a 3D map was made with a total station. This map was used for the planning and execution of the inspections. Figure 67 shows the viaduct and the map created.

Figure 67. Above, Rio Verde viaduct. Below, 3D model created with a total station.

For this second pilot, two main flight plans have been created, as seen in Figure 68. First, a general inspection covering as much of the viaduct area as possible to obtain an overall view of the condition of the infrastructure. Unlike the experiments of the first pilot, this inspection plan has been increased in difficulty, covering now more area pertaining to the 4 pillars, 1 deck and the lateral part of the deck in the second viaduct is included. Therefore, AERO-CAM must cover this larger area and perform an in-flight viaduct change. Later, when an area of interest has been located where more detail is required, a second inspection plan has been made marking the point where to install the target, to later take pictures of that same point. Another difference with the previous campaign is that this time a single inspection point is being used for the specific inspection and not a small inspection area.

Figure 68. Visual Inspection plans in the IVP. Above, general inspection plan. Below, specific inspection plan.

As in the first pilots, the inspection plans have been executed on different days and with different environmental conditions, such as light and wind. The developed gRCS and mRCS software was used for the execution. This was done with ground equipment that does not maintain direct line of sight with the aircraft. All data were transmitted from the platform to the ground. The safety pilot was in the flight area with direct line of sight to the UAV. Communication between the different personnel was continuous via walkie-talkies.

Figure 69. Test campaign execution with AERO-CAM in Rio Verde, Marbella.

General visual inspection

The first step for the visual inspection was again the general visual inspection. Different experiments have been performed following the general flight plans presented above. All the results have been uploaded to the IVP using gRCS and mRCS. Figure 70 shows the results of the general mission executed, including the 4 pillars, 1 deck and 1 side deck. The blue line shows the trajectory followed

by AERO-CAM. The blue arrows mark each of the photographs taken. Figure 71 and Figure 72 show a capture of the gRCS and mRCS in operation during the execution of these missions.

Figure 70. Executed general Visual Inspection plans by AERO-CAM in the IVP.

Figure 71. gRCS with AERO-CAM during a general Visual Inspection execution.

Figure 72. mRCS with AERO-CAM during a general Visual Inspection execution.

As in the previous phase, these flights have been repeated on different occasions to demonstrate the repeatability of the system, uploading the post mission results to the IVP for verification. With this, it has been possible to validate the ability to take photographs of the same place at different times but keeping the same reference system, thus allowing the inspectors to analyze the evolution of the viaduct's condition. Figure 73 illustrates the repeatability of the system.

Figure 73. AERO-CAM photos for 4 different waypoints in 4 different inspections.

Another important aspect that has clearly improved since the phase 1 pilots is the safety and autonomy of AERO-CAM. On the one hand, it has been equipped with an obstacle detection algorithm adaptive to the speed and direction of movement of the aircraft. This can be understood as an ellipsoid around the UAV that deforms according to speed and direction, creating a safety volume that no obstacle should penetrate. Figure 72 illustrates this ellipsoid in green around the AERO-CAM. In case of detecting any obstacle, this volume would be shown in red and will stop the aircraft in flight, entering hovering mode until the operator confirms that the route is safe and can continue.

On the other hand, the autonomy of the drone has been substantially improved by improving the localization algorithm and photo capture strategy. In the localization, the global localization has been improved, which every 10 seconds performs a check of the current position of AERO-CAM with

respect to the previous map, comparing both point clouds. This process continuously improves the transform, drastically improving the localization and accuracy of the platform throughout the mission. The main motivation for this improvement has been the choice of a much larger viaduct where longer distances are covered from the starting point. This new scenario was handicapped by the fact that the overall localization is greatly degraded as AERO-CAM moves away from the takeoff area. Therefore, cyclic corrections are being made to solve this problem, allowing long distances to be surveyed.

Also, the photo capture strategy is improved by reducing the time taken by the AERO-CAM to capture each photo. This has been achieved by improving the control algorithms to allow a higher travel speed (1m/s) and by setting the lens focus manually to avoid the lens having to focus each photo automatically. All this has allowed AERO-CAM to go from 5-6 seconds per photo to only 1-1.5 seconds. Combined with the increase in speed, the system now makes it possible to cover greater distances and take more photos in a single flight, reducing time and improving inspection performance.

Finally, an AI network processes the photos obtained. These networks detect and classify possible defects, as represented in Figure 74. These networks can detect small-size defects, which would be difficult to see by the human eye in the images. The images in Figure 74 were generated with a network with 0.7 confidence, which is the standard value, defined by archiving a compromise between not missing relevant defects and not detecting too many false defects.

Figure 74. AERO-CAM inferred photos.

Furthermore, as shown in Figure 75, the defects segmentation has been improved from previous experiments. Deliverable D6.2 gather all the changes that led to this improvement. Firstly, a change of network, using BiSeNet, which is faster and more precise than its predecessor. Secondly, a change of approach, having specialised networks for each defect. The algorithm chose which network to use with the annotations from the detection and segmentation network.

Figure 75. Defect segmentation with detection, and segmentation networks' results.

Survey target installation

The next step to complete the visual inspection of the viaduct is the installation of the survey target. After the general inspection of the viaduct, the VIADDRONE aerial robot places the survey targets on the potential defects identified by the AERO-CAM platform. These targets are reflective, allowing for accurate and reliable measurements in different lighting conditions. They are also impact resistant and durable, making it possible to track defects on the viaduct over time. For more information on the design of the VIADDRONE aerial robot, see Deliverable 4.3.

The final experiments are carried out on the same span of the Rio Verde viaduct where the general inspection, discussed in the previous section, takes place. To carry out the installation of the survey targets, several missions are defined, one for each target to be attached. It should be noted that the target installation mechanism can only place one target in each mission. For this reason, three different missions are defined in the final experiments. Figure 76 shows the procedure for the installation of survey targets by the VIADDRONE aerial robot on the Rio Verde viaduct. First, the VIADDRONE takes off from the starting point and moves to the first approach point, which is perpendicular to the viaduct abutment and at a safe distance from the installation point. Once the target is fixed to the abutment, the VIADDRONE returns to the starting point where a new target is

fixed to the pole. Then, the aerial robot moves on to the next inspection point. This process is repeated until all points of interest have been inspected.

Figure 76. Procedure for the installation of the survey target on the Rio Verde viaduct abutment in the final experiments.

The first step in performing this use case is to create an inspection plan in the IVP. In the IVP, the 3D map of the Rio Verde viaduct is visualized and the areas in which the survey targets will be located are defined. Both the 3D map and the points to be inspected are then downloaded to the gRCS. This interface allows communication with the aerial robot and monitoring of the inspection status in real-time. Figure 77 shows the inspection plan created in the IVP on the right and the complete mission downloaded and running in gRCS on the left. More detailed information on the inspection plan generation can be found in Deliverable 7.3.

Figure 77. Inspection plan created from the IVP for the inspection location (left) and complete mission designed in gRCS (right) for the survey target installation.

After creating the inspection plan, the aerial robot can start the mission. Figure 78 shows the complete sequence carried out by the VIADDRONE to install the survey target on inspection point 3 (IP3) of the viaduct abutments. It can be seen how the aerial robot takes off from the starting point, climbs vertically and moves to the approach point. At this point, it contacts the pillar to fix the target. Figure 79 shows the survey target placed on the viaduct abutment by the VIADDRONE.

Figure 78. VIADDRONE performing the surveying target installation on the Rio Verde viaduct in the final experiments.

Figure 79. Survey target installed on the Rio Verde viaduct abutment using the VIADDRONE aerial robot mast in a fully autonomous mission.

The navigation system of the VIADDRONE in this scenario and its approach to the viaduct abutment is performed autonomously following the localization methods described in Deliverable 5.3. In addition, the contact between the VIADDRONE retractile mechanism and the viaduct abutment is autonomously controlled. The proposed localization methods and the control performed allow to estimate the position of the aerial robot on the viaduct and to fix the target very precisely. In order to validate the perception system developed, Figure 80 above compares the estimated position of the VIADDRONE throughout the mission (in blue) with the estimated position of the ground truth generated by the Total Station (in red). In addition, Figure 80 below shows the errors achieved in each coordinate axis throughout the mission. The blue-shaded area refers to the moment when the aerial robot makes contact with the viaduct abutment. The average errors achieved in this use case are 7.07cm for the X-axis, 3.02cm for the Y-axis, and 17.47cm for the Z-axis. In addition, the average error obtained at the point of contact is 3.2cm. It is worth highlighting the high accuracy of the

localization system and the autonomous control of the survey target installation. This ensures accurate and safe autonomous missions.

Figure 80. VIAD-DRONE robot localization estimation in blue against the ground truth localization estimated with a Leica Total station in red (top) and the related localization errors (bottom) in the survey target installation use case. The blue shaded area corresponds to the moment of direct contact with the viaduct abutment.

Figure 81 shows some results of the installation of the survey target during the final experiments at inspection point 1, IP1 (see Figure 76). The robustness and reliability of the system was validated by the correct installation of the survey target near the intended inspection point 1 (IP1). In addition, these results allow to validate the repeatability of the system and the accuracy of the proposed localization methods, as it places the survey targets near each other. The experiments were performed on different days and under different wind conditions, demonstrating the robustness of both the robot's GNSS-based pose estimation method and the robot's autonomous navigation system.

Figure 81. Results of the survey target installation use case in the final experiments.

Specific visual inspection

Once the target is in place, AERO-CAM performs a specific mission in which the point is photographed. Figure 82 shows an example of a specific visual inspection, where a point on the inside face of an abutment has been selected. The figure on the left shows the mission in the IVP, having been repeated twice to show repeatability. On the right, the photograph obtained in each inspection is shown, demonstrating that it is possible to return to the same location.

Figure 82. Specific visual inspection results with AERO-CAM.

3.3. Viaduct Bearing Inspection

Visual inspection of bearings is one of the main objectives of viaduct inspection. These elements play an important role in the transmission of forces and the absorption of deformations as they support and transfer loads between the bridge and the viaduct abutment. Monitoring of the bearings is therefore essential, as their performance is critical for the entire structure. This type of operation is based on visual inspections, which allow a general assessment of the bearings to detect defects, stresses, or displacements. The height of the viaducts makes it difficult to access the bearings for proper inspection, so the use of aerial robots would help to simplify maintenance procedures, reduce the risks associated with working at height and minimize costs.

In the PILOTING project, the bearings will be inspected visually using the VIADDRONE aerial robot. The aim is to obtain high quality images close to the bearings, from different angles, in order to correctly visualize the condition of these elements. The final experiments were carried out on the same span of the Rio Verde viaduct where the general visual inspection and the installation of the survey targets were carried out.

Figure 83. Procedure for the visual bearing inspection on the Rio Verde viaduct in the final experiments.

The inspection procedure is described in Figure 83. First, the aerial robot takes off from the starting point and climbs to a position very close to the top of the viaduct. Unlike the first experiments described in Deliverable 8.1, the aerial robot is not attached to the top of the viaduct to take images but is positioned very close to it. There are a large number of bridges that are curved, making it difficult for the aerial robot to fix itself close to the bearings. In these cases, the UAV had to be positioned on the straight part of the viaduct, which could be far from the bearings. To avoid this problem and to ensure that images were taken safely and on different types of viaducts, the visual inspection was performed without attaching to the top of the viaduct. As will be seen in this section, this solution allows high quality images to be captured, while making this type of robotic inspection generalizable to any viaduct.

Figure 84. Inspection plan created from the IVP for the inspection location (left) and complete mission designed in gRCS (right) for the viaduct bearing inspection use case.

As with the general inspection, the first step in carrying out the visual inspection of the bearings is to create an inspection plan. The 3D map of the viaduct and the inspection points where the images will be taken are downloaded to the gRCS, which allows communication with the aerial robot. Figure 84 shows the inspection plan created in the IVP on the right and the complete mission planning in the gRCS on the left. First, the VIADDRONE takes off from the starting point and climbs vertically. It then moves horizontally and climbs to the approach point defined in the gRCS. This sequence is shown in Figure 85 where the VIADDRONE aerial robot completes the bearing inspection on the Rio Verde viaduct in the final experiments.

The results of the visual inspection of the bearings are shown in Figure 86. The images on the left of Figure 86 were captured on a different flight than the images on the right. Very similar images of the bearings can be seen in each mission, demonstrating the repeatability of both the VIADDRONE localization system and the execution of the inspection mission. The use of the gimbal to stabilize and orientate the camera enabled high quality images to be captured, as can be seen in the enlarged images of the bearings in Figure 87. The control of the gimbal and the image capture were conducted autonomously and commanded by the gRCS. These pictures could be used for real assessment of the bearings as they have a good level of detail for the operator to evaluate the viaduct infrastructure.

Figure 85. VIADDRONE performing the viaduct bearing inspection on the Rio Verde viaduct in the final experiments.

Figure 86. Results from the visual bearing inspection obtained with the VIADDRONE. Images of the left column were captured in a different flight from the images of the right column. Both flights were commanded by the gRCS following the same designed inspection plan.

Figure 87. VIAD-DRONE robot localization estimation in blue against the ground truth localization estimated with a Leica Total station in red (top) and the related localization errors (bottom) in the bearing visual inspection use case.

The navigation of the aerial robot was fully autonomous by fusing the measurements collected by the on-board sensors. The localization methods used are those described in Deliverable 5.3. The sensors and localization techniques are the same as those used to install the survey target. In order to validate the perception system, the aerial robot's position estimate was compared with the estimate generated by the Total Station used as ground truth. Figure 87-top shows in blue the estimated localization of the VIAD-DRONE and in red the estimated localization of the Total Station, used as ground truth. Figure 87-bottom shows the errors obtained in each coordinate axis, where the average error in the X-axis is 14.76cm, in the Y-axis is 10.44cm and in the Z-axis is 14.88cm. Based on the results and performance of the experiments, it has been demonstrated that the aerial robot can perform visual bearing inspection with robustness and reliability, correctly, and autonomously taking high quality pictures of the inspection locations.

3.4. Viaduct Sensor Installation

Installing a sensor box on the viaduct with devices such as accelerometers or IMUs is commonly used to monitor the condition of the infrastructure. In particular, it is used to measure vibrations, accelerations or displacements of the viaduct. However, these sensor boxes are usually located at the top of the viaduct abutment, which is high and difficult to access. For this reason, it is proposed to use aerial robots with aerial manipulation capabilities to install the sensors in the areas of interest selected by qualified personnel. This eliminates the need for personnel to work at height and in hard-to-reach areas. It also reduces inspection time and costs and increases operational safety by eliminating the need to use heavy machinery to access these areas.

For this use case, the final experiments involved placing a sensor box on top of the viaduct abutment, near the bearings, using aerial robots with advanced capabilities. This use case presents additional risks due to the difficulty of access and the very tight locations where the aerial platform must navigate to perform the installation. In addition, in this area there are significant aerodynamic effects caused by the proximity of the aerial robot to the structure. All this means that the pilot does not have a clear line of sight to the robot during the mission.

The final experiments were performed in the Archidona viaduct. It is a low viaduct that has allowed the different experiments and the complete development of the use case. It should be noted that once installed, the box must be removed by qualified personnel before the next experiment is carried out, as the aerial robot does not have the manipulation capacity to remove the box.

Figure 88. Procedure for the sensor box installation on the Archidona viaduct in the final experiments.

Figure 88 shows the procedure executed during the final experiments to install the sensor box on the top of the viaduct abutment. The VIADDRONE aerial robot takes off from the starting point and approaches the top of the viaduct. It is then attached to the viaduct deck to move along it using the caterpillars and taking advantage of the ceiling effect. This effect provides suction to the platform, allowing it to remain attached throughout the mission. The aerial robot moves along the viaduct deck until it reaches the waypoint where it must release the box. This waypoint is located between the two bearings and between the viaduct deck and the top of the viaduct pier. After installing the sensor box, the UAV moves backwards with the caterpillar. Finally, when the aerial robot is in a safe position and away from the viaduct pier, it detaches from the deck and lands at the starting point.

Like the other use cases, the first step in performing the box installation is to create the inspection plan in the IVP. The viaduct map and inspection plans were then downloaded to gRCS, where the detailed inspection plan was created by adding some waypoints and connecting them to the inspection points. This process ensures a safe and efficient route for the aerial robot in the environment. The inspection plan designed in the IVP to perform the installation of the sensor box is shown in Figure 89-left. Figure 89-right shows the complete inspection schedule created in gRCS for the same inspection plan.

Figure 90 illustrates the VIADDRONE aerial robot performing the installation of the box on the Archidona viaduct during the final experiments. It can be observed that it follows the procedure defined in the inspection plan in IVP and gRCS. The aerial robot autonomously navigates tracking a list of waypoints from the starting point. The robot pose estimation was performed using GNSS-denied localization techniques that were implemented in real time and on board the robot. Physical contact with the viaduct deck, caterpillar track advance control and box installation is done fully autonomously.

Figure 89. Inspection plan created from the IVP for the inspection location (left) and complete mission designed in gRCS (right) for the sensor box installation use case.

Figure 90. VIADDRONE performing the sensor box installation on the Archidona viaduct in the final experiments.

After completing the mission shown in Figure 83, the sensor box is installed on top of the viaduct abutment. Figure 91 illustrates the position of the box installed autonomously by the VIADDRONE aerial robot. However, it should be noted that the aerial robot does not have the capability to remove the sensor box from the viaduct. An operator would have to pick up the box when the required measurements of the structure are collected.

Figure 91. Sensor box installed on the top of the Archidona viaduct abutment in the final experiments.

For enabling the GNSS-denied autonomous navigation of the robot, accurate and reliable localization of the drone was estimated fusing the measurements gathered by the sensors on-board. The localization methods used are those described in Deliverable 5.3. Figure 92-top shows in blue the estimated localization of the VIADDRONE and in red the estimated localization of the Total Station, used as ground truth. Figure 92-bottom shows the errors obtained in each coordinate axis, where the average error in the X-axis is 15.78cm, in the Y-axis is 24.37cm and in the Z-axis is 13.56cm. These results reveal the high accuracy of the aerial robot's localization system, which is critical to carry out the fully autonomous mission. The mission was repeated up to four times, demonstrating the robustness and reliability of the complete system.

Figure 92. VIAD-DRONE robot localization estimation in blue against the ground truth localization estimated with a Leica Total station in red (top) and the related localization errors (bottom) in the bearing visual inspection use case.

3.4.1. IoT Sensors

The use of IoT sensors explores different possibilities for a sensor node system to instrument bridges that are difficult to access and whose installation is approached through the use of a drone.

The main requirements of such a system are to achieve a compact node unit, low weight (less than 1.5 kg), with sufficient computational capacity to perform the necessary readings and data filtering for the correct monitoring of the bridge and with a battery life that is considered acceptable for the considered application.

In this sense, a system of sensor nodes with the possibility of wireless communication or internal data storage is the best alternative.

Due to the particularity of the installation method, where the operation should be simplified as much as possible, alternatives of sensor nodes are mainly explored that allow their direct installation on the

elements of the structure in a single package, without the need of manipulation or installation of complex or delicate external elements.

Main design would be based on the use of an inertial sensor, consisting of a triaxial accelerometer, gyroscope and magnetometer. This sensor allows the hardware to be used according to three different types of sensor nodes:

- Inclinometers: they provide information on the variations in the tilting of the piers, thus making it possible to control one of the essential parameters in bridge design regulations: angular distortion.
- Accelerometers: these provide information on the stiffness of the structure and its different elements, depending on their location, from the recording of bridge vibrations.
- Scour sensor: similar to the accelerometer sensor, the scour sensor is placed on the pier head to record the vibrations and thus know the presence and evolution of the scour phenomenon.

The main characteristics of the inertial sensor are long-term average stability, very low noise density and low power consumption. Sensors are selected on the basis of their characteristics, which ensure compatibility and reliability of records for structural health monitoring applications.

In addition to the electronics, the encapsulation of the node, which protects it from adverse weather conditions and brings together the rest of the components in a single unit, is particularly important. This requires a protective box, preferably made of ABS or Polycarbonate to favour a low weight, with IP65 or higher certification.

Figure 93. Example of inclinometer node installation.

a) Nodo inclinómetro

Use	measurement of pile tilt and sending to the server in real time		
Range	±2·g	Accuracy	3,9·µg
Sampling frequency	1·Hz	Measurement sampling	1·hour
Weight	425·g	Dimensions	145·x·95·x·55·mm
Endurance	3·months	Data transmission	Wireless, via ZigBee

b) Nodo acelerómetro

Use	Continuous vibration measurement and forwarding to server on real time		
Range	±E·g	Accuracy	15,·E·n
Sampling frequency	50·Hz	Measurement sampling	3s
Weight	42,5·€	Dimensions	14,5·x·95·v·55·MIRN
Endurance	14·days	Data transmission	Wireless, via ZigBee

Figure 94. Technical characteristics of the nodes.

Proposal for the Rio Verde Viaduct

After a preliminary analysis of the structure, it has been proposed the installation of 5 nodes with a single gateway for sending the registered information.

The location in the structure of the proposed node configuration is as shown in the following figure:

Figure 95. Location in the structure of the proposed node configuration.

Since the instrumented roadway was the one located to the south, in the Malaga-Almeria direction, due to its better accessibility on the footprint of the bridge. The distance between the furthest sensors has not exceed 65 metres.

The nodes have been arranged according to the following notations:

- Taking the central pointed arch as a reference, three accelerometers have been arranged in the span adjacent to the keystone of the arch in the NW direction. They have been placed at $3/8$, $1/2$ and $5/8$ of the span length from the keystone.

The frequency analysis of the vertical accelerations at different points of the deck allows us to know their frequencies and, indirectly, to obtain significant variations in its stiffness with respect to the values expected for a healthy state of the bridge.

The reason for proposing this specific distribution is that if only one accelerometer were installed at the centre span, preference would be given to the first mode of vibration of the bridge. Thus, through our approach, information from other modes of vibration would be obtained, since through this distribution all nodes would have excitation.

4. Tunnels Experiments

Egnatia Odos AE (EOAE) is the end user representing Tunnel Inspection operations on actual parts of the transport network. For the purposes of this final round of experiments, two different tunnels were used by the consortium (see next Section for further details). The experiments lasted for 10 days and EOAE with the support of INLECOM and the rest of the partners. The event was fully organised by the EOAE and INLECOM personnel, where EOAE was also responsible for the actual infrastructures provision, participants' safety, lanes closure, access and delivery as well as most aspects of the pilots validation, KPIs and feedback to the technical team

4.1. Description of Tunnel Location

The part of Egnatia motorway selected for these experiments, was the tunnel of Metsovo (in Ioannina) and a drainage tunnel very close to this one. These two tunnels were selected as i) the Metsovo tunnel indicates some interesting inspection points while is in full traffic and can represent traffic scenarios and realistic tunnel inspections and ii) the drainage tunnel used as a reference tunnel without any traffic (so experiments can run in safety) while indicates a concrete tunnel without internal lining that could represent tunnels under construction.

Figure 96. Exact area of inspections.

There were various different scenarios used, that are detailed below, that focused on i) experiment on various robotic missions' execution, ii) test procedures, mechanisms and configurations in real settings, iii) validate the system, create feedback and measure KPIs. The different scenarios used were created much before the experiments to make sure that all above, but also the tunnel and realistic settings (traffic, weather conditions, access), together with the robotic system peculiarities are fully covered and carefully considered before the actual visit.

The final type of validation scenarios included autonomous navigation such as placing the robot at the crosspassage near the defected/under inspection area, robot autonomously navigates in the tunnel through a set of waypoints while avoiding obstacles. In the same approach there were some other more inspection focused scenarios for the sensors activation as an actual mission execution. These included, robot autonomously navigating in the tunnel through a set of waypoints, robot stops at each point of interest and triggers cameras to take photos of the area, the robot automatically controlling the pan and tilt mechanism to take all images on one side of the tunnel, captured images are associated

with a location and a timestamp, images are viewed through the ground control station and time is automatically tracked in the mission data. Finally, some scenarios were created to test complete inspection missions using the developed digital workflow.

As two different tunnels were used, the scenarios above were adapted and organized in means to solve the operational difficulties of real tunnel inspection (some times in traffic). As described below, the scenarios were separated in road and drainage tunnel scenarios with local and general tunnel inspections for each.

Figure 97. road tunnel experiments (left) and the drainage tunnel experiments (right).

4.2. General Tunnel inspection

4.2.1. Road Tunnel

The general inspection was performed on a 300m distance area inside the road tunnel at Metsovo. The area is picked for the pilot due to the known defects that exist (Spallation/Rebar exposure areas and cracks). Images were captured, depicting one of the side walls of the tunnel, as we had access to one of the two traffic lanes for the purposes of the pilot.

A total of 397 images were gathered, portraying the designated area of interest. These images were obtained at three distinct elevations, each separated by intervals of 1.5 meters, while the capturing process maintained a constant operational distance of 1.8 meters, facilitated without any interruption in the robot's movement. This procedure incorporated a 20% overlap to ensure comprehensive coverage. The maximum point of capture was approximately 4 meters, utilizing the robotic arm fully extended to its 3-meter limit. Notably, an inspection image facilitates a region measuring 2.5 meters in width and 1.6 meters in height, possessing a resolution of 9504x6336 pixels.

Due to the continuous movement of the robot during the image capture process and the inadequate luminosity from the present lighting sources, a post-processing procedure was implemented on the acquired images to enhance their brightness. This adjustment was made feasible by the high-resolution nature of the captured images and the retained information within them.

Using the defect detection system on the captured inspection images, we are able to first train the system on the collected images and then to extract the potential defected areas. This includes the areas of interest with the spallation/rebar exposure as well as cracks that are in the area. Below some examples of the system are shown.

Figure 98. Input and predicted potential defected areas from the defect detection system on the images collected from the Metsovo road tunnel.

4.2.2. Drainage Tunnel

The general inspection was performed on a 40m distance area from the entrance inside the drainage tunnel at Metsovo. The area is picked for the pilot due to the known defects that exist (Spallation/Rebar exposure/Watering Sediments areas and cracks). Images were captured, depicting both side walls of the tunnel.

A total of 114 images were gathered, portraying the designated area of interest. These images were obtained at four distinct elevations, each separated by intervals of 1.5 meters, while the capturing process maintained a constant operational distance of 2 meters, facilitated without any interruption in the robot's movement. This procedure incorporated a 20% overlap to ensure comprehensive coverage. The maximum point of capture was approximately 4 meters, utilizing the robotic arm fully extended to its 3-meter limit. Notably, an inspection image facilitates a region measuring 2.8 meters in width and 1.8 meters in height, possessing a resolution of 9504x6336 pixels.

Using the defect detection system on the captured inspection images, we are able to first train the system on the collected images and then to extract the potential defected areas. This includes the areas of interest with the spallation/rebar exposure as well as cracks that are in the area. Below some examples of the system are shown.

Figure 99. Input and predicted potential defected areas from the defect detection system on the images collected from the Metsovo drainage tunnel.

4.2.3. FARO Laser Scanner

Within the framework of the comprehensive inspection protocol, the utilization of the FARO Laser scanner was employed in the tunnel experiments for the acquisition of three-dimensional (3D) scans, facilitating the depiction of defects with a remarkable level of precision, measured in millimeters. Notably, the scanning activities were directed towards local inspections of tunnels and were conducted in both road and drainage tunnel environments. The deployment of the CART robot was exclusively chosen for these experiments, attributed to the weight and dimensions of the scanner, rendering it impractical for drone-based transportation.

In terms of scanner resolution, a deliberate decision was made to employ a 43.7 megapixels per second (Mpxs)/3x quality setting. This choice was guided by the provision of a cloud point-to-point distance of 6.1mm at a range of 10 meters. Considering the proximity of the scanner to the tunnel wall (1 meter), the actual system accuracy, particularly towards the lane side of interest, was determined to be 0.6mm, which was deemed more than satisfactory for the intended system construction. The selection of a 3x quality was driven by the objective to optimize scan quality while concurrently minimizing scan duration. Subsequent modifications to these settings were implemented to achieve comparable accuracy with reduced precision, coupled with a decreased inspection time (less than 3 minutes), thereby facilitating application in the intricate operational contexts of the CART robot. Additionally, alterations were made to color preferences and subsequently tested, revealing that while color scanning did not impact accuracy, it did enhance the visual perception of the inspected points.

Aligned with the mission objectives, 3D laser scanning scenarios were executed as part of the experimental procedures. The inspection mission entailed stopping the CART robot at specified locations, followed by the execution of 3D laser scan measurements. The validation protocol assessed the seamless integration of the robotic system (CART) with the scanner interface, enabling the execution of scans under the explicit guidance of the robotic mission.

Exemplary instances of local inspections utilizing the laser scanner are illustrated below. Figure 100 portrays the amassed point cloud data with millimeter precision, while Figure 101 provides a rendered representation of the tunnel reconstructed in three dimensions. Diverse measurements and local computations can be performed through various methodologies and software packages.

Figure 100. Rendered image of the drainage tunnel reconstructed in 3D.

Figure 101. Rendered image of the drainage tunnel reconstructed in 3D.

Similarly, a 3D laser inspection was performed in the drainage tunnel as well. Some indicative results are presented below:

Figure 102. Rendered image of the drainage tunnel reconstructed in 3D.

Finally, we had the chance in close collaboration with EGNATIA and by expanding the scope of the project to gather several more detailed 3D laser scans with even higher accuracy at the cost of time. Since we were able to witness such a rare phenomenon form from its initial phase, we were able to collect data from different timeframes (every year) and conduct a thorough 3D deviation analysis that concluded into new findings regarding the status and the progress of the defect as well as provided EGNATIA with meaningful insights in terms of the current situation. As seen below (Figure 103) by comparing scans from 2020 till 2023 we notice 4 specific points of interest that show the highest deviation from 2020 to 2023.

Figure 103. 3D Deviation Analysis on the FARO Laser scans from 2020 to 2023.

4.2.4. Autonomous ground robot navigation

The navigation system for the ground robot (CART) generates a map in the form of a 3D point cloud. The map contains LIDAR points with high density as well as a sparse set of globally unique landmarks. The landmarks allow the system to relocalize and to correct for drift along the length of the tunnel. These landmarks are today a set of AprilTags that we stick on the walls of the tunnel with roughly 20m between.

Figure 104. APRIL tag stuck to wall of drainage tunnel.

To test the mapping and localization functionalities of the navigation, data gathering missions were performed along the length of both tunnels creating a map. See an example map from the drainage tunnel in Figure 105, and an example of the map generated on the road tunnel in Figure 106.

Figure 105. Top: Map from drainage tunnel. The map geometry in white / cyan, AprilTag landmarks in blue and carts trajectory in red. The yellow mark represents an actively observed AprilTag landmark and the pink represents the actively observed map geometry. Bottom: The robot platform at the entrance of the tunnel.

Figure 106. Top: Example map from the road tunnel, where the tests were done in a 300-meter section. The white / cyan is the map geometry and the blue are the AprilTag landmarks. The pink is the actively observed geometry and the yellow the actively observed AprilTag landmarks. Bottom: Robot platform during an autonomous inspection mission.

The results that can be highlighted are:

- The navigation system creates a map that is geometrically consistent with the environment.
- Localization in existing maps works well.
- Comparing estimated position with ground truth, positional RMSE is well below 1% on the 80-meter trajectory of the drainage tunnel.

For both tunnels, the initial step was to generate a map of the area the robot will operate autonomously in. This was achieved by the robot moving with a consistent speed through the area. Then this map was used for localization in the subsequent autonomous missions, where the localization data allowed the robot to consistently inspect points of interest. It was therefore imperative that the map generated was accurate. A total station, a tool for determining the position of an object with sub-centimeter accuracy, was available to check the quality of our positioning solution in the drainage tunnel. The results, (see table below) show a reasonably low RMSE. Unsurprisingly the error is significantly lower when localizing in an existing map vs localizing without an a-priori map. A comparison between the estimated and the ground truth trajectories, with and without a map in the figure below.

Ground truth positional data was unfortunately not available in the road tunnel; however, the maps were visually inspected and appeared good. Furthermore, everything with the localization results during the inspection missions went well, also indicating that the maps were good.

The road tunnel presented an additional potential issue for map generation, as it was in use by regular cars while the tests and missions were being worked on. Cars, and especially large trailers, can be mistakenly added to a map during the map generation phase. The easiest way to handle this would be to generate the map while no vehicles are in the tunnel. Due to some lucky traffic, a map of the entire area the robot would operate in was generated and used for the missions in the tunnel. Backup solutions where a map was generated by removing the dynamic objects from the scene was also tested on data with more traffic.

Table 14. Root mean squared error (RMSE) in meters from the two datasets where we have ground truth position as reported by the Leica total station available.

Run	RMSE (m)
Run 1 (no map, no tags)	0.353
Run 1 (with map and tags)	0.240
Run 2 (no map, no tags)	0.552
Run 2 (with map and tags)	0.320

Figure 107. Comparison of estimated trajectory (colored), and ground truth trajectory (gray dotted) from 2nd run in drainage tunnel. When localizing in an existing map (TOP) and when not using a map (BOTTOM).

With respect to the autonomous navigation, first it was tested basic missions where the robot was just commanded to cover certain distance at a stable speed. The objective here was to receive a waypoint and then command the robot to such point but with different constraints, such as maintaining the robot always at the same distance from the wall (this feature is critical for high quality data retrieval). The wall following feature was tuned in order to use a specific speed of 0.5m/s with waypoints at 4 to 5 meters apart. With such distance, it was successfully tested that autonomous navigation system the works ok in the road tunnel. However, the drainage tunnel presents a significant slope that complicated the navigation system since CART vehicle does only counts with the break coming from the engine itself. This aspect will be considered in order to improve the navigation system of the CART robotic vehicle and being able to also cope with tunnels with slope.

An additional challenge was introduced with the 1.5m steps data request in order to obtain images of the tunnel with enough overlapping for the visual inspection (see next section), which then needed a different configuration as the Ackermann kinematics needs a more aggressive action in order to reach goals with shorter distances. The current navigation system does not cope well with this requirement, and the navigation was not smooth enough. Then, this aspect will be also covered during the improvements of the navigation functionality of the CART robotic vehicle during the second development phase.

4.3. Local Tunnel inspection

The aim of this use case is to use the TTDRONE aerial vehicle to carry out a thorough on-site inspection of the tunnel and capture high quality images of the defects. For this purpose, two different scenarios are considered depending on the type of local inspection to be performed inside the tunnel.

On the one hand, in the first scenario, a portable localisation structure is used and, on the other hand, in the second scenario, both an aerial robot and a ground robot are used. It should be noted that the use of an aerial robot for local inspection has some advantages over general inspection by ground robots:

It can access hard-to-reach areas that the ground robot may not be able to reach. The UAV provides the flexibility to inspect almost any area.

Accurate inspection is achieved because the UAV can get close to the tunnel walls and take images at 1.5 metres from the wall. These images improve the accuracy of the general inspection measurements, providing a greater level of detail of the defects and also identifying new ones.

Figure 108 shows the two scenarios tested in the final experiments in the Metsovo tunnel. These scenarios were designed to demonstrate the functionalities of the developed system, in particular to evaluate the KPIs and to validate the requirements of the use case in a real tunnel, as presented in Section 5. and Annex I: Requirements Validation. In the following, each of the scenarios is described in detail and the results obtained are presented.

Figure 108. Scenarios considered in the local inspection of the tunnel in the final experiments. On the left is Scenario 1 where the TTDRONE is used with a portable localization system. On the right is Scenario 2, where the UAV and UGV are used together.

Scenario 1: aerial robot inspection using a portable localization system

The first scenario considered for carrying out the local tunnel inspection uses the TTDRONE aerial vehicle and a portable localization structure. This structure allows the drone to localize itself inside the tunnel for an autonomous mission. The objective is to place the portable structure in those areas where inspection is required. The applicability of this scenario is mainly focused on completing the inspection when defects are small and close together. The portable system can be easily dismantled and transported to any tunnel. It is also very easy to install. This minimizes costs and logistical issues when large areas do not need to be inspected. For this reason, the aerial vehicle is battery powered, unlike Scenario 2, which uses a tethered system. In addition, this system makes it possible to track the evolution of defects over time. It should be noted that it is not always necessary to follow the progress of all defects, sometimes only some are more critical and require more continuous maintenance. In these cases, the portable system is very useful, as it makes it possible to easily and quickly inspect defects that require special monitoring.

Figure 109. TTDRONE aerial robot (left) and portable localization system used in the final experiments of the Scenario 1.

Figure 109 shows the TTDRONE aerial vehicle, and the portable localization structure used in the final experiments in Scenario 1. It also shows the arrangement and number of ultra-wideband (UWB) sensors used to locate the vehicle in GNSS-denied environments. Extensive analysis was carried out to determine the optimum position and number of sensors required to minimize the position error inside the tunnel. The perception system was comprised of two LIDAR sensors, placed at the front and right side of the robot, a ultra-wideband sensor, at the rear of the robot and another four ultra-wideband sensors placed on the portable structure. More information on the localization techniques and sensors used can be found in Deliverable 5.3. Concerning the TTDRONE aerial vehicle, further information on the design and a detailed explanation of the individual components is provided in the Deliverable 4.3.

Scenario 2: aerial robot and ground robot inspection

The second scenario for carrying out the local inspection of the tunnel consists of the combined use of the TTDRONE aerial vehicle and the CART ground robot. The ground robot is responsible for the general inspection of the tunnel while the aerial robot has to perform the local inspection, providing a closer view of the inspection points. The UAV is attached to the ceiling of the CART by electromagnets and the ground robot moves to the points where it has previously detected potential defects. The UGV then stops at these points for the UAV to perform the local inspection. The aerial robot captures high quality images of these defects and inspects the areas that are difficult for the ground robot to access. The applicability of this scenario focuses on the inspection of large areas over long periods of time. This requires a ground robot to move the UAV to points of interest that may be a long way from the origin. Also, in this case, the aerial robot is powered by the tethered system, which increases the inspection time. The tethered system is placed inside the CART and allows the two robots to be connected (see Deliverable 8.1 for more information). The tether passes through the roof of the UGV and connects to the aerial module of the aerial vehicle installed on the underside of the UAV.

Figure 110. Hardware modifications made to the TTDRONE for the final experiments (left) and positioning of ultra-wideband sensors on the surface of the car for autonomous navigation inside the tunnel (right).

Several hardware modifications were required to enable the inspection to be conducted safely. Firstly, the height of the landing gear had to be increased. The purpose of this modification is to move the propellers away from the 3D Lidar at the front of the ground robot. The take-off and landing operations take place in a very confined space close to the Lidar, so extreme precautions must be taken to avoid damaging nearby equipment. On the other hand, a friction reducing part has been incorporated in the roof of the CART to minimize cable friction when the UAV is in flight. This part helps to make the cable exit smoother and more controlled. The left side of Figure 110 shows the new landing gear with the current distance to the 3D Lidar and the friction reducing part. As for the localization system, the ultra-wideband tags are placed on the surface of the CART, as shown in Figure 110. The number of sensors required, and their position have been analysed in detail in order to minimize the positioning errors of the aerial robot. To complete the perception system, the ultra-wideband anchor is placed on the TTDRONE, in the same way as in Scenario 1. Thus, five ultra-wideband sensors and two 2D Lidar sensors will be required to locate the aerial robot inside the tunnel (see Deliverable 5.3 for more information).

4.3.1. Drainage Tunnel Results

Two local inspection missions were performed in the tunnel. In order to assess the consistency of the system, both local inspection missions are identical. The testing area spans at 10m from the start of the tunnel and with help of Egnatia knowledge experts, 3 points of interest were identified. These areas of interest contain all the defects that the defect identification system tries to identify.

An inspection plan is required to carry out the local tunnel inspection in any of the above scenarios. For the final experiments, an inspection plan was designed in the Intelligence and Visualization Portal (IVP). In contrast to the first experiments, the map of the Metsovo drainage tunnel generated by the SINTEF payload was used. On this map, the end-user (Egnatia ODOS) can select the points of interest to be inspected by the aerial robot. Figure 111 shows the map used in the final experiments and uploaded to the IVP web portal. In addition, a few yellow markers can be seen, representing the points to be inspected by the TTDRONE in the tunnel. The point cloud provided the precision required to accurately locate the inspection points in the environment, enabling good inspection plan design and local inspection performance.

Figure 111. Visualization of the 3D map of the Metsovo tunnel and the inspection points defined by the end-user in the IVP. The point cloud is generated by the SINTEF payload.

In the final experiments, an inspection plan was defined consisting of four different inspection locations. This inspection plan was carried out both in Scenario 1 using the portable structure and in Scenario 2 using both the aerial and ground robots. The map of the Metsovo drainage tunnel and inspection points created in IVP are downloaded to the gRCS where the full mission is planned following the same procedure. Figure 112 shows the complete mission downloaded and running in the gRCS. This interface allows communicating with the aerial robot from the ground in real time and monitoring the drone's telemetry, battery status and consumption, inspection progress, inspection procedure time, etc. In addition, the gRCS autonomously controls the position of the aerial robot so that it can capture images in the inspection points from the specified distance. It also controls the position of the gimbal, considering both the position of the aerial robot and the location of the inspection points in the tunnel. Image capture with the inspection camera is commanded when the aerial robot is at the approach point of each inspection point.

Figure 112. Inspection plan created in the IVP and downloaded in gRCS to perform the tunnel local inspection with the TTDRONE.

Figure 113 illustrates a sequence of the TTDRONE performing the local inspection of the tunnel in Scenario 1. In this case, the landing and take-off point is on the tunnel floor. Figure 114 depicts the visual inspection performed by the TTDRONE in Scenario 2. In this case, the take-off and landing point is on the roof of the UGV. In both cases the planned mission is the same. Once the TTDRONE takes off, it begins autonomous navigation through the tunnel, capturing images at the inspection points defined in the inspection plan. The approach distance at which the images are taken is 1.5 metres from the tunnel wall and is defined in gRCS. The gimbal device is controlled autonomously

by the gRCS considering the robot pose and orientation with respect to each of the defects to be captured. The camera capture is also controlled autonomously by the gRCS.

Figure 113. TTDRONE in Scenario 1 performing the visual inspection of some defects in the Metsovo tunnel in the final experiments.

Figure 114. TTDRONE in Scenario 2 performing the visual inspection of some defects in the Metsovo tunnel in the final experiments.

The developed perception system allowed to accurately estimate the position of the aerial robot inside the tunnel in the two scenarios. In order to validate the localization system, the estimated position of the aerial robot was compared with a reference position (ground truth). Figure 115 shows the localization results for one of the many experiments carried out in Metsovo. The upper part of Figure 115 shows in blue the estimated localization of the TTDRONE in each coordinate axis and in red the estimated localization with the Total Station, which was used as ground truth. The lower part of Figure 115 shows the error between the estimated position and the ground truth on each axis. The average error is 9.7 cm on the x-axis, 9.6 cm on the y-axis, and 10.24 cm on the z-axis. It is worth noting the high accuracy of the localization system in the Metsovo drainage tunnel, allowing accurate autonomous inspections to be carried out. In particular, the results shown in Figure 115 were obtained performing an autonomous mission in Scenario 1. The localization method used in both scenarios is the same. Therefore, the positioning results of the aerial robot in each scenario are very similar, with no relevant differences between the cases considered. Only the arrangement of the ultra-wideband sensors affects the localization precision.

Figure 115. TTDRONE robot localization estimation in blue against the ground truth localization estimated with a Leica Total Station in red (top) and the related localization errors (bottom).

Once the tunnel inspection is complete, the data generated is uploaded to the IVP web portal. In this interface, the end-user can visualize the trajectory followed by the TTDRONE aerial robot and assess the captured images at each inspection point of interest. Figure 116 illustrates the inspection results obtained from one of the experiments carried out in the Metsovo tunnel. It shows a point cloud of the tunnel, with inspection points marked in green and defect capture locations marked with blue rectangles. In addition, each defect capture location contains an image, as shown by the red rectangles in Figure 117.

Figure 116. Results obtained from the execution of one of the visual local inspection plans. They were uploaded to the IVP after the final experiments.

Figure 117. Results obtained from the execution of one of the visual local inspection plans. Location of defect capture in the IVP contains an image taken with the TTDRONE inspection camera.

Finally, Figure 118 presents some images taken during the local inspection of the tunnel with the TTDRONE aerial robot. The images on the left of Figure 118 were captured on a different flight than the images on the right. The same defect can be observed in different flights, demonstrating the repeatability of both the TTDRONE localization system and the execution of the inspection mission. In addition, the images are of high quality, allowing the defects to be easily identified. This allows the precise control of the gimbal to be validated, taking into account the position and orientation of the robot with respect to each defect. Robustness and reliability in real-world conditions are proven when similar and highly accurate results are obtained in different missions.

Figure 118. Results from the tunnel local inspection obtained with the TTDRONE. Images of the left column were captured in a different flight from the images of the right column. Both flights were commanded by the gRCS following the same designed inspection plan.

The areas of interest are on both the sides of the walls as well as the crown of the tunnel. The captured images have a resolution of 6000x4000 pixels and with a working distance of 1.7m, they depict an area of 2.6m x 1.7m.

The system is able to detect and extract defected areas of the tunnel. The identified defects are:

- Spallation
- Rebar exposure
- Cracks
- Efflorescence

Below some examples of the system are shown.

Figure 119. Input and predicted defected areas from the defect identification system on the images collected from the Metsovo drainage tunnel.

4.3.2. Road Tunnel Results

Also, local inspection missions were conducted within the roadway tunnel, with specific attention directed towards two focal points. These points highlighted instances of Spallation and Rebar exposures, recognized by the experts affiliated with Egnatia. It is demonstrated that our team successfully identified and extracted the affected regions present within the tunnel. The identified defects are:

- Spallation
- Rebar exposure
- Cracks

Below some examples of the system are shown.

Figure 120. Input and predicted defected areas from the defect identification system on the images collected from the Metsovo road tunnel.

5. Evaluation of KPI's

This section summarizes the evaluation of the KPI's for each robotic solution as defined in PILOTING deliverable 3.2.

5.1. Refinery Pilot

5.1.1. Tank Inspection

Table 15. Tank - Large structure business KPIs.

ID	KPI	Achieved
RLS-KPI-B-01	Inspection Time; Reduce by at least 5 times the inspection time in comparison with traditional inspection procedures.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
<p>The AEROX platform is capable of doing this. The reduction in time required to erect scaffolding around a tank structure, and possible requirement to take a tank out of service is eliminated through the use of this technology. The AEROX platform was able to achieve full line scans on the tank within minutes, with the ability to then move to complete additional line scans as necessary. Extrapolation of inspection time shows what would normally take at least a day or two can be achieved in a matter of hours.</p>		
RLS-KPI-B-02	Inspection costs: Reduce the inspection bill by at least 25% by using robotic inspection technologies	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
<p>Yes, reduction in personnel involved, overall man hours, reporting time and equipment such as scaffolding and safety kit makes this a viable proposition to come in 25% under current costs.</p>		
RLS-KPI-B-03	Quality of inspection: Reduce subjective data interpretation, increase quality of gathered data and improve quality of inspection by using 100% digital information system that facilitates comparison and analysis of inspection data.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
<p>Inspection quality has been significantly improved for the phase 2 experiments. Both the roller probe assembly and the data processing logic were reworked. The matching between the hand-tool measurements and the platform's output resulted in a successful validation (max. error from 0.4 to 0.008 millimetres between test phases). Continuing with last year's inspection plan, the AEROX performed a new vertical line to demonstrate the repeatability in positional data.</p>		

RLS-KPI-B-04	Personal Safety: Reduce the number of hours of personnel working at height inspecting tank walls.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
Meets all safety criteria. The removal of personnel working at height and on scaffolding is a huge improvement on current work practices for tank inspection.		

Table 16. Tank - Large structure technical KPIs.

ID	KPI	Achieved
RLS-KPI-T-01	AEROX platform integrates the following hardware systems: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gas detection system. • Robotic device to perform contact operations. • RMCP as the end-effector. • Datalink for ground communications. 	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
The AEROX platform has successfully achieved full integration with all the previously listed systems. Thus, it included a gas-detecting sensor, a robotic device and RMCP (in the form of a robotic arm coupled with a crawler carrying the measuring tools), as well as the widely standardized MAVLink protocol (carrying out the role of communications datalink).		
RLS-KPI-T-02	AEROX platform integrates the following software systems: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Autonomous/Assisted navigation system while not in contact. • Autonomous control of the aerial platform while contacting the surface. • Force control over the surface. • Emergency procedures. 	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
The AEROX platform has demonstrated its ability to perform autonomous flights during contact operations, where only the approach to the targeted surface is manually assisted by the pilot. Furthermore, while on state of contact, the system keeps an automatic controlled force over the surface to maintain the RMCP in contact even in case of having external disturbances (such as wind). Throughout all AEROX's flight time, the platform was always ready to cope with the different considered emergencies (loss of communications, losing force over the surface, etc.).		
RLS-KPI-T-03	The AEROX platform is shipped to Oronite plant on a standard EUR-pallet by airfreight cargo. It is depalletized in a designated protected storage area and hand carrying to the deployment location on the asset.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No

<p>The AEROX system was indeed depalletized in a designated protected storage area from where it was later hand carried to the deployment location, but instead of an airfreighted EUR-pallet, a custom-design pallet was made for AEROX's safe ground transportation that was a little bit larger than a EUR-pallet.</p>		
RLS-KPI-T-04	The RMCP performs ultrasonic measurements with telemetry valid to generate an inspection report.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
<p>As it was shown in section 2. , it has been evidenced that the RMCP was capable of providing consistent telemetry in a valid format for report generation.</p>		
RLS-KPI-T-05	Repeatability of the measurements is possible between operations, with 10cm of precision.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
<p>Repeatability of the measurement location has been substantiated by means of a centimetre-accurate position estimator, that has been thoroughly tested against CATEC's ground truth systems. This position estimator, based on a total station, together with the 3D model of the asset and a real-time representation of the robotic vehicle position allows to repeat measurements with the desirable precision.</p>		
RLS-KPI-T-06	Wall thickness measurements are taken from 3mm to nominal	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
<p>The wall thickness accuracy was validated by way of comparison with a certified ultrasonic measurement hand tool in a set of different test points. The ultrasonic device was calibrated employing a 1018-Steel calibration block (25 to 5 millimetres) akin to the one used for phase 1 testing.</p>		
RLS-KPI-T-07	The AEROX platform meets the safety, operational and best practices requirements and procedures of a standard refinery.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
<p>The AEROX platform has repeatedly shown its compliance with all the required criteria regarding its operation in refinery grounds. Also, AEROX obtained an operational authorization for the aviation authorities (the same one that it is required for commercial aerial services).</p>		
RLS-KPI-T-08	Ground HMIs give access to the pilot and inspector to the required systems during the operation.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No

Developed HMIs have demonstrated a top-level integration that has facilitated a seamless operation of the AEROX system by the inspector and the aerial robot operator.

5.1.2. Vessel Inspection

Table 17. Vessel inspection business KPIs.

ID	KPI	Achieved
RV-KPI-B-01	Inspection Time; Reduce by at least 5 times the inspection time in comparison with traditional inspection procedures.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
<p>The BIKE platform can reduce the ‘inspection time’ by over 5 times based on current practices. This will be more pronounced in vessels with complex internals that are difficult for an operator to inspect manually. Preparation time for conducting a vessel inspection is not significantly reduced as vessels still require isolation, some form of manual cleaning and erection of scaffold to introduce the robot to the manway.</p>		
RV-KPI-B-02	Inspection costs: Reduce the inspection bill by at least 25% by using robotic inspection technologies	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
<p>Agree that overall the use of the BIKE platform when in frequent use to conduct a number of vessel inspections on a site could reduce the cost of inspection by 25% or more, by reducing the man hours required to inspect and verify measurements.</p>		
RV-KPI-B-03	Quality of inspection: Reduce subjective data interpretation, increase quality of gathered data and improve quality of inspection by using 100% digital information system that facilitates comparison and analysis of inspection data	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
<p>Quality of inspection is vastly improved through the BIKE platform. Inspection in confined spaces can be subjective but the BIKE with its 3D modelling package and localization accuracy gives more confidence in repeat and accurate inspection with standardized reporting.</p>		
RV-KPI-B-04	Personal Safety: Reduce the number of hours of personnel working in hazardous confined spaces performing internal pressure vessel inspections.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
<p>Meets all safety criteria. The removal of personnel working in confined and contaminated space is a huge improvement on current work practices for vessel inspection.</p>		

Table 18. Vessel inspection technical KPIs.

ID	KPI	Achieved
RV-KPI-T-01	System shipped to Chevron Oronite's Gonfreville plant on a standard EUR-pallet by airfreight cargo. Depalletizing in a designated protected storage area and hand carrying to the deployment location on the asset.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
Successfully tested as described in section 2.4 - Transportation		
RV-KPI-T-02	Capability of BIKE (crawler robot) driving on the surface of carbon steel materials, where the surface is oriented vertical, upright, and overhead. A non-magnetic layer on the surface and rubberized magnetic wheels of minimum total thickness 0.2 mm are to be accounted for.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
Successfully tested as described in section 2.4 - Mobility Capabilities and Safety Demonstration		
RV-KPI-T-03	Capability of the BIKE to be driven into the vessel by remote control from a manual deployment location on the manhole flange or its cylindrical branch. The BIKE can be driven through the transition from the manhole to the vessel shell. No infringement on the confined space of the vessel by the operator either during the manual deployment or the remote-controlled driving.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
Completed in the second set of experiments		
RV-KPI-T-04	Position determination accuracy in a vessel within 3 cm / 6 cm / 10 cm using a 3D model generated from provided 2D drawings of the asset. Deployment and approach to location repeated multiple times to establish repeat accuracy.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
As described in section 2.4 - Localization Demonstration and Map Verification, all tests were within 10cm. (worst case observed was 7cm deviation). With an improved environment model, 6 cm or better can be expected in a pressure vessel of similar dimensions.		
RV-KPI-T-05	Wall thickness measurements taken at a predefined location. Results stored with id number, absolute position and thickness value.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
Successfully tested as described in section 2.4 - Inspection Demonstration. Mission data files were successfully uploaded to the Data Harmonization Layer, including location, id number and thickness values.		
RV-KPI-T-06	Multiple wall thickness point measurements arranged in a grid pattern of a predefined area size and point spacing. Results are stored with id number and thickness values, as well as absolute position of the grid origin and relative values for each measurement point.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No

Successfully tested as described in section 2.4 - Inspection Demonstration. Mission data files were successfully uploaded to the Data Harmonization Layer, including location, id number and UT scanfiles for raster scan.		
RV-KPI-T-07	Detection of dangerous concentration of flammable gases (LEL). System response of removing any ignition source and alerting the user of danger.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
Successfully tested as described in section 2.4 - Mobility Capabilities and Safety Demonstration.		
RV-KPI-T-08	Preparation a predefined vessel area for subsequent inspection. Visual and ultrasound inspection performed before and after cleaning to establish impact on technique.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
Successfully tested as described in section 2.4 - Surface Preparation Demonstration.		
RV-KPI-T-09	Capability of system for automatic navigation of the robot to a predetermined point of interest.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
Successfully tested as described in section 2.4 - Inspection Demonstration.		
RV-KPI-T-10	Equipment and procedures fulfil the requirements of API 579-1/ASME FFS-1-2016 and API 510.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
The design of the inspection procedure and equipment is based on the requirements defined in API 579-1/ASME FFS-1-2016 and API 510 and extended by the requirements of the specific application.		
RV-KPI-T-11	Performance of visual inspection of tank interior. Images stored with identification number and absolute position of both robot and location of picture center on 3D model.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
Successfully tested as described in section 2.4 - Inspection Demonstration.		
RV-KPI-T-12	Live feed to operator or inspector of <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • UTM A-Scan • Camera • Location in 3D model 	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
Successfully tested as described in section 2.4 - Inspection Demonstration.		

5.1.3. Pipe Inspection while ground monitoring

Table 19. Pipes inspection and ground monitoring business KPIs.

ID	KPI	Achieved
PGM-KPI-B-01	Inspection Time; Reduce by at least 5 times the inspection time in comparison with traditional inspection procedures.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
<p>HYBRID platform and IoT sensors have the potential to reduce the time taken to conduct inspection on pipework. This is particularly evident when dealing with pipe work at height on congested racks where inspection access or leak detection is challenged. The ground monitoring vehicles can also reduce inspection times, this is most evident in remote locations where a resident ground vehicle could be deployed to an inspection point much faster than a person having to travel to/from a facility.</p>		
PGM-KPI-B-02	Inspection costs: Reduce the inspection bill by at least 25% by using robotic inspection technologies	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
<p>For pipework at Height – YES there would be a marked saving on inspection cost due to reduction in safety and at height equipment to access pipework. For ground monitoring vehicles, the cost saving is no a driving factor for deployment and likely would not be competitive version a human operator, however the safety benefits out weight this cost saving and still makes Ground monitoring a viable work stream for robotics in a refinery environment</p>		
PGM-KPI-B-03	Quality of inspection: Reduce subjective data interpretation, increase quality of gathered data and improve quality of inspection by using 100% digital information system that facilitates comparison and analysis of inspection data	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
<p>All of the robotic platforms from HYBRID, IoT sensors and Ground vehicles are proven capable of acquiring repeat and accurate data from pipework, vessels, large structures and other key ground inspection points.</p>		
PGM-KPI-B-04	Personal Safety: Reduce the number of hours of personnel working at height inspecting pipes.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
<p>Meets all safety criteria. The removal of personnel working at height is a huge improvement on current work practices for pipe and large structure inspection.</p>		

<p>PGM-KPI-B-05</p>	<p>Quality of data: Reduce subjective data interpretation, increase quality of gathered data and improve quality of operational plant checks by using 100% digital information system that facilitates comparison and analysis of operational data</p>	<p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No</p>
<p>All data gathered by UGV is made available for analysis by means of the IVP. A wholistic sensor data acquisition approach ensures that an extensive set of details of the inspection and manipulation session of the UGV is stored and uploaded through the DDHL to the DMS. This also means that a comparison of subsequent missions conducted at different times becomes feasible. This data-driven approach provides a valuable tool for both operators and inspectors.</p>		
<p>PGM-KPI-B-06</p>	<p>Personal Safety: Reduce the number of hours of personnel working in hazardous areas performing routine operations.</p>	<p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No</p>
<p>Meets all safety criteria. The removal of personnel working in dirty congested pipe racks is a huge improvement on current work practices for pipe inspection and the removal of people from dirty and congested spaces (Vessels) or the need to travel to a site for ground inspection purposes is an important use case for robotics.</p>		

Table 20. Pipes inspection and ground monitoring technical KPIs.

ID	KPI	Achieved
<p>PGM - KPI-T-01</p>	<p>Hybrid vehicle integrates the following hardware systems:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gas detection system • Landing and attachment system. • Photographic camera. • Satellite robot for precise ultrasonic inspection. • Datalink for ground communications. 	<p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No</p>
<p>The HYBRID was tested as a fully integrated system including all the mentioned systems.</p>		
<p>PGM - KPI-T-02</p>	<p>Hybrid vehicle integrates the following software systems:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Advanced Autonomous navigation and motion planning system. • Detect and Avoid system. • Autonomous landing system (including decision making on well clearance area). • Emergency procedures. 	<p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No</p>

<p>The HYBRID robot integrated all the mentioned software systems. However, and it was previously commented, it was decided that this iteration of the aerial robot was not permitted to fly due to safety concerns.</p>		
PGM-KPI-T-03	The Hybrid vehicle is shipped to Oronite plant on a standard EUR-pallet by airfreight cargo. It is depalletized in a designated protected storage area and hand carrying to the deployment location on the asset.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
<p>The HYBRID system was transported to site using a truck, but stored in custom-designed pallet for safe transportation of equivalent size of a standard EUR-pallet. At site, it was hand carried from the storage area to the deployment location.</p>		
PGM-KPI-T-04	The Satellite robot (of the Hybrid vehicle) performs ultrasonic measurements at least 1m far from the landing point and with telemetry valid to generate an inspection report.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
<p>Full remote inspection was performed using the integrated HYBRID system and cross-verified with manual measurements by a qualified NDT engineer.</p>		
PGM-KPI-T-05	The Satellite robot (of the Hybrid vehicle) performs inspections as described in D3.1/ RP-DA-(45-47, 52-53).	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
<p>It has been demonstrated that the system is capable of performing inspections in line with the stated requirements.</p>		
PGM-KPI-T-06	Repeatability of the measurements is possible between operations, with 2cm relative precision along and around the pipe (3, 6, 9 and 12 positions).	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
<p>The satellite was shown to be capable of positioning itself on a predefined location with accuracy well below 2 cm.</p>		
PGM-KPI-T-07	Wall thickness measurements are taken from 3mm to nominal.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
<p>A standard UT step gauge with step sizes from 2.5 to 20 mm was used to calibrate the complete system prior to the measurement of pipes with nominal wall thicknesses around 8.18 mm.</p>		

PGM-KPI-T-08	The Hybrid vehicle meets the safety, operational and best practices requirements and procedures of a standard refinery.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
Thanks to the knowledge acquired with other robust platforms as AEROX, HYBRID platform has shown its capabilities and compliance with the required criteria for also pipe landing operations.		
PGM - KPI-T-09	Robot control station HMIs give access to the pilot and inspector to the required systems during the operation.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
For the scope tested, the HYBRID satellite and UT inspection system was remote operated by a pilot and inspector using only the HMI and without direct line of sight to the robot.		
PGM - KPI-T-10	Images obtained by the Hybrid vehicle are used to automatically detect corrosion in the refinery infrastructure using PILOTING AI services.	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
Automatic detection of corrosion performed with images obtained by AERO-CAM. Same set up of camera and gimbal could be integrated in HYBRID		
PGM - KPI-T-11	<p>Ground robot integrates the following hardware systems:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Gas detection system ● Traction system that allows for: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Operation on a range of different surfaces (e.g. gravel, grating) - Climbing stairs <p>Datalink for ground communications.</p> <p>Robot manipulator with force sensor</p>	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
<p>Hardware systems were integrated for both RISING and RB-Watcher Robots. However in both cases the manipulator was disassembled as dedicated tests were performed with a different robot.</p> <p>The climbing stairs ability is also partially demonstrated in a lab environment with the RISING robot, and it is only achievable depending on the steepness of the steps.</p>		
PGM - KPI-T-12	The ground robot builds a 3D map representation of the plant area to inspect in teleoperation mode.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
Both ground robots are able to compete a 3D representation using only on-board sensors.		

PGM - KPI-T-13	The ground robot autonomously navigates on prebuilt 3D map following predefined inspection paths and waypoints or returning to a predefined base checkpoint.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
UGV and RISING has followed the inspection plan in autonomous manner.		
PGM - KPI-T-14	The ground robot autonomously detects and avoids obstacles while continuing with the inspection plan.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
Added obstacles no present in the prebuilt map were successfully avoided.		
PGM - KPI-T-15	The ground robot automatically detects and reads analogue gauges of 100mm diameter.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
Detection and reading was validated with several analogue pressure gauges located in the refinery.		
PGM - KPI-T-16	The ground robot automatically detects and localizes small hand wheel valves.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
Detection was validated with several hand wheel valves located in the refinery.		
PGM - KPI-T-17	The ground robot's manipulator can identify the state of small hand wheel valves (open/close) and change it according to a high-level operator's command.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
Change of valve state was validated with different high-level relative angular operator commands. Identification of state requires additional tracking information on symmetrical valves.		
PGM - KPI-T-18	The ground robot logs visual and thermal images, and audio, with timestamp and associated pose with respect to the prebuilt 3D map.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
Visual and thermal images and the metadata with poses and timestamp have been successfully recorded and compiled in the mission files. Camera streams and additional data can be retrieved from a log file.		

PGM - KPI-T-19	Ground robot is able to charge autonomously.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
Wireless charger station has been validated as well as the commands to start recharging.		
PGM - KPI-T-20	Ground robot is dustproof and waterproof.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
Robot operation has been successfully tested under different conditions and also with light rain		
PGM - KPI-T-21	The ground robot can be transported and deployed by one person at any time.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
Robot can be teleoperated into and out of the box in an easy way. The specifically designed transportation box can be moved (with its on wheels) and manipulated by one person.		

5.2. Viaduct Pilot

5.2.1. Visual Inspection (including surveying target installation)

Table 21. Visual inspection and survey target installation business KPIs.

ID	KPI	Achieved
VVI-KPI-B-01	Reducing by at least 5 times the inspection time in comparison with tradition inspection procedures.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
Currently, inspection systems are based on human vision or by non-contact means, which in the vast majority of cases prevents the inspection of all the connections between the moving elements located below the deck and above the pier. Piloting case, speeds are reduced to 5 times because in the same inspection process the conditions of all parts of the viaduct can be assessed, thus avoiding the use of other types of much more complex instrumentation.		
VVI - KPI-B-02	Reducing the inspection bill by at least 25% thanks of the use of robotics technologies.	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No

<p>Currently, data monitoring systems are particularised to each measurement site and based on point data rather than mass data. With the development of mass imaging and mass data capture, artificial intelligence techniques can be used to simplify and standardise the process.</p> <p>The process is considered partially achieved as the objectives for the training viaducts are met but design variability prevents it from being applicable to all types of structures without exception.</p>		
VVI - KPI-B-03	Reduce subjective data interpretation, increase quality of gathered data and improve quality of inspection by using 100% digital information system that facilitates comparison and analysis of inspection data.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
<p>The amount of data collected has increased considerably, which implies a substantial improvement in the amount of information. During phase II work will be done on filtering and optimising the processed information.</p>		
VVI - KPI-B-04	Reducing to zero the number of work accidents due to exposure to dangerous environments or work at	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
<p>Yes, due to 100% reduction of manual tasks during inspection with drones. Also, the use of heavy machinery is reduced drastically.</p>		
VVI - KPI-B-05	Visual inspection can be repeated (e.g. every month) in a consistent manner, allowing continuous monitoring.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
<p>Yes, AERO-CAM has a non GNSS-dependent global positioning system that allows repeat inspections in a consistent way by relating all the data obtained to the same 3D model.</p>		

Table 22. Visual inspection and survey target installation technical KPIs.

ID	KPI	Achieved
VVI-KPI-T-01	The UAV integrates the following hardware systems: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Image stabilization system (gimbal) for horizontal and vertical surfaces adaptable to different types of cameras. • Datalink for ground communications. • Localization sensors for GNSS denied environments. • Lighting system for precise pictures 	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
<p>AERO-CAM includes a gimbal that allows photography of horizontal and vertical surfaces, as well as adapting to different cameras. The UAV establishes communication with the ground and has location sensors such as LiDAR and IMU. The camera has the ability to install a flash, if necessary.</p>		

<p>VVI - KPI-T-02</p>	<p>The UAV integrates the following software systems:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Autonomous navigation system for GNSS denied environment. • Mission planner logger. • Camera pointer and stabilization system. • An obstacle avoidance system that ensures that: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The pilot is warned when the aerial robot is closer than 10m to an obstacle. • An alarm is activated once the UAV is closer than 2m. • The UAV automatically stops once it is closer than 1m to the obstacle. • Emergency procedures. 	<p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No</p>
<p>AEROCAM- integrates all these software systems and procedures. Also, all these software systems have been validated in a real viaduct. The VIAD-DRONE integrates autonomous navigation for GNSS denied environments, mission planner logger and emergency procedures. It integrates a camera pointer and stabilization system when the camera add-on is installed. Since the main purpose of the VIAD-DRONE is to perform tasks in close proximity or in contact with the viaduct surfaces, the functionalities related to warnings and automatic stops at 10, 2 and 1 m. of an obstacle do not apply in this case.</p>		
<p>VVI - KPI-T-03</p>	<p>Image quality is high enough to detect defects during the first part of the mission, and high enough to be able to measure with accuracy of 0,1mm.</p>	<p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No</p>
<p>Images obtained with the camera are of a resolution of 9504x6336 px. In addition, the configuration of the 85mm lens allows to measure with an accuracy of 0,1mm from the distance the UAV usually flights from the surface of the viaducts.</p>		
<p>VVI - KPI-T-04</p>	<p>The positioning system is accurate enough to localize the defects with an error of less than 20cm, ensuring that the UAV to return to those defects detected during the first mission.</p>	<p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No</p>
<p>Yes, AERO-CAM has a global and relative localization system that allows the robotic platform to accurately photograph defects.</p>		
<p>VVI - KPI-T-05</p>	<p>The UAV flies under windy conditions of, at least, 3 m/s</p>	<p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No</p>
<p>Yes, AERO-CAM flew in those wind conditions during the first pilots of the project.</p>		

VVI - KPI- T- 06	Robot control station HMIs give access to the pilot and inspector to the required systems during the operation.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
The gRCS and mRCS allow full control of the inspection and display all the information necessary for the execution of the inspection. From the pictures taken and visual feedback of where the camera is pointing to numerical data such as battery, flight altitude, etc.		
VVI - KPI- T- 07	The UAV meets the safety, operational and best practices requirements and procedures for a viaduct inspection.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
AERO-CAM meets the safety requirements from the aviation authorities to fly on the viaduct. In addition to the legal permits and coordination, all necessary safety precautions were taken.		
VVI - KPI- T- 08	<p>The aerial robot in charge of the survey target installation integrates the following systems:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Autonomous navigation system for GNSS denied environment. • Robotic manipulator to stick the survey targets to the viaduct pillars. • Mission planner logger. 	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
The VIAD-DRONE platform integrates all the above systems and, its hardware configuration for the survey target installation carries a pole with a retractile mechanism on the tip, which allows to place the targets with a touch and go manoeuvre. In addition, the aerial robot was able to autonomous navigate in the environment using the on-board sensors measurements and without requiring GNSS information. The state of the mission execution (the telemetry of the drone, time of the mission, the installation location, etc.) was monitored and logged from the ground by the gRCS.		
VVI - KPI- T- 09	The aerial robot sticks the passive survey targets next to the points of interest, with a precision of at least 50 cm, which allows being included inside the precise picture.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
Mean errors of the estimated VIAD-DRONE localization are less than 50 cm, which enabled both the accurate navigation of the robot in the environment and the target installations near to the defects to be inspected with less than 50 cm of precision.		
VVI - KPI- T- 10	System shipped to the Viaduct location on a standard EUR-pallet by airfreight cargo. Depalletizing in a designated protected storage area and hand carrying to the deployment location on the asset.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No

For operational reasons and due to the proximity of the viaduct to CATEC's facilities, the AERO-CAM was transported on a van without a EUR-pallet, but is designed to fit on one if necessary.

5.2.2. Bearing Inspection

Table 23. Bearing inspection business KPIs.

ID	KPI	Achieved
VBI-KPI-B-01	Reducing by at least 5 times the inspection time in comparison with tradition inspection procedures.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
<p>The use of remote data collection techniques using drones, images and sensors significantly reduces collection times. It is possible to standardise the viaducts by classification, reducing even further the time required.</p>		
VBI-KPI-B-02	Reducing the inspection bill by at least 25% thanks of the use of robotics technologies.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
<p>The costs are currently not very expensive due to the fact that visual inspections do not cover more than 15% of the structure. Today, the use of non-contact capture techniques and the systematisation of the survey analysis by artificial intelligence techniques are modifying the amount of the survey, therefore it is possible to reduce the cost of capturing one hundred percent of the data.</p>		
VBI-KPI-B-03	Reduce subjective data interpretation, increase quality of gathered data and improve quality of inspection by using 100% digital information system that facilitates comparison and analysis of inspection data.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
<p>The amount of data collected has increased considerably, which implies a substantial improvement in the amount of information. During phase II work will be done on filtering and optimising the processed information.</p>		
VVI-KPI-B-04	Reducing to zero the number of work accidents due to exposure to dangerous environments or work at height	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
<p>Yes, due to 100% reduction of manual tasks during inspection with aerial robots. Also, the use of heavy machinery has been reduced drastically.</p>		

VBI-KPI-B-05	Bearing inspection can be repeated (e.g.: every month) in a consistent manner, allowing continuous monitoring	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
<p>Yes, the VIAD-DRONE is able to take high quality images of the bearings with a localization error < 15 cm, allowing for continuous monitoring.</p>		
VBI-KPI-B-06	Bearing inspection provide with enough accuracy to measure defects in a consistent and objective manner.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
<p>Sensors accuracies used and the control & verification procedures allow us to validate the system for a priori accuracies in the order of 5 mm in length and 0.5 g in gravity. For imaging systems, the accuracies obtained do not depend on the 20 megabits of the camera, but we have confirmed that it is adequate to be able to calibrate a process with an accuracy of less than one millimetre.</p>		
VBI-KPI-B-07	System is suitable for inspecting bearings in different typologies of bridges with different types of bearings (neoprene, POT...).	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
<p>Not all bearings are visible, Pot models are enclosed in a box and the system would not allow image captures, so they are excluded from this system. For the rest, as long as it is possible to make an image capture, we would be able to create a useful system to robotise the process by air platforms, robotics drones and artificial intelligence techniques.</p>		

Table 24. Bearing inspection technical KPIs.

ID	KPI	Achieved
VBI-KPI-T-01	The aerial robot integrates the following systems: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Autonomous navigation system for GNSS denied environment. • Image stabilization system for the inspection camera. • Mission planner logger 	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
<p>The VIAD-DRONE system integrates all the above-mentioned systems. The robot was able to autonomously navigate in a GNSS-denied environment carrying an image stabilization device for the inspection camera. The execution of the different inspection plans (telemetry of the drone, inspection locations, gathered sensor measurements, time of the missions, etc.) was monitored and logged by the gRCS from the ground.</p>		
VBI-KPI-T-02	The aerial robot is able to perform visual inspection of the bearings from all their sides, i.e., the external and the internal sides.	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No

<p>VIAD-DRONE has been validated performing visual inspection of the bearings from the external sides and internal sides with visibility, so in some viaduct configurations with single bearings and bearing visibility it is possible the inspection from all the sides. The VIAD-DRONE is able to inspect the internal sides of the bearings in some configurations, but it has not been validated in the pilot.</p>		
VBI-KPI-T-03	The aerial robot flies under windy conditions of, at least, 3 m/s.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
<p>The VIAD-DRONE flew under the above-mentioned wind conditions in the viaduct location. Anemometer sensors were used to validate it.</p>		
VBI-KPI-T-04	The robot control station displays live video from the images taken on-board the UAV.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
<p>Measurements gathered by the on-board sensors of the VIAD-DRONE platform (camera and LIDAR sensors) were visualized and monitored from the ground.</p>		
VBI-KPI-T-05	System shipped to the Viaduct location on a standard EUR-pallet by airfreight cargo. Depalletizing in a designated protected storage area and hand carrying to the deployment location on the asset.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
<p>Due to the proximity of the viaduct to facilities of the University of Seville, the VIAD-DRONE was safely transported on a van without a EUR-pallet to the viaduct location, but is designed to fit on one if required.</p>		

5.2.3. *Sensor Installation*

Table 25. Sensors installation business KPIs.

ID	KPI	Achieved
VSI-KPI-B-01	Wireless monitoring of viaducts using sensors to be placed on top of pillars that currently are not installed due to accessibility restrictions.	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
<p>The VIAD-DRONE has demonstrated and validated in the pilots the capability of placing a sensor box on top of the pillars that now are not monitored due to accessibility restrictions. However, the installed devices were mockup sensor boxes without the sensors, so the actual wireless monitoring has not been validated.</p>		

VSI-KPI-B-02	Reducing to zero the number of work accidents due to exposure to dangerous environments or work at height.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
Yes, due to 100% reduction of manual tasks during inspection with aerial robots. Also, the use of heavy machinery has been reduced drastically.		

Table 26. Sensors installation technical KPIs.

ID	KPI	Achieved
VSI-KPI-T-01	The aerial robot integrates the following systems: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Autonomous navigation system for GNSS denied environment. • Sensor installation system that allows installing sensors of different shapes and sizes. • Mission planner logger 	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
The VIAD-DRONE system integrates all the above-mentioned systems. The robot was able to autonomously navigate in a GNSS-denied environment. The cargo system, responsible for carrying the sensor box and deploying it, is designed to work with standard and also taller sensor boxes. The execution of inspection plans (telemetry of the drone, inspection locations, gathered sensor measurements, time of the missions, etc.) was monitored and logged by the gRCS from the ground.		
VSI-KPI-T-02	The aerial robot is able to install a sensor box in reduced and difficult to access spaces and in a consistent manner.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
Yes, the VIAD-DRONE installed the sensor box on top of the pillar several times during the pilots.		
VSI-KPI-T-03	The aerial robot flies under windy conditions of, at least, 3 m/s.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
The VIAD-DRONE flew under the above-mentioned wind conditions in the viaduct location. Anemometer sensors were used to validate it.		
VSI-KPI-T-04	The robot control station displays live video from the images taken on-board the UAV.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
Measurements gathered by the on-board sensors of the VIAD-DRONE platform (camera and LIDAR sensors) were visualized and monitored from the ground.		

VSI-KPI-T-05	System shipped to the Viaduct location on a standard EUR-pallet by airfreight cargo. Depalletizing in a designated protected storage area and hand carrying to the deployment location on the asset.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
<p>Due to the proximity of the viaduct to facilities of the University of Seville, the VIAD-DRONE was safely transported on a van without a EUR-pallet to the viaduct location, but is designed to fit on one if required.</p>		

5.3. Tunnel Pilot

5.3.1. General Inspection

Table 27. Tunnel general inspection business KPIs.

ID	KPI	Achieved
TG-KPI-B-01	Reducing by at least 5 times the time required for detailed inspection of tunnel concrete intrados in comparison with tradition inspection procedures.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
<p>The existing conventional way using EGNATIA's inspection procedures prescribes an almost 3h (180 minutes) work for 200m inspection (at two different heights). The approach used in PILOTING indicated the following measured times:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 45m of drainage tunnel, at 3 different heights, in less than 8 minutes • 900m of road tunnel, 3 different heights, in less than 50 minutes. <p>A consideration is that the time consumed is not linear as the reposition of the cameras is performed 3 times in a fixed timing (around 1 minute each)</p> <p>Thus concluding in the following benchmark and KPI achievement.</p>		
TG-KPI-B-02	Reducing the inspection cost by at least 30% thanks of the use of robotics technologies. (Considering the whole tunnel maintenance life cycle)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
<p>Since the required inspection time is 41% of the total time when comparing the conventional means, we expect a similar reduction in costs.</p>		
TG-KPI-B-03	Reduce subjective data interpretation, increase quality of gathered data and improve quality of inspection by using 100% digital information system that facilitates comparison and analysis of inspection data.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No

<p>Using the automatic robotic inspection, subjective data interpretation is drastically removed as the approach used uses 100% digital systems. This is related to robotic system positioning, sensor systems positioning, automatic measurements and analysis of inspection data.</p> <p>Also, the robot can capture images always with the same angle of the camera while with conventional ways it is difficult having the same angle for each capture.</p> <p>Moreover, capturing images or laser scans every 'X' meters is more accurate with the robot rather than manual methods.</p>		
TG-KPI-B-04	Reducing to zero the number of work accidents due to exposure to dangerous environments	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
<p>This KPI is verified indirectly as it is not possible to compare accident rates. Instead, we investigated work accidents as being reduced due to the following factors:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Decreased inspection time being 5 times less the required of the time in comparison with traditional methods • Reduced personnel • Reduced road blocking and deviations required <p>Reduced exposure to traffic, truck or supporting vehicles</p>		
TG-KPI-B-05	Reducing the time and the cost of after inspection reporting / representation of findings/ interpretation of findings by 10 times in comparison with conventional in house or outsourcing consultancy	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
<p>The after-inspection time and precision of results has been drastically improved following fully automated results aggregation, reporting and formatting. Particular user interfaces (IVP) have been designed to present results in a more user- friendly approaches, as indicated, specified and validated by different end-users. It is planned for the second pilot campaign to perform complete inspections and measure this reduction time.</p>		
TG-KPI-B-06	Increasing the completeness, accuracy, objectivity of the structural evaluation of tunnel, in comparison with conventional in house or outsourcing assessment	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
<p>The after-inspection time and precision of results has been drastically improved following fully automated results aggregation, reporting and formatting. Particular user interfaces (IVP) have been designed to present results in a more user- friendly approaches, as indicated, specified and validated by different end-users. On top, the automation of specific, high-accuracy apparatus (3D laser scanner) fully integrated with autonomous robotic systems provides greatly increased completeness evaluation of tunnels under inspection.</p>		

Table 28. Tunnel general inspection technical KPIs.

ID	KPI	Achieved
TG-KPI-T-01	The robotic ground vehicle will operate fully autonomously.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
<p>The robotic vehicle can navigate and follow a mission plan (including data capturing and precise geo-location) once the mission is triggered. It is assumed that a valid map is already available, through a mapping session where the vehicle is manually operated.</p>		
TG-KPI-T-02	The robotic ground vehicle will inspect tunnel segments up to 1 km in length in a single mission.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
<p>Successful mission captured data of more than 900m in less than 50 minutes.</p> <p>It is assumed that KPI is achieved since nothing is restricting the mission for even more lengths.</p> <p>There might be a misunderstanding on how this 1km segment is measured (either as a straight line, as a curved line following the tunnel walls or as the distance covered by the vehicle in the middle of the lane).</p>		
TG-KPI-T-03	The robotic ground vehicle will measure its position within the tunnel with an accuracy of 10 cm from the tunnel entrance under the following conditions: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No GNSS coverage • No fixed lighting or partial lighting 	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
<p>The accuracy is a few decimetres, measured as RMSE.</p> <p>The average error is really close to the 10cm, but specific numbers of the SINTEF's payload accuracy are already discussed in deliverable 5.4</p>		
TG-KPI-T-04	Within inspected tunnel segments, the robotic ground vehicle will measure the following values to within an accuracy of 10 cm: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tunnel diameter • Segment length • Width of the paved road surface • 3D location of defects 	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
<p>The 3D laser scanner has been fully integrated on the robotic vehicle (CART) and provides inspections at the required points. The process is fully automated following the robotic mission execution and the laser scanner performs inspections with an accuracy of 1 millimetre (could be even higher in some cases). Also, thanks to the information from the CART vehicle it is possible to locate defect within 10 cm accuracy.</p>		

<p>TG-KPI-T-05</p>	<p>The robotic ground vehicle will capture inspection imagery of a sufficient quality to enable automatic detection of the following defects:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cracks • Spalling • Corrosion stains • Exposed bars • Damp areas or water leakage areas • Calcium leaching areas (salt deposits in general) <p>Under the following conditions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No fixed lighting or partial lighting • In the presence of moving vehicles (headlights) 	<p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Partially</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> No</p>
<p>The captured images have a sufficient quality to enable automatic defect detection. Results from the AI systems show that, defects that datasets were available to train the systems, are able to be correctly identified and extracted from areas of interest. Even though, from the mentioned defects, corrosion stains and calcium leaching areas are not tested, as the developed AI systems do not try to identify these defects, due to the lack of annotated data for the systems to be trained on, the captured images have a sufficient quality to enable automatic detection when training data is available.</p>		
<p>TG-KPI-T-06</p>	<p>The robotic ground vehicle will have the following capabilities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ground clearance of at least 20 cm and suspension system enabling operation on rough surfaces (e.g. asphalt, gravel) • Tolerate up to 15 cm standing water • Tolerate up to 15 deg surface inclination • Max dimensions 3.5 m x 2.5 m x 2 m and max weight 2t to be transportable by truck • Max width 2.5 m to fit within a single road lane • Operational range of at least 10 km or 2 hr • Obstacle avoidance for trespassing vehicles, humans and objects max 20cm height from the ground. • Batteries rechargeable on-site 	<p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Partially</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> No</p>
<p>All of the robot capabilities were tested against rough conditions, specially in accessory drainage tunnel where those were present.</p>		

TG-KPI-T-07	The robotic ground vehicle will operate safely, have will have the following functions: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Onboard safety lights and relevant warning placards • Remote emergency shut down • Manual control override 	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
All 3 functionalities were present. Manual override and emergency shut down were also consistently tested by driving the robot in manual mode and triggering the radio e-stop before moving.		
TG-KPI-T-8	The robotic ground vehicle will have continuous wireless communications link with the ground control station such that inspection images and robot pose can be viewed live.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
Updated performance in last tests demonstrate the KPI is achieved. Difficulties with multiple operators at a time where resolved with reworked networks and addition of PtP omnidirectional antennas. Live data can also be seen now, either within a remote GCS or directly in the onboard tablet that presents this information together with some user-selectable parameters for current mission.		
TG-KPI-T-9	The data capture by the robot allows measuring the actual deformed geometry of tunnel perimeter along the inspection path, with an accuracy of 1-2cm.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
The 3D laser scanner has been fully integrated on the robotic vehicle (CART) and provides inspections at the required points. The process is fully automated following the robotic mission execution and the laser scanner performs inspections with an accuracy of 1 millimetre (could be even higher in some cases).		

5.3.2. Local Inspection

Table 29. Tunnel local inspection business KPIs.

ID	KPI	Achieved
TL-KPI-B-01	Reducing by at least 5 times the time required for detailed inspection of tunnel concrete intrados in comparison with tradition inspection procedures.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
TT-DRONE for capturing images at 8 points only required 2 min and 30 sec. In comparison with traditional methods this is a great improvement.		

TL-KPI-B-02	Reducing the inspection cost by at least 30% thanks of the use of robotics technologies. (Considering the whole tunnel maintenance life cycle)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
<p>Since the required inspection time is 5 times faster when comparing the conventional means, we expect a similar reduction in costs.</p>		
TL-KPI-B-03	Reduce subjective data interpretation, increase quality of gathered data and improve quality of inspection by using 100% digital information system that facilitates comparison and analysis of inspection data.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
<p>Using the automatic robotic inspection, subjective data interpretation is drastically removed as the approach used uses 100% digital systems. This is related to robotic system positioning, sensor systems positioning, automatic measurements and analysis of inspection data. Also, the robot can capture images always with the same angle of the camera while with conventional ways it is difficult having the same angle for each capture.</p>		
TL-KPI-B-04	Reducing to zero the number of work accidents due to exposure to dangerous environments	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
<p>This KPI is verified indirectly as it is not possible to compare accident rates. Instead, we investigated work accidents as being reduced due to the following factors:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Decreased inspection time by 5 times • Reduced personnel • Reduced road blocking and deviations required <p>Reduced exposure to traffic, truck or supporting vehicles.</p>		
TL-KPI-B-05	Reducing the time and the cost of after inspection reporting / representation of findings/ interpretation of findings by 10 times in comparison with conventional in house or outsourcing consultancy	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
<p>Following the final pilots, the after-inspection time and precision of results have seen significant improvements, thanks to the implementation of fully automated results aggregation, reporting, and formatting. To enhance user experience, tailored user interfaces (IVP) have been developed to present results in a more user-friendly manner, as requested, detailed, and verified by various end-users.</p>		
TL-KPI-B-06	Increasing the completeness, accuracy, objectivity of the structural evaluation of tunnel, in comparison with conventional in house or outsourcing assessment	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No

The after-inspection time and precision of results has been drastically improved following fully automated results aggregation, reporting and formatting. Particular user interfaces (IVP) have been designed to present results in a more user- friendly approaches, as indicated, specified and validated by different end-users. On top, the automation of the methods to obtain high quality images (from the aerial and ground robots) provides greatly increased completeness evaluation of tunnels under inspection.

Table 30. Tunnel local inspection technical KPIs.

ID	KPI	Achieved
TL-KPI-T-01	<p>The aerial robot integrates the following systems:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Autonomous navigation system for GNSS denied environment. • Image stabilization system for the inspection camera. • Mission planner logger 	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
<p>The TTDRONE platform was able to autonomously navigate using only the on-board sensors measurements in the drainage tunnel where GNSS measurements are not available. The visual local inspection results were gathered with a stabilized inspection camera installed at the top of the robot. The execution of inspection plans was monitored in real time and logged from the ground by the gRCS.</p>		
TL-KPI-T-02	<p>The aerial robot is able to obtain adequate enough high-quality images at less than 2 meters distance.</p>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
<p>The TTDRONE platform performed the visual local inspection at 1.3 and at 1.7 meters from the defects to be inspected.</p>		
TL-KPI-T-03	<p>The aerial robot is able to perform advanced inspection operations and revisit previously identified spots.</p>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
<p>The repeatability of the visual local inspection performed by the aerial robot was tested and validated by performing the same inspection plans repeatedly (see Section 4.). The gathered results validate the performance of the developed system.</p>		
TL-KPI-T-04	<p>The system can record the position of tunnel defects (x, y, z) with 10 cm accuracy.</p>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No

<p>A Leica Total Station was used as ground truth to obtain the error of the TTDRONE localization during the execution of the missions. The estimated localization was accurate enough for localizing the defects with 10 cm accuracy in the environment.</p>		
TL-KPI-T-05	<p>The aerial robot has enough flight time to perform the required inspections (at least 15 minutes).</p>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
<p>Yes, the TTDRONE is connected with a tether to the ground robot that provides power through the tether allowing several hours of continuous inspection flight.</p>		
TL-KPI-T-06	<p>The ground robot control station displays live video from the images taken on-board the aerial robot.</p>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
<p>Yes, the aerial robot transmits images from its camera to the ground robot control station.</p>		
TL-KPI-T-07	<p>The robotic ground vehicle will operate fully autonomously.</p>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
<p>The robotic vehicle can navigate and follow a mission plan (including data capturing and precise geo-location) once the mission is triggered. It is assumed that a valid map is already available, through a mapping session where the vehicle is manually operated.</p>		
TL-KPI-T-08	<p>The robotic ground vehicle will measure its position within the tunnel with an accuracy of 10 cm from the tunnel entrance under the following conditions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No GNSS coverage • No fixed lighting or partial lighting 	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
<p>As previously commented (see KPI TG-KPI-T-03), the accuracy is a few decimetres, measured as RMSE.</p>		
TL-KPI-T-09	<p>Within inspected tunnel segments, the robotic ground vehicle will measure the following values to within an accuracy of 10 cm:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tunnel diameter • Segment length • Width of the paved road surface • 3D location of defects 	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No

<p>With the use of the 3D laser scanner, any position inside the tunnel can be measured with an accuracy of 1mm. Also, the aerial and ground robots are able to locate the images within 10 cm accuracy.</p>		
<p>TL-KPI-T-10</p>	<p>The robotic ground vehicle will have the following capabilities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ground clearance of at least 20 cm and suspension system enabling operation on rough surfaces (e.g. asphalt, gravel) • Tolerate up to 15 cm standing water • Tolerate up to 15 deg surface inclination • Max dimensions 3.5 m x 2.5 m x 2 m and max weight 2t to be transportable by truck • Max width 2.5 m to fit within a single road lane • Operational range of at least 10 km or 2 hr • Obstacle avoidance for trespassing vehicles, humans and objects max 20cm height from the ground. • Batteries rechargeable on-site 	<p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No</p>
<p>All of the robot capabilities were tested against rough conditions, especially in accessory drainage tunnel where those were present.</p>		
<p>TL-KPI-T-11</p>	<p>The robotic ground vehicle will operate safely, have will have the following functions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Onboard safety lights and relevant warning placards • Remote emergency shut down • Manual control override 	<p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No</p>
<p>All 3 functionalities were present. Manual override and emergency shut down were also consistently tested by driving the robot in manual mode and triggering the radio e-stop before moving.</p>		
<p>TL-KPI-T-12</p>	<p>The robotic ground vehicle will have continuous wireless communications link with the ground control station such that inspection images and robot pose can be viewed live.</p>	<p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No</p>
<p>Updated performance in last tests demonstrate the KPI is achieved. Difficulties with multiple operators at a time where resolved with reworked networks and addition of PtP omnidirectional antennas. Live data can also be seen now, either within a remote GCS or directly in the onboard tablet that presents this information together with some user-selectable parameters for current mission.</p>		

TL-KPI-T-13	Measurement of tunnel diameter deformation in tunnel slices every 100m, with 1-2m per slice, accuracy 1-2mm.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
With the use of the 3D laser scanner, any position inside the tunnel can be measured with an accuracy of 1mm.		
TL-KPI-T-14	Detailed photographing of the defect or highly deformed areas, by taking photos of high resolution	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
Images obtained with the camera are of a resolution of 9504x6336 px. In addition, the configuration of the specific lens allows to measure with great accuracy defect or highly deformed areas as shown in Section 4.		

In summary, and considering the three scenarios, 96%³ of all KPIs have been already completely fulfilled, 4% partially fulfilled and none have not been fulfilled. With respect to the overall business and technical KPIs the fulfillment distribution is the following:

Table 31. Overall fulfillment percentage per type of KPI.

KPI/Fulfillment	Yes	Partially	No
Business	96%	4%	0%
Technical	97%	3%	0%

With respect to each scenario, the fulfillment percentage of validation KPIs is:

Table 32. Fulfillment percentage of validation KPIs per type of scenario.

Scenario/Fulfillment	Yes	Partially	No
Refinery	98%	2%	0%
Viaduct	94%	6%	0%
Tunnel	95%	5%	0%

As can be seen in Table 32, almost all the KPI's have been validated in each of the scenarios during this last year of the project.

If we analyze the fulfillment percentage of each type of KPI per validation scenario (see deliverable D3.2), the following results are obtained:

³ To facilitate the readiness, no decimals have been used and the percentages have been rounded to the closest whole number.

Table 33. Fulfillment percentage of validation KPIs per type of validation scenario.

Validation scenario	Type of KPI/Fulfillment	Yes	Partially	No
Refinery Large Structure (Tank) Inspection	Business	100%	0%	0%
	Technical	100%	0%	0%
Refinery Pressure Vessel Inspection	Business	100%	0%	0%
	Technical	100%	0%	0%
Refinery Pipe Inspection with Ground Monitoring	Business	100%	0%	0%
	Technical	91%	9%	0%
Viaduct Visual Inspection (including survey target installation)	Business	80%	20%	0%
	Technical	100%	0%	0%
Viaduct Bearing Inspection	Business	86%	14%	0%
	Technical	100%	0%	0%
Viaduct Sensor Installation	Business	100%	0%	0%
	Technical	100%	0%	0%
General Tunnel Inspection	Business	100%	0%	0%
	Technical	89%	11%	0%
Local Tunnel Inspection	Business	100%	0%	0%
	Technical	93%	7%	0%

From these results, it is important to point out that:

- Considering all the use cases, more than 96% of all the KPIs have been fulfilled. So, it can be concluded that after the second and final project experiments, almost all KPIs have been successfully completed.
- No KPI has not been fulfilled, and only 3,5% of KPIs have been partially fulfilled.
- The viaduct visual inspection has the lowest business KPIs fulfillment percentage since it only has 5 KPIs and one of them has not been fully fulfilled (reduce the bill by 25%).
- The general tunnel inspection has the lowest technical KPIs fulfillment percentage (89%) almost the target fulfillment percentage for the KPIs (90%) considering in PILOTING project.

Apart from the KPI, we have also checked the validation of the original project requirements (see deliverable D3.1). The traceability matrices where it is indicated if the requirements have or not been verified during the pilot experiments are included in Annex I: Requirements Validation.

After analyzing the results of the traceability matrices, it is important to point out that:

- Around 94% of the total requirements of the project have been validated during the second pilot experiments. Only 3% of the requirements have been partially validated and 3% not validated.
- The requirements coverage per scenario is the following (not considering requirements classified as COULD):

Table 34. Percentage of requirements verified during second pilot experiments per scenario.

Scenario/Verified	Yes	Partially	No
Refinery	94%	5%	1%

Viaduct	94%	2%	4%
Tunnel	96%	0%	4%

As can be seen, almost all the requirements have been validated in each of the scenarios during this last year of the project.

- Finally, the requirements coverage per use case is the following (not considering requirements classified as COULD):

Table 35. Percentage of requirements verified during second pilot experiments per use case.

Use case/Verified	Yes	Partially	No
Refinery Large Structure (Tank) Inspection	91%	7%	2%
Refinery Pipe Inspection	93%	6%	1%
Refinery Pressure Vessel Inspection	97%	3%	0%
Refinery Ground Monitoring	97%	3%	0%
Viaduct Visual Inspection	96%	1%	3%
Viaduct Bearing Inspection	91%	3%	6%
Viaduct Sensor Installation	92%	3%	5%
General Tunnel Inspection	100%	0%	0%
Local Tunnel Inspection	92%	0%	8%

6. Training and HMI assessment

During this second set of experiments, a number of training sessions have been organized with internal and external end-users.

The following training sessions were completed:

- Internal training sessions with APPLUS personnel in each final pilot experiments
 - Specially focused on the use of IVP and gRCS.
- External training with other end-users in PILOTING workshops (>80 people)
 - Online workshop together Sprint Robotics.
 - Final workshop at Sprint Robotics World Conference. This workshop was focused on showing the complete digital workflow using PILOTING I&M platform and services.

Figure 121. (left) Workshop with live demo during tunnel experiments in Greece. (right) Online workshop to explain in detail PILOTING digital workflow with live execution of the IVP and gRCS.

Apart from these training sessions, during the second pilot experiments, it was performed an assessment of the developed HMIs (IVP and gRCS). The assessment used the NASA TLX questionnaire (see Figure 122).

- IVP interface
 - gRCS interface
- Operator type of user (APPLUS)
 - IVP interface
 - gRCS interface
- Viaduct
 - Engineer type of user (CATEC):
 - IVP interface
 - gRCS interface
 - Operator type of user (APPLUS)
 - IVP interface
 - gRCS interface

The results obtained, after evaluating the two HMIs, are the following:

Table 36. Assessment of IVP HMI using NASA TLX methodology.

	MD	PD	TD	PM	EF	FT
APPLUS-REFIN IVP	2	2	3	8	2	0
CATEC-REFIN IVP	1	1	1	10	2	1
APPLUS-TUNNEL IVP	1	1	1	9	1	0
RBNK-TUNNEL IVP	5	2	2	8	3	3
APPLUS-VIADUCT IVP	1	1	1	10	4	1
CATEC-VIADUCT IVP	1	1	1	9	1	1
	1,83	1,33	1,50	9,00	2,17	1,00

Table 37. Assessment of gRCS HMI using NASA TLX methodology.

	MD	PD	TD	PM	EF	FT
APPLUS-REFIN gRCS	3	3	4	2	6	1
CATEC-REFIN gRCS	2	2	2	9	2	1
APPLUS-TUNNEL gRCS	4	1	1	8	2	0
RBNK-TUNNEL gRCS	7	3	4	8	4	6
APPLUS-VIADUCT gRCS	1	1	1	10	4	2
CATEC-VIADUCT-gRCS	1	1	1	9	1	1
	3,00	1,83	2,17	7,67	3,17	1,83

After analyzing the obtained results, it can be concluded that:

- IVP has obtained better results in terms of requiring less effort and cognitive load.
- The current version of IVP already obtains good results in terms of cognitive load and learning curve thanks to the improvements performed in the last year of the project after the learnings obtained during the first pilot experiments.
- gRCS is a more complex software than IVP, but there is room for improvement to reduce the cognitive load and learning curve.

7. Lessons Learned and Best Practices

This section of the report will outline a series of lessons learned and best practices for the future exploitation of PILOTING technologies.

7.1. Refinery Pilot

7.1.1. End user observations

The refinery environment is a complex industrial location to test robotics. These petrochemical sites are typically high security/restricted access areas with a number of pre-authorizations and permitting required to enable work. Due to the restricted nature of the refinery environment, there was less flexibility in the format of the testing, with strict scheduling and supervision required at all times.

Industry wide there is a core need to develop robotics technologies in large industrial environments such as refineries as a means to eliminate confined space entry work, mundane or routine tasks as well as dangerous elevated work in congested complex process facilities.

The primary driver for implementing robotics from an industry perspective is a safety focus through remote work enablement. A secondary driver is to automate the mundane/routine jobs that are typically carried out daily. The PILOTING project has demonstrated and proven the development and testing of numerous novel solutions addressing all of these needs.

All the PILOTING solutions cover significant areas for future development from an end user perspective.

1. AEROX / HYBRID: Tank/pipe inspection (Reducing working at height or in congested areas)
2. BIKE: Internal vessel inspection (Eliminating confined space entry)
3. UGV / WATCHER: observational data capture & manipulation (Automation and repetition of routine jobs)

PILOTING has also proven that that use of a generic robot control system (gRCS) coupled with automated reporting from an Intelligent Visualization portal (IVP) is a viable alternative to facilitate multiple robot/solution agnostic work scopes supporting facility inspections.

A number of the key ‘lessons learned’ and ‘best practices’ identified from the first round of experiments in 2022 were incorporated into the planning and execution of the 2023 final experiments such as:

- More comprehensive safety inductions for visitors implemented. Better documentation on the H2S gas monitors, 4-gas monitors and evacuation masks were provided up front.
- Improvements to the timetable of experiments to allow more experiments to be conducted in tandem improved scheduling and allowed for redundancy during poor weather conditions.
- Permitting and flight authorizations for aerial experiments were acquired well in advance to the Refinery experiments to streamline this mandatory process.
- Mandatory safety rules must be followed at all times while on site, with daily toolbox talks prior to commencing any work ensuring full attendance and alignment on safety principles.
- Based on lessons learned from initial experiments, a ratio of 1:4 was maintained between Chevron personnel and external visitors which allowed multiple experiments simultaneously with appropriate levels of supervision.
- Engaging a media company removed administration/logistics for EC review purposes as well as promotional material generation for WP10 support.

Moreover, the following learned lessons, and improvements from the first set of experiments have been identified.

7.1.2. Large structure Inspection

Figure 123. New probe-centered crawler design.

Figure 124. New data processing logic.

- New roller assembly (Figure 123): Significant improvements were observed in the crawler's design in its latest iteration. The RMCP no longer employs a rack and pinion mechanism to actuate the probe; instead, it uses a spring-loaded holder that applies the necessary pressure passively. Elimination of moving parts greatly minimizes the potential for jams and tolerances causing issues to the probe's perpendicularity (which till now was a matter of great concern). Centering the roller probe on the crawler's frame notably enhanced perceived force and, consequently, the quality of ultrasonic interfacing. Moreover, it reduced the likelihood of the crawler lifting itself from the surface using the probe's end for support. The coupling interface, previously a dense gel, has been replaced with a smoother oil, proving to be more effective during contact operations.
- Improved data processing (Figure 124): A new approach to the ultrasonic interface has finally demonstrated that measurement repeatability is achievable with the AeroX system. Moving away from the manual 'gate method' for wave peak detection or the use of a weak algorithm to search for local maxima, the new post-processing loop expands on processing options (e.g., extended sample averaging, wave correlation, Hilbert's transform envelope). It employs a

reliable and automatic peak detector that performs a smart scan over the wave, searching for local maxima while considering various user-input parameters. These parameters include, for instance, the minimum and maximum separation between peaks to be expected, the magnitude threshold for peak consideration, among others. Ultimately, this new methodology allows for a configuration similar to that seen with gates, but with significantly reduced user supervision.

- **Susceptibility to weather conditions:** The heavy dependence on wind and rain conditions was keenly felt during the last phase of testing. Despite the platform's considerable resistance to perturbations, the ever-changing environmental conditions still impact inspection operations. However, resolving this issue is no simple task, as it represents a fundamental challenge shared among all aerial robots. Nevertheless, we can confidently state that finding effective ways to deal with this necessity is an enduring goal for us.
- **Autonomy and flight times:** Being closely tied to the previous point, the aircraft's operable flight time is easily compromised in the face of sudden interruptions. AeroX inspection missions, although faster and safer than conventional ones, are still susceptible to delays that, when accumulated, can significantly deplete the available flight time. Assuming the regular occurrence of varying weather conditions, the mission's workflow could cascade into a situation where battery power is almost entirely consumed in attempting to make contact with the surface. Even partially uncharged batteries need recharging, further reducing the available battery sets. Obviously, these issues tend to leave the system with little to no reserves, limiting the window for planned inspections. In a positive light, all highlighted issues are common to all aerial robotic vehicles, indicating that AeroX-specific problems have been noticeably addressed. These aspects will undoubtedly be managed seamlessly by future inspection platforms yet to be tested.

7.1.3. *Vessel Inspection*

- Improvements in the BIKE's surface preparation tool was a huge leap forward for cleaning the vessel and improving the visibility of the operator.
- Major upgraded was deployed with new SLAM for point cloud mesh surface generation using the onboard rotating LIDAR unit. This provided increased reliability and accuracy for the inspection operations.
- Based on learning from the 2022 experiments on lipped flanges, where the BIKE still had to be manually deployed and meant an operator has to 'break confinement', a lipped flange deployment tool was developed. While the new pressure vessel did not require this tool for deployment, this was tested in lab conditions and will be a huge safety enhancement to this solution.
- Several deviations were observed during the experiments and a crucial deviation was successfully incorporated into the 'asset model' solely using the Piloting portal.

7.1.4. *Pipe Inspection*

- As mentioned in Section 2.3, due to the incapability for the previous HYBRID to land safely on pipes, a new HYBRID platform (Figure 15) has been carried out focusing on a different concept of control allowing the aircraft to perform movements in X,Y plane with no need to use roll and/or pitch rotations.
- A more reliable and robust LiDAR based odometry solution has been developed for localization in refinery, as can be seen in Figure 125. Finding it improves significantly the

aircraft performance respect to the previous solution providing a consistent localization used for critical autonomous operations such landing on pipes.

Figure 125. LiDAR based SLAM solution rviz view.

- The pipe detector (Figure 126) now is more robust than before including a 2D LiDAR fused with a depth camera. It also improved the robustness against double detections being able to increase the confidence about detected pipes. It has been found this algorithm can still detects fake pipes in a very concurred space like refineries, where there are a lot of pipes. This didn't suppose an issue for the experiments but something to consider for future improvements.

Figure 126. Pipe detector rviz view.

- The anchorage system has been improved passing from a magnetic system to be a mechanical one using linear actuators with sawtooth grip as can be seen in Figure 127. It was found that this system holds the aerial aircraft strong enough to resist on the pipe even with moderate winds.

Figure 127. Anchorage system of HYBRID.

- Susceptibility to weather conditions: The heavy dependence on wind and rain conditions was keenly felt during the last phase of testing. Due to the force control required for landing, it was found that wind speed over 6m/s makes difficult, risky and/or impossible to perform a safe landing on pipes. This is a physical limit for the aircraft design and can't be changed or modified. To improve this behaviour, a new aircraft must be designed taking into consideration to fly with strong wind.
- Despite the platform's considerable resistance to perturbations, the ever-changing environmental conditions still impact inspection operations. However, resolving this issue is no simple task, as it represents a fundamental challenge shared among all aerial robots. Nevertheless, we can confidently state that finding effective ways to deal with this necessity is an enduring goal for us.
- Testing saw a 100% successful deployment and retrieval rate for both the drone and the satellite UT crawler.
- Ultrasonic thickness measurements were successfully repeated and verified against manual measurements.

7.1.5. Ground Monitoring

- Both ground robots (RB-WATCHER and UGV with manipulator arm) were able to utilize existing point cloud maps and accuracy in inspection accuracy and repeatability between the initial experiments in 2022 and the final experiments in 2023 was excellent.
- Full integration of all systems into the Piloting I&M platform was a significant enhancement from the initial 2022 experiments.
- RB-WATCHER robot inclusion was helpful to understand that, for the ground monitoring and other cases, the value comes from automating tasks but also from the quality of the data. The challenges for ground robots are well identified, coming from a good positioning of quality sensors that can retrieve this data with a robust solution that provides a good repetitiveness.
- With the UGV, high torque manipulation is not physically possible with the current manipulator. However, the system has shown high reliability as the full mission was repeated more than 10+ times without failures nor interventions. The safety of the system was also validated with successful obstacle avoidance, and compliant manipulation where small errors

in valve detection did not cause any damage - The focus of the final experiments for the mobile manipulator is to close the action perception loop. Thus, two functionalities were required: i) the autonomous pressure gauge reading and ii) the valve position estimation. Both of which were achieved successfully.

- Several improvements were implemented to surmount various malfunctions that appeared in the IoT system. Those mainly concern wireless communication, the limited sunlight conditions of the pilot area, and the inability of automated re-operation when the solar power system is fully charged. All of them have been thoroughly described in Section 2.6, and briefly included the adoption of customised solutions, supporting a commercial solution, such as the external 4G modem, the arduino board and the 2nd solar panel. Additionally, integration and data transmission tests were performed before the initiation of both pilot phases.
- Nevertheless, preliminary conclusions would be to additionally develop a second MQTT broker prior to the transmission of the collected observations to the DDHL, acting as a back-up, and thus avoiding any data loss. Additionally, we firmly believe that it would be better to design and fabricate the whole IoT system, including the sensors, and gateway, etc. The specific equipment from the NCD company proved by far inadequate to meet the requirements of this pilot and in general the quality level that was necessary. Any other solutions were exceeding in cost level and couldn't be adopted with the budget that was allocated for this task.

7.2. Viaduct Pilot

Viaducts are found on any road or linear infrastructure where we need to move ourselves or move energy.

In the normal case, viaducts are designed with a lifetime for which they do not need excessive care or maintenance. The weakest and most stressed part may be the pavement in the case of a road or the anchorages in the case of a pipeline, but they are designed to complete their life cycle without the need for maintenance. However, the changes that have taken place over the last 30 years with respect to the use of infrastructures at the limit of their capacities have caused some of them to reach a state of rupture or the limit of their useful life. From this point, the necessity arises to be able to carry out a prior maintenance and condition study that allows us to know if it is necessary to carry out actions or if it is still in its perfect condition.

This is where the use of robotics, artificial intelligence and all the techniques that may arise to support new remote sensor capture systems that allow the normal use of the infrastructure to remain unchanged while data is being collected.

The main motivation for implementing robotics with drones and Artificial Intelligence techniques in industry is safety for people using the infrastructure and for workers. To achieve this, remote working is essential. A secondary factor is the automation of routine jobs that are performed on a daily basis. The Piloting project has demonstrated and tested the development and testing of numerous novel solutions that meet all these needs.

The ability to redo the same operations at the scheduled time serves to improve maintenance conditions and to ensure that no further intermediate operations will be necessary within the scheduled time.

A number of the key ‘lessons learned’ and ‘best practices’ identified from the first round of experiments in 2022 were incorporated into the planning and execution of the 2023 final experiments such as:

- How to Accelerate, Simplify and Optimize all Devices in the operation. Most of navigation and capture sensors have been changed in the way to optimize process.
- Importance of process certification for global markets. We have been working together to the final operator in the same way to obtain certification to the whole results as the actual inspector sings.
The main goal is to use drones, robotics vehicles and AI computing to get the same. Of course, in less time, risk and gain repeatability.

7.2.1. End user observations

Regarding health and safety, we have been able to greatly improve the processes by being located in areas away from traffic. It is only necessary to access the area below the viaduct to be able to carry out all kinds of operations. In our specific case on the "Rio Verde Bridge", we needed the help of the concessionaire to access this unique viaduct, but this will not be necessary on the vast majority of viaducts that have proper access from below.

Another lesson learned is that we can reduce the number of personnel associated with operations. It is also possible that these personnel may be lower skilled than what is currently required for visual inspections, which, coupled with the low cost of drones and sensors, can allow the jobs to be multiplied with the same engineering equipment.

7.2.2. Visual Inspection (including surveying target installation)

Improving organizational processes by optimising flight times and thus improving the quality of the process. The amount of data collected, compared to the previous year, has increased more than 5-fold.

Rio Verde Viaduct itself is a challenge for the system due to the large span sizes between its piers and the height above ground. The system currently checks 85% of the data required for a maintenance check. That remaining 15% can be made up for in subsequent experiments if we can get permission to fly at higher altitudes.

7.2.3. Bearing Inspection

Bearing inspection has improved in terms of observation capabilities. Last year we only had 2 cases in which this inspection could be carried out, and in neither of these two cases was it possible to carry out a 360° inspection. This year we have managed to carry out the general inspection and the detailed inspection of the bearings in the longitudinal direction, reaching the possible interpretation of artificial intelligence. It would be necessary to re-organise the project so that the inspection would cover the 360° but it is simply an organizational part, technically it would be possible to do it with the means we have now.

Target installation was fully achieved last year. New approaches have been tested during this year with similar results.

7.2.4. *Sensor Installation*

Regarding the box installation we have had a year with different strategies. In a first approach last year it was done by crawling along the bottom of the deck. During the middle of this year, this reptation process has been changed into a free flying process which allows access to all types of structures regardless of whether the bottom of the board is horizontal or not.

Finally, the University of Seville has decided to return to the reptation system for the implementation on the Archidona viaduct in which this process is safer if it is done through the movement of the lower part of the deck.

From the end user's point of view both are necessary and probably the applications that we can find are greater considering that both systems have been able to work.

7.3. Tunnel Pilot

7.3.1. *End user observations*

Fundamental requirement to advance robotics technologies for the elimination of traditional inspection and maintenance methods as well as human interference. The main motivator is:

1. To enhance safety by enabling robotics technologies and remote inspection methods
2. Automate and optimize time consuming and rigorous tasks that need to be performed during traditional I&M processes.

Then, PILOTING has proven that:

- ✓ The use of novel technologies developed within the project can optimize and cover the needs for Tunnel I&M.
- ✓ Using a generic robot control system (gRCS) with automated reporting through an Intelligent Visualization portal (IVP) is a viable option for diverse, robot-agnostic facility inspections.
- ✓ We managed reduce the time required for a detailed inspections versus traditional methods while minimizing work accidents and costs.
- ✓ The use of AI-assisted defect detection as well as novel 3D Laser scanning technologies can provide results with greater accuracy and in less time.

Some remarks on the lessons learnt are following, with a common focus on technical aspects that serve for both road tunnel and drainage tunnel.

7.3.2. *General Inspection*

After days of testing, several missions were uploaded successfully, with relevant data for the AI algorithms and ultimately for the end-user on the structural assessment.

Autonomous navigation and localization is working flawlessly. An additional steep slope control makes easier for the robot to keep position or speed in harsh conditions such as the unpaved terrain of drainage tunnels. In both cases there was an additional effort for the robot to be capable of navigating (and capturing) while driving backwards. This was possible with an additional lidar in the rear part of the CART, mainly for obstacle avoidance but also for helping in the wall following algorithm.

It is also worth noting how different knowledge from the previous tests served to improve the system and make it easier to run. A good example is the addition of user-selectable parameters in a new HMI that can be accessed through a remote connection or directly in a side-mounted tablet in the robot cockpit. The same can be used to control the piloting interfaces and the GRCS. With this, the previous work such as the mapping and parametrization for the sensors is easier and takes less time.

This is also affecting on how the robot is operated, since new features of other modules (such as the segment definition within the IVP) are perfectly integrated with the new tools.

This and other improved features allowed us to have data captured for the full tunnel (right side & left side) with an improved speed of process:

- 75 pictures, 40m segment in 7:35.
- 379 pictures, 900m segment in 49 minutes.

Figure 128. Results of general inspection of motorway tunnel visualized in IVP.

The main identified lessons learnt are:

- An agile robotic platform is crucial in order to operate in such environment, specially in tunnels with traffic that need to remain active. The preparations for such robotic vehicle must be minimal and timing of the works and data capturing are really critical.
- Extensive testing of individual modules and the whole pipeline for the localization system is essential to ensure that the software and hardware of the system work as expected. In preparation for the tests in Metsovo during 2023, the localization was tested in controlled environments. This ensured that it would be easier to get the system up and running during the tests, as well as making debugging on-site easier.
- Having backups to different parts of the system is very important. For the 2023 tests in Metsovo, an extra localization payload was brought, as well as different backup versions of the code. This would allow trivial switches in cases where hardware or software didn't behave as expected. During these tests the power adapter used to power the localization system from a power socket broke, however as the localization system was powered by the robot platform, this was not a hinderance to the testing.
- Integration testing between the localization system and the robot platform is very important to ensure that they are cooperating well. These are complex systems, and it is not trivial to synchronize them. Spending time ensuring that they do work together is essential, and the integration tests done before the tests in Metsovo during 2023 were very important in ensuring that the localization worked as consistently and stably as it did.

7.3.3. Local Inspection

The local inspection procedure implies the positioning of the robot by autonomous navigation and then the usage of different means of data capturing: Single point visual inspection, TTDrone or Lidar inspection (FARO Lidar)

When it comes to the robotic vehicle, the main achievements in comparison to previous iterations and taking into account the already described features complementing the general inspection procedures are:

- Successfully tested repetitivity with same mission and POI's
- New type of mission "LIDAR inspection" successfully tested with FARO scanner in several missions.

Figure 129. Creation of inspection plans in tunnel.

8. Conclusions

This is the final technical report for WP8 which summarizes the results of the final large-scale industrial experiments on the PILOTING project. This report highlights the steps taken during the planning of industrial experiments using the PILOTING I&M platform and service, covers the testing and results from the Refinery, Viaduct and Tunnel environments, discusses the evaluation of the Business and Technical KPI's, looks at the validation of the technical requirements of the system involve and concludes with a series of lessons learned and improvements which were taken from the initial 2022 experiments and incorporated into the final experiments, as well as documenting future areas for development beyond the Piloting project.

These final large-scale industrial experiments were recognized a major success within the PILOTING project consortium with a large number of highly relevant technical and operational results. In total more than 14+ weeks of experimental testing (between the first and second set of experiments) was executed in real operational scenarios considering the three PILOTING scenarios. All industrial testing was conducted safety, on-time and per the initial planning expectations/requirements, which is testament to the collaboration of all the partners, developers and end users that make up the consortium.

From the evaluation of the KPI's and the validation traceability of the original project requirements, the following conclusions can be obtained:

- **An important number of the KPI's (96%) and project requirements (94%) were validated in operational scenarios (TRL 7) during this initial phase of experimentation.**
- All of experiments performed **fully integrated with the PILOTING I&M platform** and services - Able to validate a 100% digital workflow for inspection works (including mission planning, execution and analysis).
- **Worldwide achievement** with the autonomous landing of the HYBRID on a pipe at height in the refinery
- **Speed of inspection identified as crucial factor for future success in Viaduct** use cases - additional improvements in AEROCAM and VIAD-DRONE solutions implemented in 2023 to address this from 2022.
- **Large improvement in CART performance** after upgrades navigation module.
- Comprehensive set of feedback, lessons-learned and best practices have been captured from 'End users' and 'Robotic/Service developers' to aid future exploitation of PILOTING technologies.

The project aims to fully disseminate the results of the project to industry and certain parts of the project will continue to be developed beyond the scope of this project with the transition of some technologies to other developers (AeroX to VES Robotics) and Piloting I&M platform to be utilized by the Horizon Europe SIMAR project.

9. Annex I: Requirements Validation

This section discusses the validation of the **requirements** of the robotic vehicles for different inspection use cases in the industrial scenarios. More specifically, we provide a validation check for all the requirements introduced in piloting deliverable D3.1, where these requirements have been divided in categories regarding their nature:

- Non-autonomous functional requirements.
- Autonomous functional requirements.
- System requirements:
 - Physics non-functional requirements.
 - Certification non-functional requirements.
 - Safety non-functional requirements.
- Operational Requirements.
- Autonomous Functional Data Representation requirements.

These requirements were checked about their ‘verification’ status in deliverable D7.4, and here we add a ‘Validation’ column with the outcome from the live industrial tests.

9.1. Refinery Pilot

9.1.1. Tank Inspection

Table 38. Verification of the requirements for the Refinery large structures inspection.

Requirement ID	Req Group	Description	Verified in D7.4	Validation	Validation Explanation (If Partially or No)
RLS-FNA-01	Fun-NA	A gas detection system must be installed on-board the robotic vehicle	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RLS-FNA-02	Fun-NA	Aerial robotic vehicle has to be contact proof (for example mechanical protection around propellers)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RLS-FNA-03	Fun-NA	Perform single point ultrasonic measurement	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	

RLS-FNA-04	Fun-NA	Perform grid-type ultrasonic measurements	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RLS-FNA-05	Fun-NA	Perform scan-type of ultrasonic inspections	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	Only up to B-scans are supported, in which case the Leica-based position estimator is needed
RLS-FNA-06	Fun-NA	The system must be able to reload ultrasonic coupling onsite (if applicable)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RLS-FNA-07	Fun-NA	Be able to perform basic surface preparation operations, such as mechanical cleaning of the surface, particularly on areas of rust scabs, paint coating break down.	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	Implemented in previous versions of the RMCP, although not continued in the latest version due to not required for CHEVRON tanks.
RLS-FNA-08	Fun-NA	The system must perform an ultrasonic inspection for wall thickness from 3mm to 100mm	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RLS-FNA-09	Fun-NA	The system must perform an ultrasonic inspection for wall thickness from <2.5mm to 100mm	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	

RLS-FNA-10	Fun-NA	The UT sensor must be calibrated using an ultrasonic step calibration block	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RLS-FA-01	Fun-A	If gas is detected, the system must communicate the alarm to all the involved people in less than 1s start a getaway operation as fast as possible.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RLS-FA-02	Fun-A	Be able to come back to a previous location where an ultrasonic measurement has been performed, and perform a measurement in the same place (10cm precision)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RLS-FA-03	Fun-A	Be able to come back to a previous location where an ultrasonic measurement has been performed, and perform a measurement in the same place (2,54cm/1inch precision)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RLS-FA-04	Fun-A	Be able to operate under "autopilot" mode where a path, previously planned, is automatically followed	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	The on-board autopilot can follow a planned path, although it is not integrated with the current workflow. A pilot is required for contact and detach operations.
RLS-FA-05	Fun-A	While the aerial robot is in contact with the surface, the aerial platform must generate a perpendicular force to the surface in order to keep the RMCP in contact	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	

RLS-Sys-01	Sys-Phy	The system must be small enough to be transported in a box of maximum 2.2x0.8x0.8 m	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RLS-Sys-02	Sys-Phy	The system should be small enough to be transported by airfreight cargo	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	Theoretically it is possible, but it has not been tested due to the protections needed for the robot to be packed in this way.
RLS-Sys-03	Sys-Phy	Batteries must be protected against impacts	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	Batteries are in a safe location in the last version of the vehicle. Destructive impact has not been tested.
RLS-Sys-04	Sys-Phy	Maximum weight of transporting box 30Kg	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RLS-Sys-05	Sys-Phy	Robotic system MTOW must be less than 25Kg	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RLS-Sys-06	Sys-Phy	Robotic system MTOW should be less than 20Kg	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	

RLS-Sys-07	Sys-Phy	Robotic system MTOW could be less than 15Kg	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	This is a COULD requirement
RLS-Sys-08	Sys-Phy	The capacity of the power system (batteries) must allow the system to have an autonomy of 10 min	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RLS-Sys-09	Sys-Phy	The capacity of the power system (batteries) must allow the system to have an autonomy of 13 min	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RLS-Sys-10	Sys-Phy	The capacity of the power system (batteries) must allow the system to have an autonomy of 16 min	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RLS-Sys-11	Sys-Cer	Flight plan including emergency paths approved before the operation	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RLS-Sys-12	Sys-Cer	The risk assessment must consider safety mitigations plan ahead and approved taking into consideration the possibility of collision with obstacles	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	

RLS-Sys-13	Sys-Cer	The risk assessment must consider safety mitigations plan ahead and approved, taking into consideration the possibility of gas detected (explosion).	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RLS-Sys-14	Sys-Cer	The risk assessment must consider safety mitigations plan ahead and approved taking into consideration the possibility of loss of communication	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RLS-Sys-15	Sys-Cer	Have a detailed plan for obtaining the permit to flight one year in advance of the experiments	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RLS-Sys-16	Sys-Cer	API 579-1/ASME FFS-1-2016 must be followed for fitness-for-service assessment techniques	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RLS-Sys-17	Sys-Cer	For tank inspections, procedures in API 653 must be followed	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RLS-Sys-18	Sys-Safety	Only brushless motors can be used	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially	

			<input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> No	
RLS-Sys-19	Sys-Safety	Gas detection alarm must be clearly communicated to the pilot	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RLS-Sys-20	Sys-Safety	The system must incorporate a clear and fast interface to start the emergency procedure after gas detection	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RLS-Sys-21	Sys-Safety	Robotic vehicle must be collision-proof (for example mechanical protection around propellers)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RLS-Sys-22	Sys-Safety	The system must incorporate a pure manual control mode to allow the pilot to take the control of the aerial robot in any case, moment and situation	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RLS-Op-01	O	Any maintenance must be done within a safe area	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RLS-Op-02	O	The system must be able to change or recharge batteries onsite (in safe areas only)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	

RLS-Op-03	O	The aerial robot must be able to fly under windy conditions	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RLS-Op-04	O	The aerial robot should be able to fly under windy conditions	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RLS-Op-05	O	The aerial robot should be able to fly under windy conditions	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RLS-FADR-01	Fun-A	In single points measurements, it is necessary to log: identification number, and wall thickness value	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RLS-FADR-02	Fun-A	In grid measurements, the system must log: identification number of the area and for each point it must log: the position (relative to the grid) and the wall thickness	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RLS-FADR-03	Fun-A	In scan-type inspections, the system could log: identification number of the area, minimum wall thickness, and an image (using standard colour coding) that contains position (relative to the grid) and thickness for each point	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	This type of data formatting is more relevant in C-scan scenarios, which is not the case for this robot. This is a COULD requirement.

RLS-FADR-04	Fun-A	The system must incorporate similar ultrasonic sensor user interface on the ground as regular ultrasonic sensor systems	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RLS-FADR-05	Fun-A	The system must be able to use a mission plan data embedded from the pre-mission plan	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RLS-FADR-06	Fun-A	The system must be able to save and display in real-time A-SCAN data on the ground	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	

9.1.2. Vessel Inspection

Table 39. Verification of the requirements for the Refinery vessel inspection.

Requirement ID	Req_Group	Description	Verified in D7.4	Validated	Validation Explanation (If Partially or No)
RV-FNA-01	Fun-NA	The system must be able to climb vertical surfaces	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RV-FNA-02	Fun-NA	Be able to perform wall thickness measurements	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RV-FNA-03	Fun-NA	The system must be able to reload ultrasonic coupling onsite (if applicable)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RV-FNA-04	Fun-NA	Robotic system should be able to perform basic surface preparation operations	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	

RV-FNA-05	Fun-NA	Be able to repeat the measurements between large period of times, for example performing the same inspection path than in previous operations within localization systems accuracy	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RV-FNA-06	Fun-NA	Be able to operate under "autopilot" mode where a path, previously planned, is automatically followed	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RV-FA-01	Fun-A	Robotic system must be able to perform single point thickness measurement	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RV-FA-02	Fun-A	Robotic system could be able to perform grid-type thickness measurements	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RV-FA-03	Fun-A	Be able to obtain live video of the inspection site	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	

RV-FA-04	Fun-A	Localization of the sensor in the 3D asset model / environment map must stay within 10 cm of accuracy	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RV-FA-05	Fun-A	Localization of the sensor in the 3D asset model / environment map should stay within 6 cm of accuracy	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RV-FA-06	Fun-A	Localization of the sensor in the 3D asset model / environment map could stay within 3 cm of accuracy	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	Accuracy depends on asset size and mainly model accuracy. This is a COULD requirement.
RV-FA-07	Fun-A	Be able to read-in a 3D model of the PV or provide tools to model a PV from 2D drawings	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RV-Sys-01	Sys-Phy	System small enough to be transported by van or pallet. Each case can be transported on a EUR Pallet (1200x800 mm).	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	

RV-Sys-02	Sys-Phy	System small enough to be transported by airfreight cargo. Each case must not exceed dimensions 224x318 cm. Hazard sources (magnets, batteries, pressure bottles, etc) mitigated to qualify for air transport.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RV-Sys-03	Sys-Phy	The system must be deployable through standard manways, such as flush with cylindrical part on the inside (no lip), of min inner diameter 400 mm	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RV-Sys-04	Sys-Phy	Maximum weight of transporting box 30 kg	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RV-Sys-05	Sys-Phy	Robotic system must be deployable by a human operator.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RV-Sys-06	Sys-Cer	The risk assessment must consider safety mitigations, plan ahead, and take into consideration the possibility of collision with obstacles	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RV-Sys-07	Sys-Cer	The risk assessment must consider system failure or getting stuck. Mitigations must be planned ahead.	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	

RV-Sys-08	Sys-Cer	The risk assessment must take into consideration the possibility of gas being detected (explosion).	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RV-Sys-09	Sys-Cer	The risk assessment must consider the possibility of loss of communication.	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<p>The JSA (Job Site Analysis) covers this and is specific to the deployment situation and asset type.</p> <p>JSA will be updated in collaboration with the site operators.</p>
RV-Sys-10	Sys-Cer	API 579-1/ASME FFS-1-2016 must be followed for fitness-for-service assessment techniques.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<p>The pilot experiments were not completed following these standards – however, the BIKE system is equipped with VT and UT sensors allowing for inspections up to standards. VT: resolution requirements are fulfilled by inspection camera, given the distance to the object is within specs, UT sensor accuracy was verified with test pieces.</p>
RV-Sys-11	Sys-Cer	For vessels inspections, procedures in API 510 must be followed.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<p>The pilot experiments were not completed following these standards – however, the BIKE system is equipped with VT and UT sensors allowing for inspections up to standards. VT: resolution requirements are fulfilled by inspection camera, given the distance to the object is within specs, UT sensor accuracy was verified with test pieces.</p>

RV-Sys-12	Sys-Safety	Gas detection alarm should be clearly communicated to the operator visually or acoustically.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RV-Sys-13	Sys-Safety	The system must incorporate a clear and fast interface to start the emergency procedure after gas detection.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RV-Sys-14	Sys-Safety	System should have a gas detector on-board and in case of gas detection the robot will automatically shut down	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RV-O-01	O	The system must operate on vessels made of ferromagnetic materials	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RV-O-02	O	The system must be able to operate with a non-magnetic layer of 0.2 mm thickness	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	The vessel in the field trial did not have any coating layer. However, adhesion testing in the lab showed that the BIKE wheels will adhere on a 0.2 mm coating layer.
RV-O-03	O	The system must operate on surfaces clean of loose debris and rust	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	

RV-O-04	O	The system must operate on surfaces that are not covered with scale rust layers thicker than 0.2 mm	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RV-O-05	O	The system must operate on an atmosphere free of explosive gas concentrations	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RV-O-06	O	The system must operate in empty and no more than 2 cm of standing fluid	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RV-FADR-01	Fun-A	In single points measurements, it is necessary to log: identification number, position and wall thickness value	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RV-FADR-02	Fun-A	In grid measurements, it is necessary to log: identification number of the area, position of the area, and for each point the position (relative to the grid) and the wall thickness	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RV-FADR-03	Fun-A	Real-time view on thickness signals must allow for analysis and evaluation by certified inspector	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	

RV-FADR-05	Fun-A	Be able to save high quality (HD) images where demanded by the system operator	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RV-FADR-06	Fun-A	Show high resolution (HD) images during inspection	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RV-FADR-07	Fun-A	Show robot and sensor position in 3D model of asset	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	

9.1.3. Pipe Inspection

Table 40. Verification of the requirements for the Refinery pipes inspection.

Requirement ID	Req Group	Description	Verified in D7.4	Validated	Validation Explanation (If Partially or No)
RP-FNA-01	Fun-NA	A gas detection system must be installed on-board the robotic vehicle	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	

RP-FNA-02	Fun-NA	Batteries must be protected against impacts	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	Batteries transported and used to power satellite, UT instrument and communication during onsite test.
RP-FNA-03	Fun-NA	The system must incorporate sensors to determine if the landing area is clear of obstacles or not	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RP-FNA-04	Fun-NA	The satellite installed on the aerial robot must be able to move along the pipe	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RP-FNA-05	Fun-NA	The system must incorporate sensors to allow the pilot or automatically the system to assess the condition of the whole pipe	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RP-FNA-06	Fun-NA	The system will incorporate the sensors to allow the pilot or automatically the system to locate the weld of the pipe	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RP-FNA-07	Fun-NA	The system must perform an ultrasonic inspection for wall thickness from 3mm to 100mm	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	Calibrated on step gauge 2.5 to 25 mm and tested on nominal pipe thickness of 8.25 mm.
RP-FNA-08	Fun-NA	The system must perform an ultrasonic inspection for wall thickness from <2.5mm to 100mm	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially	Calibrated on step gauge 2.5 to 25 mm and tested on nominal pipe thickness of 8.25 mm.

			<input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> No	
RP-FNA-09	Fun-NA	The system could be able to measure height of corrosion deposit or depth (at least with 0.5 mm relative accuracy)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RP-FNA-10	Fun-NA	The system must be able to perform ultrasonic inspection at 3, 6 , 9 and 12 positions in the first, middle and second welds in horizontal elbows	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RP-FNA-11	Fun-NA	The system must be able to perform ultrasonic inspection at 3, 6, 9 and 12 positions in the first, middle and second welds in vertical elbows	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RP-FNA-12	Fun-NA	The system must be able to perform ultrasonic grid inspections on elbows following Chevron inspection procedures	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	Only partial grid scan performed
RP-FNA-13	Fun-NA	The system should be able to perform ultrasonic grid inspections on horizontal T joints (in 1 and 3 areas)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	Only partial grid scan performed on T-Section. No test on reducer.

RP-FNA-14	Fun-NA	The system should be able to perform ultrasonic quadrant inspections on horizontal T joints (in 1 and 3 areas)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	Only partial grid scan performed on T-Section. No test on reducer.
RP-FNA-15	Fun-NA	The system could be able to perform ultrasonic grid inspections on reducers and horizontal T joints (in area 2)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	Only partial grid scan performed on T-Section. No test on reducer.
RP-FNA-16	Fun-NA	The system could be able to perform ultrasonic quadrant inspections on reducers and horizontal T joints (in area 2)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	Only partial quadrant scan performed on T-Section. No test on reducer.
RP-FNA-17	Fun-NA	The system must be able to perform quadrant inspection of a horizontal pipe	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	Only partial quadrant inspection performed on horizontal pipe.
RP-FNA-18	Fun-NA	The system must be able to inspect racks of pipes of 25cm distance between pipes	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RP-FNA-19	Fun-NA	The robotic system should be able to perform A-scan type of inspection in straight pipes and in areas close to welds	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RP-FNA-20	Fun-NA	The system could be able to perform A-scan type of inspections in straight pipes with elbows	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially	

			<input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> No	
RP-FNA-21	Fun-NA	The system must be able to reload ultrasonic coupling onsite (if applicable)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RP-FNA-22	Fun-NA	The system must integrate the necessary sensors to detect any unexpected obstacle	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RP-FA-01	Fun-A	If gas is detected, the aerial robot must start a getaway operation in less than two seconds.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	No flight and associated tests performed
RP-FA-02	Fun-A	The system must incorporate sensors to allow the pilot or automatically the system to assess the condition of the pipe	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RP-FA-03	Fun-A	The system must allow positioning relative to a feature (e.g. weld) with an accuracy of 2 cm at 3, 6, 9 and 12 positions.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RP-FA-04	Fun-A	The system should locate itself, autonomously, with respect to the weld in 3, 6, 9 and 12 positions with less than 2cm of accuracy	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	

RP-FA-05	Fun-A	The system must allow positioning relative to a feature (e.g. weld) with an accuracy of 1 cm at 3, 6, 9 and 12 positions.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RP-FA-06	Fun-A	Be able to operate under "autopilot" mode where a path, previously planned, is automatically followed	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RP-FA-07	Fun-A	In single points measurements, the system must log: identification number, and wall thickness value	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RP-FA-08	Fun-A	In grid measurements, the system must log: identification number of the area and for each point it must log: the position (relative to the grid) and the wall thickness	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RP-FA-09	Fun-A	In A-scan type inspections, the system could log: identification number of the area, minimum wall thickness, and an image (using standard colour coding) that contains position (relative to the grid) and thickness for each point	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RP-FA-10	Fun-A	Real-time HD video or high-quality images of the surroundings	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RP-FA-11	Fun-A	Be able to save HD images under operator demand	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes	

			<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RP-FA-12	Fun-A	The system must incorporate similar ultrasonic sensor user interface on the ground as regular ultrasonic sensor systems	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RP-FA-13	Fun-A	The system must be able to save and display in real-time A-SCAN data on the ground	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RP-FA-14	Fun-A	The system must allow the operator to control the ultrasonic sensor from the ground	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RP-FA-15	Fun-A	While in assisted mode, the aerial platform must detect any obstacle and avoid them	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RP-Sys-01	Sys-Phy	The system must be small enough to be transported in a box of maximum 1.2x1x0.5 m	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	

RP-Sys-02	Sys-Phy	System could be small enough to be transported by helicopter	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RP-Sys-03	Sys-Phy	The system must be small enough to be transported by airfreight cargo	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RP-Sys-04	Sys-Phy	Maximum weight of transporting box 30 kg	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RP-Sys-05	Sys-Phy	Robotic system MTOW must be less than 15 kg	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RP-Sys-06	Sys-Phy	Robotic system MTOW should be less than 12 kg	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	No
RP-Sys-07	Sys-Phy	Robotic system MTOW could be less than 8 kg	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	No. This is a COULD requirement.

RP-Sys-08	Sys-Cer	Flight plan including emergency paths must be approved before the operation	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RP-Sys-09	Sys-Cer	The risk assessment must consider safety mitigations plan ahead and approved taking into consideration the possibility of loss of communication	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RP-Sys-10	Sys-Cer	The risk assessment must consider safety mitigations plan ahead and approved taking into consideration the possibility of collision with obstacles	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RP-Sys-11	Sys-Cer	The risk assessment must consider safety mitigations plan ahead and approved taking into consideration the possibility of the drop of the robotic vehicle while flying	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RP-Sys-12	Sys-Cer	The risk assessment must consider safety mitigations plan ahead and approved taking into consideration the possibility of gas detected (explosion).	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RP-Sys-13	Sys-Cer	In ATEX areas it is needed to follow standard procedures	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	

RP-Sys-14	Sys-Cer	The system should be designed taking into consideration major restrictions to be able to extend its capabilities to operate in ATEX zone 1 areas in the future	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RP-Sys-15	Sys-Cer	The operator must have a detailed plan for obtaining the permit to flight one year in advance of the experiments	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RP-Sys-16	Sys-Cer	API 579-1/ASME FFS-1-2016 must be followed for fitness-for-service assessment techniques	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RP-Sys-17	Sys-Cer	For piping inspections, procedures in API 570 must be followed	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RP-Sys-18	Sys-Safety	Only brushless motors must be used	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RP-Sys-19	Sys-Safety	Robotic vehicle must be collision-proof (for example mechanical protection around propellers)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	

RP-Sys-20	Sys-Safety	The flight envelope and clearance requirements around the aerial vehicle must be provided for flying and landing	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RP-Sys-21	Sys-Safety	Gas detection alarm must be clearly communicated to the pilot	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RP-Sys-22	Sys-Safety	The system must incorporate a clear and fast interface to start the emergency procedure after gas detection	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RP-O-01	O	Recharging and maintenance must be done within a safe area	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RP-O-02	O	The combination of both robotic systems must be able to operate in pipes from 8 to 20 inches of diameter	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RP-O-03	O	The combination of both robotic systems must be able to operate in 6 inches diameter pipes	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	Landing tested on 10 inch pipe. Satellite tested on 8 inches and above.
RP-O-04	O	The combination of both robotic systems must be able to operate in pipes from 20 to 24 inches of diameter	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially	

			<input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> No	
RP-O-05	O	The Aerial Robot must be able to land by means of a magnetic landing platform	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RP-O-06	O	The system must operate only on non-insulated pipes	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RP-O-07	O	The system magnets must operate on a surface with a non-magnetic layer of 1mm or less	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RP-O-08	O	The system magnetics should operate with a non-magnetic layer of 2mm or less	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	N/A

RP-O-09	O	The system magnetics could operate with a non-magnetic layer of 3mm or less	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	N/A
RP-O-10	O	The robotic system should be able to cross 5 mm high welds	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RP-O-11	O	The robotic system should be able to cross horizontal elbows of OD>12"	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RP-O-12	O	The system should be able to operate on surfaces at 60°C	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RP-O-13	O	The system could be able to operate on surfaces at 100°C	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	Not tested. Component selection may allow up to 80°C surface temperature. This is a COULD requirement.
RP-O-14	O	The system must be able to change or recharge batteries onsite (in safe areas only)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	

RP-O-15	O	The operator must be able to perform critical repairs and maintenance onsite (in safe areas only)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RP-FADR-01	Fun-A	In single points measurements, the system must log: identification number, and wall thickness value	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RP-FADR-02	Fun-A	In grid measurements, the system must log: identification number of the area and for each point it must log: the position (relative to the grid) and the wall thickness	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	Grid measurement data gathering and upload through DDHL analogous to refinery vessel inspection. But only tested with BIKE robot.
RP-FADR-03	Fun-A	In A-scan type inspections, the system could log: identification number of the area, minimum wall thickness, and an image (using standard colour coding) that contains position (relative to the grid) and thickness for each point	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RP-FADR-04	Fun-A	Real-time HD video or high-quality images of the surroundings	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RP-FADR-05	Fun-A	Be able to save HD images under operator demand	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	Standard quality images are only possible in this version.

RP-FADR-06	Fun-A	The system must incorporate similar ultrasonic sensor user interface on the ground as regular ultrasonic sensor systems	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RP-FADR-07	Fun-A	The system must be able to save and display in real-time A-SCAN data on the ground	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RP-FADR-08	Fun-A	The system must allow the operator to control the ultrasonic sensor from the ground	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	

9.1.4. Ground Monitoring

Table 41. Verification of the requirements for the refinery ground monitoring.

Requirement ID	Req Group	Description	Verified in D7.4 (ETH)	Verified in D7.4 (ROB)	Validation	Validation Explanation (If Partially or No)
RGM-FNA-01	Fun-NA	A gas detection system must be installed on-board the robotic vehicle	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	

RGM-FNA-02	Fun-NA	System must be able to overcome small obstacles/debris	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RGM-FNA-03	Fun-NA	The system should be able to operate small low torque types of valves	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RGM-FNA-04	Fun-NA	The system could be able to operate large high torque types of valves	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	This is a COULD requirement
RGM-FNA-05	Fun-NA	Be able to teleoperate the robot from a remote location	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RGM-FNA-06	Fun-NA	Be able to place static sensor in specific places	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RGM-FNA-07	Fun-NA	Be able to create a 3D map of the environment	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	

RGM-FNA-08	Fun-NA	The system should need no major preparation from deployment to work	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RGM-FA-01	Fun-A	The system should be able to come back autonomously to the recharge station and recharge itself	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RGM-FA-02	Fun-A	The system should be able to operate using waypoint-type of navigation	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RGM-FA-03	Fun-A	The system should be able to autonomously navigate in a refinery area	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	

RGM-FA-04	Fun-A	The system should be able to detect obstacles and avoid them, while reaching the goal location	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	Containment areas can be seen as obstacles as well
RGM-FA-05	Fun-A	Be able to automatically read gauges and determine if reading is correct	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RGM-FA-06	Fun-A	Be able to automatically estimate the position of a valve and determine if valve position is correct	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	Sending of relative target position commands compared to current position is possible.
RGM-Sys-01	Sys-Phy	System size fits an europallet	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RGM-Sys-02	Sys-Phy	System weight below airfreight cargo max weight	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	

RGM-Sys-03	Sys-Phy	System is weatherproof	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RGM-Sys-04	Sys-Phy	System runs on electric power sources	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RGM-Sys-05	Sys-Cer	The risk assessment must consider safety mitigations plan ahead and approved taking into consideration the possibility of collision with obstacles	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RGM-Sys-06	Sys-Cer	The risk assessment must consider safety mitigations plan ahead and approved taking into consideration the possibility of gas detected (explosion).	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	Gas detector onboard. Actions to be taken in case of alarm to be implemented

RGM-Sys-07	Sys-Cer	The risk assessment must consider safety mitigations plan ahead and approved taking into consideration the possibility of loss of communication	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RGM-Sys-08	Sys-Cer	The inspection program must follow API RP 580	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RGM-Sys-09	Sys-Cer	The procedures and methodology of Risk-Based Inspections must follow API RP 581	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RGM-Sys-10	Sys-Safety	Emergency stop button on robotic vehicle	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RGM-Sys-11	Sys-Safety	System power source can be immediately removed in case of emergency	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially	

			<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> No	
RGM-Sys-12	Sys-Safety	Robot vehicle speed is limited while moving autonomously	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RGM-O-01	O	Recharging need to be done within a safe area	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RGM-O-02	O	Critical maintenance operations need to be performed onsite.	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RGM-O-03	O	The system should be able to climb stairs with 45° stair angle or less	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	Test avoided due to visible risk of flipping over. Robot stability to be revised in such steep conditions
RGM-O-04	O	The system must be able to operate on grating floors	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	

RGM-O-05	O	The system must be able to operate on gravel areas	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RGM-FADR-01	Fun-A	HD video in real-time	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RGM-FADR-02	Fun-A	Thermographic video in real-time	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RGM-FADR-03	Fun-A	Be able to log HD images under operator demand	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RGM-FADR-04	Fun-A	Be able to log thermographic images under operator demand	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	

RGM-FADR-06	Fun-A	Be able to log surround noises and transmit them to the system operator	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	Audio is logged. Transmission to be implemented
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9.2. Viaduct Pilot

9.2.1. Visual Inspection (including surveying target installation)

Table 42. Verification of the requirements for the viaduct visual inspection.

Requirement ID	Req Group	Description	Verified in D7.4	Validation	Validation Explanation (If Partially or No)
VVI-FNA-01	Fun-NA	The UAV must be able to take pictures of the whole viaduct with enough resolution to detect any defect	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VVI-FNA-02	Fun-NA	The UAV must be able to take detailed pictures of the previously detected defects, marked with a radiometric target.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	

VVI-FNA-03	Fun-NA	Be able to acquire high-resolution visual images	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VVI-FNA-04	Fun-NA	The imagen must have enough overlap between them, so that the defect is completely located	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VVI-FNA-07	Fun-NA	The UAV must not overfly people or properties without a previous warning	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VVI-FA-01	Fun-A	Be able to localize images with cm precision with respect to infrastructure	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VVI-FA-02	Fun-A	Be able to operate under "autopilot" mode where a path, previously planned, is automatically followed	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VVI-FA-03	Fun-A	Be able to detect obstacles closer than 10 meters	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VVI-FA-04	Fun-A	Be able to detect obstacles closer than 15meters	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially	

			<input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> No	
VVI-FA-05	Fun-A	The aerial robot is able to stop its movement and maintain the distance without moving when it detects that it is too close to an obstacle	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VVI-FA-06	Fun-A	The system must take pictures in a way that it minimizes the deformation of the surface	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VVI-FA-07	Fun-A	The system must be able to fly and localize itself underneath the viaduct	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VVI-FA-08	Fun-A	The aerial robot must take off and land autonomously. Always with the pilot supervision and controlling the compliance of the security requirements	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VVI-Sys-01	Sys-Phy	The aerial platform must be small enough to be transported in a box of 65x85x80 cm plus a dedicated box for the vision system (camera + stabilizer)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VVI-Sys-02	Sys-Phy	System small enough to be transported by airfreight cargo	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	

VVI-Sys-03	Sys-Phy	The aerial robot must have a diameter lower than 2m	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VVI-Sys-04	Sys-Phy	The aerial robot should have a diameter lower than 1m	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	The main dimension is slightly larger than 1 meter
VVI-Sys-05	Sys-Phy	The capacity of the power system (batteries) must allow the system to have an autonomy of 10 min	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VVI-Sys-06	Sys-Phy	The capacity of the power system (batteries) must allow the system to have an autonomy of 15 min	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	It depends on weather conditions and battery cycles.
VVI-Sys-07	Sys-Phy	The capacity of the power system (batteries) must allow the system to have an autonomy of 20 min	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	Not possible with the current robot. This is a COULD requirement.
VVI-Sys-08	Sys-Phy	Robotic system MTOW must be less than 25Kg	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	

VVI-Sys-09	Sys-Phy	Robotic system MTOW should be less than 20Kg	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	If the parts are separated in different boxes.
VVI-Sys-10	Sys-Phy	Robotic system MTOW could be less than 15Kg	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	If the parts are separated in different boxes. This is a COULD requirement.
VVI-Sys-11	Sys-Cer	Have a detail plan for obtaining the permit to fly one year in advance of the experiments	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VVI-Sys-12	Sys-Cer	The risk assessment must consider safety mitigations plan ahead and approved taking into consideration the possibility of loss of communication	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VVI-Sys-13	Sys-Cer	The risk assessment must consider safety mitigations plan ahead and approved taking into consideration the possibility of collision with obstacles	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VVI-Sys-14	Sys-Cer	The risk assessment must consider safety mitigations plan ahead and approved taking into consideration the possibility of the drop of the robotic vehicle while flying	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VVI-Sys-15	Sys-Cer	The operation is under supervision of the health and safety committee and all the entities involved	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially	

			<input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> No	
VVI-Sys-16	Sys-Cer	The conditions of the data acquisition should be contained in a report (flight parameters, meteorological conditions, incidences, environmental conditions)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VVI-Sys-17	Sys-safety	The system must incorporate a pure manual control mode to allow the pilot to take the control of the aerial robot in any case, moment and situation	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VVI-Sys-18	Sys-safety	Robotic vehicle must be collision-proof (for example mechanical protection around propellers)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VVI-Sys-19	Sys-safety	The pilot interface must show the needed information to have a simple, fast and clear situation awareness to decide on the safety of the operation at any time.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VVI-Sys-20	Sys-safety	The UAV allows that the data acquired are controlled by another external system, besides the pilot	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VVI-OP-01	O	Be able to work at night with artificial lighting	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes	

			<input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VVI-OP-02	O	Be able to work at night without artificial lighting	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	Flashing system could be integrated in the camera, but it is not available in this version. This is a COULD requirement.
VVI-OP-03	O	Be able to operate the aerial robot without having a direct visual line of sight between the operator and the aerial robot.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VVI-OP-04	O	The aerial robot must be able to fly under windy conditions (3m/s)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VVI-OP-05	O	The aerial robot should be able to fly under windy conditions (5m/s)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VVI-OP-06	O	The aerial robot should be able to fly under windy conditions (8m/s)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	Safety distance to the structure should be bigger.
VVI-FADR-01	Fun-ADR	Be able to see live video with the images that the aerial robot is taking	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	

VVI-FADR-02	Fun-ADR	Be able to have a 3D representation of the viaduct and represent the area that have been covered by the pictures taken during the flight	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VVI-FADR-03	Fun-ADR	Be able to log HD images under operator demand	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	

Table 43. Verification of the requirements for the viaduct surveying targets installation.

Requirement ID	Req Group	Description	Verified in D7.4	Validation	Validation Explanation (If Partially or No)
VST -FNA-01	Fun-NA	The passive device, e.g. a surveying target, should be used for geometric and survey monitoring of the viaduct using a total station	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VST -FNA-02	Fun-NA	Aerial robotic vehicle has to be contact proof (for example mechanical protection around propellers)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	

VST -FNA-03	Fun-NA	Batteries must be protected against impacts	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VST -FNA-04	Fun-NA	The system must incorporate sensors to determine if the landing area is clear of obstacles or not	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VST -FNA-05	Fun-NA	The system must integrate the necessary sensors to detect any unexpected obstacle	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VST -FNA-06	Fun-NA	The robot should be able to adapt to piles with variable geometry	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VST -FNA-07	Fun-NA	The UAV must have the manipulation capabilities to install the device on the pillar, so that neither the survey targets nor the structure are damaged	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VST -FA-01	Fun-A	Be able to stick passive survey targets on the pillar	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially	

			<input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> No	
VST -FA-02	Fun-A	Be able to operate under "autopilot" mode where a path, previously planned, is automatically followed	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VST -FA-03	Fun-A	Be able to come back to a previous location where a survey target was sticked, and stick a new survey target (10cm precision)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	The robot is able to revisit some installation locations but the quantitative precision of the installations has not been measured yet.
VST -FA-04	Fun-A	The system must be able to fly and localize itself underneath the viaduct	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VST -FA-05	Fun-A	The aerial robot must take off and land autonomously	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	Not implemented yet. The aerial robot navigates autonomously once it has taken-off. The landing is also performed in manual mode.

VST -FA-06	Fun-A	The aerial robot is able to stop its movement and maintain the distance without moving when it detects that it is too close to an obstacle	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VST -Sys-01	Sys-Phy	System small enough to be transported in a box of 65x85x80 cm plus a dedicated box for the vision system (camera + stabilizer)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VST -Sys-02	Sys-Phy	System small enough to be transported by airfreight cargo	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VST -Sys-03	Sys-Phy	The aerial robot should have a diameter lower than 2m	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VST -Sys-04	Sys-Phy	The aerial robot should have a diameter lower than 1m	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	

VST -Sys-05	Sys-Cer	The operator must have a detailed plan for obtaining the permit to flight one year in advance of the experiments	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VST -Sys-06	Sys-Cer	The risk assessment must consider safety mitigations plan ahead and approved taking into consideration the possibility of collision with obstacles	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	
VST -Sys-07	Sys-Cer	The risk assessment must consider safety mitigations plan ahead and approved taking into consideration the possibility of loss of communication	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VST -Sys-08	Sys-Safety	The system must incorporate a pure manual control mode to allowed the pilot to take the control of the aerial robot in any case, moment and situation	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	

VST -Sys-09	Sys-Safety	Robotic vehicle must be collision-proof (for example mechanical protection around propellers)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VST -Sys-10	Sys-Safety	The pilot interface must show the needed information to have a simple, fast and clear situation awareness to decide on the safety of the operation at any time	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VST -Sys-11	Sys-Safety	The operation is under supervision by the health and safety committee and all the entities involved	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VST -Sys-12	Sys-Safety	The UAV must not overfly people or properties without a previous warning	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	

VST -Sys-13	Sys-Safety	The conditions of the data acquisition should be contained in a report (flight parameters, meteorological conditions, incidences, environmental conditions)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VST -O-01	O	Be able to work at night	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	The robot localization and thus, the navigation in the environment, would be less accurate. Future work is to incorporate a lighting system to the UAV. It is a COULD requirement.
VST -O-02	O	The aerial robot must be able to fly under windy conditions	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VST -O-03	O	The aerial robot should be able to fly under windy conditions	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VST -O-04	O	The aerial robot should be able to fly under windy conditions	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	

VST -O-05	O	The system must be able to change or recharge batteries onsite (in safe areas only)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VST -FADR-01	Fun-A	Be able to see live video from an on-board camera	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VST -FADR-02	Fun-A	Be able to see live video of the exact point of contact	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VST -FADR-03	Fun-A	Be able to see a 3D representation of the viaduct and a representation where the aerial robot is with respect to the 3D model of the viaduct	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VST -FADR-04	Fun-A	The operator on ground must be able to monitor the state of the aerial robot	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	

9.2.2. Bearing Inspection

Table 44. Verification of the requirements for the viaduct bearing inspection.

Requirement ID	Req Group	Description	Verified in D7.4	Validated	Validation Explanation (If Partially or No)
VBI-FNA-01	Fun-NA	Camera with enough resolution to allow reading the metric system on the bearing	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VBI-FNA-02	Fun-NA	Aerial robotic vehicle has to be contact proof (for example mechanical protection around propellers)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VBI-FNA-03	Fun-NA	Batteries must be protected against impacts	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VBI-FNA-04	Fun-NA	The system must incorporate sensors to determine if the landing area is clear of obstacles or not	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	

VBI-FNA-05	Fun-NA	The system must integrate the necessary sensors to detect any unexpected obstacle	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VBI-FNA-06	Fun-NA	The UAV must be able to take detailed pictures of the previously detected defects	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VBI-FNA-07	Fun-NA	The UAV must be able to flight near enough to the bearings	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VBI-FNA-08	Fun-NA	The imagen must have enough overlap between them, so that the defect is completely located	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VBI-FA-01	Fun-A	Be able to take pictures of the external sides of each bearing while flying.	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VBI-FA-02	Fun-A	Be able to take pictures of internal sides (those in the longitudinal axis of the viaduct) of each bearing	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	Only frontal side of the bearings have been captured.

VBI-FA-03	Fun-A	Be able to operate under "autopilot" mode where a path, previously planned, is automatically followed	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VBI-FA-04	Fun-A	The system must be able to fly and localize itself underneath the viaduct	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VBI-FA-05	Fun-A	The aerial robot must take off and land autonomously	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	Not implemented yet. The aerial robot navigates autonomously once it has taken-off. The landing is performed in manual mode.
VBI-Sys-01	Sys-Phy	System small enough to be transported in a box of 65x85x80 cm plus a dedicated box for the vision system (camera + stabilizer)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VBI-Sys-02	Sys-Phy	System small enough to be transported by airfreight cargo	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VBI-Sys-03	Sys-Phy	The aerial robot should have a diameter lower than 2m	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	

VBI-Sys-04	Sys-Phy	The aerial robot should have a diameter lower than 1m	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VBI-Sys-05	Sys-Cer	Have a detailed plan for obtaining the permit to flight one year in advance of the experiments	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VBI-Sys-06	Sys-Cer	The risk assessment must consider safety mitigations plan ahead and approved taking into consideration the possibility of collision with obstacles	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VBI-Sys-07	Sys-Cer	The risk assessment must consider safety mitigations plan ahead and approved taking into consideration the possibility of loss of communication	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VBI-Sys-08	Sys-Safety	The system must incorporate a pure manual control mode to allow the pilot to take the control of the aerial robot in any case, moment and situation	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VBI-Sys-09	Sys-Safety	Robotic vehicle must be collision-proof (for example mechanical protection around propellers)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	

VBI-Sys-10	Sys-Safety	The pilot interface must show the needed information to have a simple, fast and clear situation awareness to decide on the safety of the operation at any time	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VBI-Sys-11	Sys-Safety	The operation is under supervision by the health and safety committee and all the entities involved	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VBI-Sys-12	Sys-Safety	The UAV must not overfly people or properties without a previous warning	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VBI-Sys-13	Sys-Safety	The conditions of the data acquisition should be contained in a report (flight parameters, meteorological conditions, incidences, environmental conditions)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VBI-O-01	O	Be able to work at night	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	The robot localization and thus, its navigation, would be less accurate. Flashing could be activated in the inspection camera. This is a COULD requirement.
VBI-O-02	O	The aerial robot must be able to fly under windy conditions	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	

VBI-O-03	O	The aerial robot should be able to fly under windy conditions	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VBI-O-04	O	The aerial robot should be able to fly under windy conditions	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VBI-O-05	O	The system must be able to change or recharge batteries onsite (in safe areas only)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VBI-FADR-01	Fun-A	Be able to see live video from an on-board camera	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VBI-FADR-02	Fun-A	Be able to see live video of the exact point of contact	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	The camera sensor points downwards, so the exact point of contact (at the viaduct's deck) is not perceived.
VBI-FADR-03	Fun-A	Be able to see a 3D representation of the viaduct and a representation where the aerial robot is with respect to the 3D model of the viaduct	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VBI-FADR-04	Fun-A	Be able to visualize in real-time the data related to the total station	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes	

			<input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
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9.2.3. Sensor Installation

Table 45. Verification of the requirements for the viaduct sensors installation.

Requirement ID	Req Group	Description	Verified in D7.4	Validation	Validation Explanation (If Partially or No)
VSI -FNA-01	Fun-NA	The box of sensors has to be dropped from the aerial robot at a sufficient distance to the pillar surface that avoids any damage to it	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VSI -FNA-02	Fun-NA	Aerial robotic vehicle has to be contact proof (for example mechanical protection around propellers)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	

VSI -FNA-03	Fun-NA	Batteries must be protected against impacts	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VSI -FNA-04	Fun-NA	The system must incorporate sensors to determine if the landing area is clear of obstacles or not	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VSI -FNA-05	Fun-NA	The system must integrate the necessary sensors to detect any unexpected obstacle	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VSI -FNA-06	Fun-NA	The UAV must have horizontal stability during the flight so that the box sensor doesn't break	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VSI -FNA-07	Fun-NA	The UAV must have the manipulation capabilities to install the device on top of the pillar, so that neither the box sensor nor the structure are damaged	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	

VSI -FNA-08	Fun-NA	The UAV must be able to carry the sensor box	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VSI -FNA-09	Fun-NA	The robot should be able to adapt to piles with variable geometry	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	The actual design of the UAV is prepared for the shape of the pilot viaduct. Next step is to design a system capable to adapt to different shapes.
VSI -FNA-11	Fun-NA	The UAV must not disturb the box sensor once it is placed	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VSI -FA-01	Fun-A	Be able to place and position a box with sensors at the top of the pillar (in the empty space next to the bearings)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VSI -FA-02	Fun-A	Be able to remove the sensor box installed at the top of the pillar	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	

VSI -FA-03	Fun-A	Be able to operate under "autopilot" mode where a path, previously planned, is automatically followed	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VSI -FA-04	Fun-A	The system must be able to fly and localize itself underneath the viaduct	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VSI -FA-05	Fun-A	The aerial robot must take off and land autonomously	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	Not implemented yet. The aerial robot navigates autonomously once it has been taken off. The landing is also performed in manual mode.
VSI -FA-05	Fun-A	The aerial robot is able to stop its movement and maintain the distance without moving when it detects that it is too close to an obstacle	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VSI -Sys-01	Sys-Phy	System small enough to be transported in a box of 65x85x80 cm plus a dedicated box for the vision system (camera + stabilizer)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	

VSI -Sys-02	Sys-Phy	System small enough to be transported by airfreight cargo	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VSI -Sys-03	Sys-Phy	The aerial robot should have a diameter lower than 2m	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VSI -Sys-04	Sys-Phy	The aerial robot should have a diameter lower than 1m	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VSI -Sys-05	Sys-Cer	The operator must have a detailed plan for obtaining the permit to flight one year in advance of the experiments	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VSI -Sys-06	Sys-Cer	The risk assessment must consider safety mitigations plan ahead and approved taking into consideration the possibility of collision with obstacles	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	

VSI -Sys-07	Sys-Cer	The risk assessment must consider safety mitigations plan ahead and approved taking into consideration the possibility of loss of communication	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VSI -Sys-08	Sys-Safety	The system must incorporate a pure manual control mode to allowed the pilot to take the control of the aerial robot in any case, moment and situation	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VSI -Sys-09	Sys-Safety	Robotic vehicle must be collision-proof (for example mechanical protection around propellers)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VSI -Sys-10	Sys-Safety	The pilot interface must show the needed information to have a simple, fast and clear situation awareness to decide on the safety of the operation at any time	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	

VSI -Sys-11	Sys-Safety	The operation is under supervision by the health and safety committee and all the entities involved	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VSI -Sys-12	Sys-Safety	The UAV must not overfly people or properties without a previous warning	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VSI -Sys-13	Sys-Safety	The conditions of the data acquisition should be contained in a report (flight parameters, meteorological conditions, incidences, environmental conditions)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VSI -O-01	O	Be able to work at night	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	The robot localization and thus, its navigation, would less accurate. This is a COULD requirement.
VSI -O-02	O	The aerial robot must be able to fly under windy conditions	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	

VSI -O-03	O	The aerial robot should be able to fly under windy conditions	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VSI -O-04	O	The aerial robot should be able to fly under windy conditions	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VSI -O-05	O	The system must be able to change or recharge batteries onsite (in safe areas only)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VSI -FADR-01	Fun-A	Be able to see live video from an on-board camera	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VSI -FADR-02	Fun-A	Be able to see live video of the exact point of contact	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	The camera points downwards, so the exact point of contact (at the viaduct's deck) cannot be perceived.
VSI -FADR-03	Fun-A	Be able to see a 3D representation of the viaduct and a representation where the aerial robot is with respect to the 3D model of the viaduct	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VSI -FADR-04	Fun-A	The operator on ground must be able to monitor the state of the aerial robot	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially	

			<input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> No	
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9.3. Tunnel Pilot

9.3.1. General Inspection

Table 46. Verification of the requirements for the tunnel general inspection.

Requirement ID	Req Group	Description	Verified in D7.4	Validation	Explanation (If Partially or No)
TG-FNA-01	Fun-NA	The robotic vehicle shall be able to operate on rough surfaces (unpaved, small obstacles, debris, etc)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
TG-FNA-02	Fun-NA	The robotic vehicle shall be able to operate in areas partially submerged by water.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
TG-FNA-03	Fun-NA	The robotic vehicle shall be able to operate on inclined slopes.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	

TG-FNA-04	Fun-NA	Robot vehicle to keep speed within appropriate range	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
TG-FNA-05	Fun-NA	Robot vehicle to steer precisely	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
TG-FNA-06	Fun-NA	The system shall enable continuous wireless communication between the robotic vehicle and remote-control interface.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
TG-FNA-07	Fun-NA	Represent the visual images obtained by the robotic vehicle in a user interface	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
TG-FNA-08	Fun-NA	Robotic vehicle position tracking at control station	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
TG-FNA-09	Fun-NA	The system shall be able to create a 3D map of the environment.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	

TG-FA-01	Fun-A	The system shall be able to autonomously navigate to specified waypoints.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
TG-FA-02	Fun-A	The system shall be able to operate autonomously in GNSS-denied environments.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
TG-FA-03	Fun-A	The system shall be able to autonomously avoid collisions with obstacles.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
TG-FA-04	Fun-A	The system shall be able to autonomously capture inspection data with complete coverage of the desired inspection area.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
TG-FA-05	Fun-A	The system shall be able to automatically detect defects such as cracks, spalling, corrosion stains, exposed bars, damped areas and calcium.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
TG-FA-06	Fun-A	The system shall be able to automatically localise detected defects within the tunnel.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	

TG-FA-07	Fun-A	The system should need no major preparation from deployment to work	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
TG-FA-08	Fun-A	The system should need no major preparation from deployment to work	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
TG-FA-09	Fun-A	The system should need no major preparation from deployment to work	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
TG-Sys-01	Sys-Phy	Robotic vehicle size and weight to be transported by truck	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
TG-Sys-02	Sys-Phy	Robotic vehicle size to be used on a single lane	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
TG-Sys-03	Sys-Phy	Robot vehicle size to fit small drainage tunnel	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	

TG-Sys-04	Sys-Phy	Robot runs on electric power	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
TG-Sys-05	Sys-Cer	A risk assessment must be carried out and a hazard mitigation plan must be developed in preparation for on-site testing.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
TG-Sys-06	Sys-Cer	The risk assessment and hazard mitigation plan must at least include hazards due to technology failures, environmental factors, and operator error.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
TG-Sys-07	Sys-Cer	Field testing must be carried out in accordance with the risk assessment and hazard mitigation plan.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
TG-Sys-08	Sys-Safety	The system shall be equipped with an emergency shutdown button for the robotic vehicle.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
TG-Sys-09	Sys-Safety	Appropriate safety lighting and signage shall be used to ensure safe operation of the autonomous system.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	

TG-Sys-10	Sys-Safety	When operating autonomously, the robotic platform shall have a movement speed in accordance with limits identified in risk assessment and hazard mitigation plan.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
TG-O-01	O	Robotic vehicle able to recharge batteries onsite	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
TG-O-02	O	Robotic vehicle able to inspect large parts of highway network	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
TG-O-03	O	Robotic vehicle able to inspect large parts of highway network	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
TG-O-04	O	Robotic vehicle able to inspect large parts of highway network	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	This is a COULD requirement.
TG-O-05	O	Inspection able to be performed during night hours	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	

TG-O-06	O	Inspection able to be performed with one lane open to traffic	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
TG-FADR-01	Fun-A	The system shall be able to capture high quality inspection data of defects.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
TG-FADR-02	Fun-NA	The system shall enable measurement of the tunnel diameter at requested locations.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
TG-FADR-03	Fun-NA	The system shall enable measurement of the length of inspected tunnel segments.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
TG-FADR-04	Fun-NA	The system shall enable measurement of the width of the paved road at requested locations.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
TG-FADR-05	Fun-A	Measurement of tunnel diameter deformation in tunnel slices	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	

9.3.2. Local Inspection

Table 47. Verification of the requirements for the tunnel local inspection.

Requirement ID	Req Group	Description	Verified in D7.4	Validation	Validation Explanation (If Partially or No)
TL-FNA-01	Fun-NA	The system must be able to inspect detailed defects of the whole tunnel length	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
TL-FNA-02	Fun-NA	Ground robot vehicle able to move on rough surfaces (asphalt, gravel, etc.)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
TL-FNA-03	Fun-NA	Ground robot vehicle able to move on tunnels partially merged by water	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
TL-FNA-04	Fun-NA	Ground robotic vehicle able to move with inclination	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
TL-FNA-05	Fun-NA	Ground robotic vehicle must be able to carry onboard safety lights and signs	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes	

			<input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
TL-FNA-06	Fun-NA	Aerial robot able to take high quality images at short distances of the defects	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
TL-FNA-07	Fun-NA	Aerial robot must be able to go to a specific location where a defect has been previously detected, and perform a detailed measurement of the crack length, width and orientation.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
TL-FNA-08	Fun-NA	Aerial robot able to mark specific points of the tunnel surface	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	Not necessary since it is known the exact position in the localization frame of the tunnel
TL-FNA-09	Fun-NA	Aerial robotic vehicle has to be contact proof (for example mechanical protection around propellers)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	Not implemented.
TL-FNA-10	Fun-NA	Batteries of the aerial robot must be protected against impacts	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	

TL-FNA-11	Fun-NA	The aerial robot must integrate the necessary sensors to detect any unexpected obstacle	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
TL-FA-01	Fun-A	Ground robotic vehicle able to navigate in GNSS-denied environments	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
TL-FA-02	Fun-A	Ground robotic vehicle wireless communication with control interface	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
TL-FA-03	Fun-A	Aerial robot able to navigate without GNSS	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
TL-FA-04	Fun-A	The aerial robot must take off and land autonomously	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
TL-FA-05	Fun-A	The aerial robot must be able to operate under "autopilot" mode where a path, previously planned, is automatically followed	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	

TL-Sys-01	Sys-Phy	The system size and weight must suite to be transported by truck	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
TL-Sys-02	Sys-Phy	The system size must suite to be used on a single lane	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
TL-Sys-03	Sys-Phy	Enough drone flying time for inspection	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
TL-Sys-04	Sys-Phy	Enough drone flying time for inspection	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
TL-Sys-05	Sys-Phy	Enough drone flying time for inspection	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
TL-Sys-06	Sys-Phy	Have a detailed plan for obtaining the permit to flight one year in advance of the experiments	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	

TL-Sys-07	Sys-Phy	The risk assessment must consider safety mitigations plan ahead and approved taking into consideration the possibility of collision with obstacles	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
TL-Sys-08	Sys-Phy	The risk assessment must consider safety mitigations plan ahead and approved taking into consideration the possibility of loss of communication	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
TL-Sys-09	Sys-Safety	Emergency shut down button on ground robotic vehicle	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
TL-Sys-10	Sys-Safety	Safe operation with the aerial robot	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
TL-Sys-11	Sys-Safety	Safe operation with the aerial robot	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	Tests were only performed in a tunnel without traffic. This is a COULD requirement.
TL-Sys-12	Sys-Safety	The aerial robotic system must incorporate a pure manual control mode to allow the pilot to take the control of the aerial robot in any case, moment and situation	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	

TL-Sys-13	Sys-Safety	Aerial robotic vehicle must be collision-proof (for example mechanical protection around propellers)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	
TL-Sys-14	Sys-Safety	The pilot interface of the aerial robot must show the needed information to have a simple, fast and clear situation awareness to decide on the safety of the operation at any time	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
TL-O-01	O	Ground robotic vehicle able to recharge batteries onsite	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
TL-O-02	O	Ground robotic vehicle able to inspect large parts of highway network	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
TL-O-03	O	Ground robotic vehicle able to inspect large parts of highway network	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
TL-O-04	O	Ground robotic vehicle able to inspect large parts of highway network	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	

TL-O-05	O	Inspection demonstration doable during the night	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
TL-O-06	O	Inspection doable with one lane open to traffic	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	This is a COULD requirement.
TL-FADR-01	Fun-A	Recording the position of all defects inspected in detail by the drone	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
TL-FADR-02	Fun-A	Ground robotic vehicle and drone position tracking at control station	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
TL-FADR-03	Fun-A	Aerial robot be able to see live video from an on-board camera	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	No cameras are used for streaming video purposes. It is a COULD requirement.
TL-FADR-04	Fun-A	Aerial robot be able to log HD images under operator demand	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	

<p>TL-FADR-05</p>	<p>Fun-A</p>	<p>The aerial robot system records and send in real time the sensor data collected</p>	<p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No</p>	<p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No</p>	
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10. Annex II: Generic safety template

In D10.7, we developed three general safety plans in Annex I (one for each type of robotic vehicle: UAVs, UGVs and crawlers due to their specificities in terms of safety).

However, during the final review meeting it was mentioned that it was necessary to complement this safety plans with a template to be used before the experiments.

Below it is the requested template.

Table 48. Generic safety template.

Generic safety template for PILOTING project		
Name:		
Last Name:		
Entity:		
Safety assessment before starting PILOTING experiments		
Have PILOTING robotic vehicles followed the generic safety plans (detailed in Annex I of D10.7)?	Yes:	No:
Potential risks for participants and mitigations during PILOTING experiments		
Risks for participants	Mitigations	
Description of Emergency Response Plan		
Type of emergency	Expected response	

Have you briefed participants about the possible risks during the experiments?	Yes:	No:
Have you been briefed about participants expected response in case of an accident during the experiments?	Yes:	No:
Date:	Signature:	

11. Annex III: Report on the impact of previous European projects into PILOTING

One of the key aspects for the very successful results in PILOTING have been the fact that a number of partners accumulated an important experience in robotics and AI applied to I&M gathered in previous FP7 and H2020 projects (see Table 49).

Table 49. European projects prior to PILOTING related to I&M and robotics and AI where previous partners participated.

Project	Scope	PILOTING partners that participated
ROBO-SPECT (FP7 CP, 2013-2016)	Contact inspection by ground robot in tunnels	ICCS, RBNK, EGNATIA
AEROBI (H2020 IA, 2015-2018)	Visual and contact inspection by aerial robots in viaducts	CATEC, USE, EGNATIA
RESIST (H2020, RIA, 2018-2022)	Visual and contact inspection by aerial robots in viaducts and tunnels	ICCS, CATEC, USE, EGNATIA
PETROBOT (FP7 CP. 2013-2016)	Wall thickness inspection in confined spaces using magnetic robotic crawlers in refineries	WTR, QUASSET, CHEVRON
AEROARMS (H2020 RIA, 2015-2019)	Contact inspection by aerial robot in refineries	USE, CATEC, WTR
HYFLIERS (H2020 RIA, 2018-2022)	Contact inspection of pipes by aerial robots in refineries	CHEVRON, USE, CATEC, WTR

As it can be observed in the above Table, eight of PILOTING partners (from a consortium of 13) already participated in European projects very much related with the use cases developed in PILOTING (viaducts, tunnels and refineries). In most of the cases they were RIA projects that targeted a lower TRL, and even the IA project (AEROBI) actually achieved lower TRL than PILOTING. Moreover, the rest of PILOTING partners already had some experience in the I&M sector:

- **APPLUS RVIS**: they are a service provider company for I&M.
- **FERROVIAL**: as end-user, they already have all the required experience for viaducts.
- **INLECOM**: the principal investigator of INLECOM was one of the researchers leading ROBO-SPECT project when he was part of ICCS at that time.
- **SINTEF**: technological center with experience in I&M sector, like for example in RIMA Network.
- **ETHZ**: they participated in European projects related with I&M like AEROWORKS

This previous experience accumulated by the consortium plus the background of technologies already developed in previous projects allowed to:

- Facilitate the communication between end-users and technological companies, research centers and universities. The end-users already knew the limitations of the current robotics technologies, so we could focus on realistic problems to be solved. And also technological companies, research centers and universities already knew the main problems of implementing robotics and AI in such use cases, and where we should focus the main technological efforts in order to make the robotics systems work robustly.
- PILOTING was built under the lessons learnt of previous experiences avoiding making the same mistakes and building upon the successful previous experiences. This allowed us to have functional systems quite fast and being able to focus, not in making work, but in increasing their TRL.
- Although in some cases, new robots have been developed from zero in PILOTING project, for others it has been used a previous developed robot that has been improved in PILOTING project. Being able to consolidate an existing technology and achieve a higher TRL.

All this allowed to make good design decisions, consolidate previous robotics technologies applied to I&M, and then have enough time during PILOTING project to make the robotic systems more robust and increase their TRL.

Also, all this accumulated experience allowed us to go step forward in the application to robotics to I&M, in comparison with previous projects, and **not only developed robots that collect data but to create complete digital inspection systems.**

As it can be seen in the above Table, some of the partners accumulated a decade of participation in robotics projects applied to I&M developing robotics solutions for similar use cases as the ones developed in PILOTING. This previous experience has been essential for the success of PILOTING project where we have reached a TRL 7 for most of the technologies.

In summary, we believe that the application of successful RIA project results into IA ones is a good practice that should be promoted by the European Commission. This will allow to maintain the same research line for a period of 8-10 years, permitting to increase the TRL of key technologies and demonstrating them in operational scenarios which facilitates its transfer to the industry. In fact, it could be good to create a new type of project (post-IA) that will provide support for the adaptation of technologies developed in IA projects to specific products or services. These could be smaller projects, just with a RTO, technological company and a potential end-user, that will take a technology developed in an IA project and create the basis for a future product or service. At least, from CATEC experience, it is not easy to execute this final stage (from TRL 7 to 8) only with private investment, and this new instrument could be very beneficial to being able to complete the transfer of technologies developed in European projects to the industry.